

**AN ASSESSMENT OF THE PRIVATE
HOUSEBUILDER'S PERFORMANCE FOR THE
BENEFITS OF SOCIETY AND THE ENVIRONMENT
AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE IN THE UK FROM
2010 TO 2020 – A STUDY OF FOUR CASES**

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of the University of the West of Scotland
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DECLARATION

I declare that this thesis has been composed solely by myself. It has not been submitted for any other degree or professional qualification except as specified. The work presented is entirely my own, except where it states otherwise by reference or acknowledgement.

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September 16, 2021

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ABSTRACT

The thesis assesses the four private housebuilders' non-financial performance for the benefits of society and the environment and their financial performance in the UK from 2010 to 2020. Based on the performance assessment, the thesis compares the financial and non-financial performance and discloses that the four private housebuilders served more social and environmental benefits than their business profits.

The thesis is taken via the deductive approach and the case study strategy. The private housebuilders of Barratt Developments, Persimmon, Bellway and Miller Homes, are selected as the target cases. The quantitative method is adopted for data collection and analysis. The online and offline questionnaire is randomly distributed to the customers (inhabitants) of the four private housebuilders. Furthermore, secondary data related to research questions are collected. The primary and secondary data are processed and analysed with the SPSS and Excel tools and descriptive statistics.

The research discussion realises the research objectives. Firstly, the four private housebuilders' performance for the benefits of society and the environment is assessed as neither satisfactory nor dissatisfactory. Secondly, the four housebuilder's financial performance is assessed as high or very high. Thirdly, the thesis concludes that the four housebuilder's financial performance surpass or far surpass the performance for the benefits of society and the environment, which proves the four housebuilders have more served their business profits than the social and environmental benefits. Finally, these research conclusions raise implications and recommendations for the four selected housebuilders, the

customers and other stakeholders in the housebuilding sector, and future research.

Keywords: Private Housebuilders; Performance Assessment; Triple Bottom Line;

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CHAPTER 1, INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research Background

The traditional approach was usually focused on financial performance in assessing business performance. Nevertheless, dynamic changes have happened in today's business world, along with which the importance of non-financial performance has been raised in business management (Narkunienė and Ulbinaitė, 2018). Accordingly, much literature has explored performance assessment in the broader range. With highlighting the corporate social responsibility (CSR), scholars included the CSR performance as a part of performance management and explored its relevant topics, like impacts of CSR practices on society and the environment, the outcomes of CSR practices (Bahurmoz, 2020, Derchi, Zoni and Dossi, 2020). According to the latest report of KPMG, about 80% of companies in the world monitor their social responsibility practices and performances and publish the corresponding reports along with the financial statements every year (Threlfall et al., 2020). In the real business context, many enterprises develop strategies and monitor the performance related to sustainable development goals (SDGs) and financial performance, covering 17 aspects to realise a better and more sustainable future (Olwig, 2021). Towards the sustainability target, the triple bottom line (TBL) framework suggests assessing business performance via three dimensions of economy, society and environment (Strezov, Evans and Evans, 2017). For the different enterprises, the specific performance metrics would be varied. TBL has been recommended as a relatively systematic approach to category these particular elements into three groups (Książak and Fischbach, 2017). The previous studies find that the conception and measurements of the non-financial performance would be varied in different theories. However, one typical feature is identified among a large proportion of literature that highlights

the performance in the social and environmental sector, which further explores the influence of business practices on creating the benefits of the society and environment (McElroy and Van Engelen, 2012, Eneizan et al., 2016, Markota Vukić, Vuković and Calace, 2018).

In performance management studies, the stakeholder theory is another typical approach. With realising the interrelated relationship between the enterprise and its diverse stakeholders, the stakeholder theory emphasises the interests of different stakeholders rather than only the shareholders, which provides one performance assessment of meeting stakeholders' needs or expectations (Laplume, Sonpar and Litz, 2008). The stakeholder approach would help identify the most critical elements by highlighting the specific stakeholder's interests (Clarkson, 1995). Therefore, to assess the non-financial business performance, the thesis would also highlight the perspective of the critical stakeholder and use it further refine the metrics for performance assessment.

In the UK, the government has paid greater attention to business impacts on the social and environmental dimensions; meanwhile, the enterprises have more valued and monitored the social and environmental performance. It is traced from the British Councils Global Social Enterprise programme, which aims to address the social and environmental problems and deliver positive changes to society via promoting more social enterprises. Besides, the UK government has decided to realise zero emission of greenhouse gas by 2050 (Sasse et al., 2020); therefore, some enterprises must report their environmental impacts (Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs, 2019).

According to the growing emphasises on the non-financial performance in both the academic area and the UK business context, the author believes that in

addition to the financial performance, the performance management of today's enterprises in the UK should value the interests of society and the environment, and care about the performance within the social and environmental dimensions at the same time, which is regarded as the main elements of the non-financial performance in this thesis. With these clues, one particular industry in the UK raises the authors interests.

The private housebuilding sector is one of the essential industries closely related to the inhabitants' daily lives and the UK's national economy. According to the latest economic footprint report, the housebuilding sector generated £38 billion of economic outputs to the UK economy, contributed £1.1 billion to the UK tax revenue, employed 239,000 people accounting for about 20% of the total employment in the UK construction sector (Home Builders Federation, 2018). Meanwhile, about 78% of newly built dwellings were provided by private housebuilders to the inhabitants from 2019 to 2020 (Ministry of Housing, Communities & Local Government, 2021). In addition to delivering the needed properties, the private housebuilders also affected the inhabitant's life via the investment in the local communities and environment, like the education facilities, sports and leisure facilities (Home Builders Federation, 2018). Considering the importance of the private housebuilding sector, it is not surprising that this sector has attracted significant attention from the government, professional bodies, academic scholars, the public and other stakeholders; meanwhile, many issues and evaluations about this sector have been raised. Within the social and environmental areas, the imbalance of housing supply and demand, the affordability and quality of a house, impacts on the environment are typical and widely concerned issues in the UK society.

Meanwhile, it is a controversial and hot topic when discussing private housebuilders' practices and performance. According to the above contents, the private housebuilders should be praised for their significant economic outputs. However, many negative comments have been put forward when searching the evaluations on the private housebuilders. For example, Khan (2017) regarded the private housebuilding sector as failing to build the properties needed. The private housebuilders were accused of deliberately building slowly to acquire juicy profits (The Economist, 2019). The construction activities of the private housebuilder have damaged the environment, like producing waste, GHG emission, generating dust (Marsh Commercial, 2021). Based on these understandings, the author then reviews the annual reports of the large private housebuilders in the UK and finds that most of them all highlights sustainable values for society, the environment and their customers. Therefore, financial and non-financial conceptions like sustainability, CSR, and social and environmental performance should be common among these large private housebuilders. However, the controversial discussions about the builders' performance, especially the non-financial performance, suggest that even though the private builders have put down their social, environmental and financial performance in reports, how the builders performed in the financial and non-financial areas is still a question.

According to the above research background, the author's research interests in the financial and non-financial performance of the private housebuilders in the UK are raised. Moreover, the following contents are presented: the rationale for conducting this study, the research aim and objectives, and research structures.

1.2 Research Rationale

The research rationale explains why the researcher is conducting this research with a specific topic (Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2018). For this study, the research rationale is illustrated from the research significance and the academic gap.

1.2.1 Research Significance

1.2.1.1 Why this Industry

In inhabitants' life, the property is a significant element; therefore, the issues about the residential property have raised a wide range of attention among inhabitants. In the government policies, many political, legal and financial actions have been developed to solve the housing issues, indicating the importance of the private housebuilding sector and the government's determination to improve this sector. Meanwhile, the capability of this industry to drive economic growth and improve sustainable communities also confirmed the significance of the private housebuilding sector in the UK (Home Builders Federation, 2018). According to the UK government, the issues about the residential house have been regarded as one of the most significant barriers to the development of Britain (Department for Communities and Local Government, 2017). Therefore, it is understandable that essential issues within this industry have been widely concerned in the UK.

Although moving beyond the shadow of the Financial Crisis, the housing building industry is still full of various uncertainties today, which raise the risks from the critical housing issues. For example, the Brexit event has affected the housebuilding sector and will bring more changes and impacts in the future (Eicheikh et al., 2020). The Covid-19 pandemic caused challenges and

opportunities for private housebuilders (Manjula Bai, 2020). Additionally, the economic factors, buyers' attitudes and needs, and climate changes also influence the housebuilding sector. Generally, the housebuilding industry is a sensitive sector to the external environment.

Given the high importance of the housebuilding sector, the housebuilders' practices and performance should affect the benefits of the country and inhabitants' life. Therefore, the performance assessment focusing on the housebuilding sector is not only about business profits the housebuilders have made but also to assess how well have the housebuilders have done to serve the benefits of the society and environment in the particular period. Besides, more uncertainties might be raised from the external environment for the housebuilding sector (Burke, 2020). It is necessary to build an in-depth understanding of how the housebuilders have performed in the last few years to deal with the possible challenges and improve the business performance in the future so that the well-founded predictions about the housebuilding sector and the practical solutions to the housing issues could be made.

1.2.1.2 Why the Sizeable Private Housebuilder

In the UK housebuilding sector, it is no doubt that private housebuilders have played a significant role. Especially from 1980, when the plan of Right to Buy was implemented, the housing supply of the private housebuilders has far surpassed other developers in the UK (Wellings, 2006). According to the new dwelling statistics, the private housebuilders have contributed about 78% of the housing supply (Ministry of Housing, Communities & Local Government, 2021), which means the market share of the private housebuilders should account for a more significant part of the UK housebuilding sector. Hence, the private housebuilders'

business practices and performance should affect the UK society and environment to a deeper and broader extent.

Moreover, the large housebuilders in the private sector mainly focus on the thesis. It is a noticeable phenomenon in the private housebuilding sector that the production and market share of the small and medium housebuilders has been shrunk, while the supply of prominent builders has been grown. According to Wellings (2006), the top ten housebuilders accounted for about 9% of the newly built dwellings in the 1960s; their supply increased to 46% by 2004. Furthermore, Lyons's study (2014) finds that about 10,000 SME (small and medium) housebuilders (refer to the builder with an annual supply below 500 units) were active and produced about 57% of the total housing supply in 1980. Nevertheless, the number of active SME housebuilders were only 2,800 and delivered 27% of newly built dwellings in 2014. This phenomenon means the inhabitants are more reliant on a small number of volume housebuilders than before; meanwhile, the large housebuilders' performance has a more significant influence on the society and environment than the SME builders.

Besides, different from the view reckoning housebuilders as the construction role, many private housebuilders in the contemporary housebuilding sector take multiple responsibilities, and the constructing work is only one part of these responsibilities (Wellings, 2006). In this thesis, the housebuilding project is explained to contain a long-term process from the land purchase and planning to the completion of sales, in which large private housebuilders are usually involved to a large extent. It means the large housebuilders have more opportunities than the role with single construction reasonability to create benefits for the society and environment via their business decisions and practices. Moreover, the large builders are supposed to have more advantages than the SME builders, like access

to loans and negotiation power in land planning (Federation of Master Builders, 2020), which are supposed to contribute to the more positive performance and impacts on society. Overall, given the role, business involvement and capacity, impact of the large private housebuilder in the UK housebuilding sector, it expects the study on the large housebuilders' performance should provide more valuable discussions to assess the private housebuilders' impacts on serving social and environmental benefits. Therefore, the thesis decides to take the large private housebuilders as the target cases.

1.2.1.3 Why this Topic

The research topic is designed to assess the private housebuilder's performance for the benefits of society and the environment (non-financial performance) and the business's profits (financial performance) and compare the non-financial and financial performance. The private housebuilder's efforts and performance within the social, environmental and economic areas will be examined via specific criteria. Then, a comparative analysis would be conducted based on the results to see the private housebuilders performed better for the benefits of society and the environment or their business profits.

The result would respond to the arguments about how well the private housebuilder performed in helping social and environmental benefits, solving social and environmental problems, and its business profit. Meanwhile, the research findings and discussions are expected to contribute to academic and practical areas.

On the one hand, the thesis would enrich the relevant literature of the performance assessment of the private housebuilders and provide one approach

for future studies to assess the performance of private housebuilders with different commercial sizes or during different periods.

On the other hand, by comparing the financial and non-financial performance of the four UK large private housebuilders, the thesis would help raise some recommendations to the four builders' business practices and decisions in the future. Also, the research findings and discussions would contribute practical implications to other housebuilders in the UK, like applying the performance assessment system in this thesis to their business, comparing their performance with the four national housebuilders, identifying their weak performance, which would help improve their both financial and non-financial performance. Moreover, the practical values of the thesis would be drawn for multiple stakeholders, like the inhabitants, local council and the public organisations in the UK. The research findings would enhance these stakeholders' understanding of the four large private housebuilders and help them improve the relevant decisions in their lives and works.

1.2.2 Academic Gaps

1.2.2.1 The Gap in the Research Topic

In addition to the practical values, the academic gap is another reason to do this thesis. As mentioned above, private housebuilders in the UK have received much attention, and many arguments about their performance have been raised. Based on these arguments, the author reviews a broader range of literature studying the UK housebuilding sector, and the first gap is identified among these studies.

The housebuilding industry in the UK has been changed a lot after the Second World War, in which housing supply, housing construction, raw material, sales and other aspects are different (Hashemi, 2013). Scholars have conducted many pieces of research and raised various findings and conclusions about the housebuilding sector in the UK. Some studies are designed from the historical perspective and explore the development history of the housebuilding industry. For example, Hashemi's paper (2013) comprehensively reviewed the British housing condition and the building process during the 20th century. Focusing on the completed residential properties, Muthesius (1984) published his book to explain the history, construction, architecture, demanding and supply of the terraced house. These studies have presented the historical profile of the British housebuilding industry. Furthermore, for the UK housebuilding industry since the millennium, many pieces of research have been done with highlighting the impact of the Global Financial Crisis on the housebuilders' business and their recovery process from the crisis, like Whitehead and Williams (2011) explained the housebuilding system after the crisis, Duca, Muellbauer and Murphy (2010) examined the lesson for the housing market during 2007 to 2009. Furthermore, from the middle of the 2010s, when most housebuilders have recovered from the crisis, researchers have shown more interest in studying the backgrounds of the UK private housebuilding sector and some critical issues during that period. For example, Aubrey (2015) explained the challenges disturbing the acceleration of the housing supply; Siebert et al. (2018) found out the barriers to changes in the UK housebuilding sector; Payne et al. (2019) also analysed the influence of the land supply system on the UK speculative housebuilding business. These studies explain the specific issues like housing supply and housing price in the UK housebuilding sector, providing a comprehensive understanding of the significant elements relating to inhabitants' benefits. In addition, a few studies are focused on the urgency of the green target, innovation in zero carbon homes and other topics

related to the environment and property. Hertin and her colleagues (2003) explore the impact of climate changes on the housebuilding industry and the housebuilders' conception and adaptive capacity towards environmental changes. Jones and Comfort (2020) discuss the sustainable development goals of the largest volume housebuilders in the UK. This study explains the builders' SDGs but does not further analyse the corresponding efforts and performance towards these SDGs. The author's knowledge about the significant environmental issues within the UK housebuilding sector is enriched with these studies.

In summary, the existing research in the housebuilding industry covers the historical development, the explanations of the external context, the clarification of key housing issues, and the analysis of some influences on the housebuilding industry, which are no doubt contributions to the academic achievements in this industry. Although the existing studies have covered a broad range of topics, few studies have been done to study the private housebuilders' performance in serving social and environmental benefits. Only studies of Archer and Cole (2016, 2021) are identified to examine the financial performance of the UK's top housebuilders since the 2010s. However, one methodological limitation of their study is also highlighted, which is explained in the following section. Moreover, none of the studies is identified to compare the private housebuilders' performance contributing to the social and environmental benefits and financial performance. Therefore, the first academic rationale for this thesis is to fill the gap of lacking studies analysing and comparing the housebuilders' performance in highlighting the social and environmental benefits and own financial profits.

1.2.2.2 The Gap in the Theoretical Framework

The second gap is about the theoretical framework to assess the private housebuilders' financial and non-financial performance considering the particular external context, stakeholder and timeline. Towards sustainability, TBL is a typical framework to evaluate the enterprise performance within the economic, social and environmental dimensions. However, one limitation of the TBL framework is mentioned by scholars that lots of elements are included in the three dimensions of TBL, and it is not very easy to use all the elements to assess the performance. Therefore, the TBL framework without refining the metrics in the three dimensions would not be applicable in this research with the restrictions of time and resources and not practical for the private housebuilders.

Therefore, another gap is found: no fitted theoretical framework is available to assess the private housebuilders' performance in the UK. Before determining the private housebuilders' social, environmental and financial performance, a theoretical framework highlighting the research objectives needs to be developed in advance.

1.2.2.3 The Gap in Research Methodology

One research gap in research methodology was mentioned by the scholar Fred Welling, who published a book to explain and analyse the history of housebuilders in the UK. Wellings (2006) emphasised that many studies have been conducted based on the abundant statistics of housing stocks, annual completions, housing prices, housing design, which have provided a credible source of data. However, Wellings (2006) also noticed that few pieces of research on private housebuilders in the UK had been conducted using the primary data. After identifying this research gap, Wellings (2006) has taken his study based on abundant facts and

primary data of the housebuilders and provided an in-depth explanation of the development of the private housebuilders in the UK. However, Wellings's (2006) study focused on a particular period from the first World War to 2004. Since then, none of the research has been found to analyse the private housebuilders' behaviours and performance with adequate primary data. For example, in Archer and Cole's (2014, 2016, 2021) studies on the private housebuilders' financial performance, only the statistics, like revenue profit before tax, were extracted from the housebuilders' annual report, and no primary data is involved in their studies. Hence, the author realises that the methodological gap lacking primary data still exists in the research on analysing the private housebuilders' behaviours and performance since 2010. Although many studies in the housebuilding sector have been well supported by the national databases, the academic values and possible results from the research based on the primary data might be neglected. Hence, the author decides to collect and analyses the primary data to answer the research questions in this thesis, so that it is expected to help narrow down the methodological gap of lacking the primary data among the literature on the housebuilding sector from 2010. Meanwhile, the values of the secondary data have been recognised by the previous literature, therefore the thesis would also use some secondary data to consolidate the research analysis and discussion on the primary findings, which would help raise the highly trusted and traceable conclusions for both the readers and the academic area.

1.3 Research Aims, Objectives and Questions

This thesis aims to assess and compare the large private housebuilders' performance for the benefits of society and the environment (non-financial performance) and the business profits (financial performance) from 2010 to 2020 in the UK. Then, a conclusion about whether the housebuilders have more served

the social and environmental benefits or the business profits, or equally served both, would be drawn based on the comparative analysis of the builders' social, environmental performance and the financial performance. It should be noticed that the performance for the benefit of society and the environment is regarded as a whole in this thesis because both the human community and the natural environment are essential parts of the UK society.

The performance of different housebuilders could be varied based on the company profile, like the stage of business development, company size, leader's preference. Therefore, instead of assessing the housebuilders' performance generally in the UK industrial range and raising the generalised conclusion for all the private builders, the author decides to take the case study approach and focus on four particular private housebuilders. The research findings and conclusions are expected to be creditable and valuable for the specific housebuilders or builders with similar profiles.

The individual objectives would be realised step by step to realise the research aim. Firstly, the thesis objective is to assess the selected private housebuilders' performance for the benefits of society and the environment in the UK from 2010 to 2020. Then another objective is to evaluate the four private housebuilders' financial performance in the UK from 2010 to 2020. Based on the above performance assessment, the difference between the non-financial performance for the benefits of society and the environment, and financial performance is disclosed to realise another objective that has the four private housebuilders more served the social and environmental benefits or their financial target in the UK from 2010 to 2020.

According to the above research rationale, one research gap is the lack of a fitted theoretical framework for performance assessment in the UK housebuilding sector, which needs to be developed before realising the above objectives. The TBL framework considering three dimensions is regarded as a theoretical foundation to fill this research gap and develop a theoretical framework for this thesis. A wide range of literature would be reviewed in the second and third chapters so that a framework for assessing the performance for the benefits of society and the environment and the financial performance would be developed to realise the research objectives. Moreover, the specific performance criteria for the UK housebuilding sector after the 2010s would also be refined.

The research questions are developed as follows, focusing on the objectives regarding the performance assessment.

Research question 1: How is the four private housebuilders' performance for serving the benefits of society and the environment in the UK from 2010 to 2020?

Research question 2: How is the four private housebuilders' financial performance in the UK from 2010 to 2020?

Research question 3: What is the difference between the four private housebuilders' performance for serving the benefits of society and the environment and their financial performance in the UK from 2010 to 2020?

1.4 Structure of the Thesis

The thesis is structured with seven chapters of introduction, literature review on theoretical frameworks, literature review on the UK housebuilding sector,

research methodology, research findings, research discussion, research conclusions.

In the first chapter, the research background about the growing importance of non-financial performance and the relevant theories, the UK housebuilding sector, the practical and academic rational explanation for conducting this research, research aims, objectives and questions, and the research structures are included.

The second chapter is developed to build a theoretical framework for this thesis. The three theories of CSR, TBL and stakeholder theory, are firstly reviewed. With the three theories, the author confirms the specific metrics, identifies the critical stakeholder and formulates an applicable framework for the performance assessment.

Then, the development of the UK private housebuilding sector and private housebuilders are included. After a brief history of the housebuilding sector, the significant issues, general development, and the relevant external context of the UK private housebuilding sector are elaborated. This part helps build a better understanding of the research target and further confirm the criteria in the above performance assessment framework, making this framework more fitted and practical for the UK private housebuilders. Also, the profile of the selected private housebuilders is presented.

The fourth chapter is the research methodology part, which explains the research approach, research hypothesis, research strategy, research method of data collection and data analysis. In this part, the reason and the approach of taking the deductive approach, adopting the case study strategy, selecting the four cases,

using the quantitative methods, collecting and analysing the quantitative data are interpreted in-depth.

In the chapter on research findings, the collected primary and secondary data are authentically presented and processed with the analytical tool. The research findings help test the hypotheses. Furthermore, in the research discussion chapter, the author compares the four housebuilders' performance for serving the benefits of society and the environment (the performance within the social and environmental dimension), and their financial performance, and finally, answer the research questions.

The last chapter firstly summarises the above contents of the above chapters, concludes the research questions, and emphasises the research contributions. Then some recommendations and limitations are explained based on the whole research journal.

CHAPTER 2, LITERATURE REVIEW ON THEORETICAL FRAMEWORKS

2.1 Introduction

As mentioned in the first chapter, the thesis is designed to assess and compare the private housebuilder's performance for the benefits of society and the environment, and the financial performance in the UK from 2010 to 2020. A wide selection of literature is reviewed, including the theoretical knowledge of corporate social responsibility (CSR), Triple Bottom Line (TBL), and stakeholder theory focusing on the research aim and questions. Firstly, the conception of CSR explains why the enterprise should consider the benefits for society and the environment, and how the enterprise would create these benefits via the CSR practice. Then, the TBL framework, three TBL dimensions, evaluation on TBL is reviewed, providing an academic foundation for the author to develop a performance assessment framework for this study. Finally, the author examines the stakeholder theory. The customer (inhabitant) of the private housebuilding companies is highlighted as this stakeholder provides a significant and typical perspective to assess the builders' performance in serving the social benefits in the thesis. From the standpoint of inhabitants, the metrics to evaluate the social performance in this thesis are confirmed. Based on the literature review, a performance assessment framework to assess the performance for the benefits of society and the environment, and the financial performance is finally proposed.

2.2 Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)

It is widely accepted that the private enterprise is profit-driven; therefore, it is common for an enterprise to assess the performance in creating business profits.

Meanwhile, the benefits of society and the environment have been more and more emphasised by today's enterprises. The CSR conceptions are usually mentioned in literature about creating benefits for society and the environment. Before confirming the theoretical models of assessing the companies' performance for the benefits of society and the environment, the CSR conception and feature, practices and approaches, and possible CSR constraints that would influence the performance for the benefits of the society and the environment are firstly reviewed.

2.2.1 Conceptions of CSR

2.2.1.1 CSR Conception before the 21st Century

The CSR term was widely accepted as a product in the 20th century, especially from the 1950s. Furthermore, Howard Bowen's explanation about social responsibility has been regarded as the start of literature in the CSR subject (Agudelo, Jóhannsdóttir and Davídsdóttir, 2019). Bowen (2013) regarded CSR as the businessmen's obligation to follow the policy and make the desirable decision to realise society's objectives, values, and environment. Bowen's CSR views might not be concrete and always fit in the development of the business world, but it still points out the core and essence of CSR, which has been followed by research subsequently. As Carroll (2008) said, Bowen's ideas about CSR was ahead of his time because he identified a new approach to business management that improves the awareness about the social impacts of the business.

Furthermore, after reviewing the different CSR definitions since the 1950s, it finds that the definition of CSR has been marked by times. Researchers tend to take CSR to respond to the problems in different periods or the possible problems in the

coming times. Moreover, some researchers raised more specific elements to realise the objectives and values of society and the environment. For example, with the growing culture about civil rights and anti-war in the 1960s, Davis (1960) included economic development and human values as the obligation of the business. Furthermore, McGuire (1963) suggested that CSR should focus on the interests of politics, community welfare, education and happiness of employees. Moreover, with the awareness of environmental issues since the 1980s, CSR researchers have emphasised business impacts on the natural environment (Carroll, 2008). According to Agudelo, Jóhannsdóttir and Davídsdóttir (2019), the CSR contents are highly affected by the factors in an external context. Furthermore, as time goes by, the changes in CSR conceptions are understandable. The academic mainstreams of the CSR subject during the 21st century are reviewed, considering the target period in this research.

2.2.1.2 CSR Conception in the 21st Century

To do something good, Kotler and Lee (2005, p3) regard CSR as “a commitment that improves the well-being in communities via the discretionary business practices and contributions of corporate resources”. The discretionary feature is highlighted in this explanation, and only the business practices and contributions made voluntarily are included. However, this feature is controversial among researchers, as it excludes the practices that are naturally ethical or regulated by laws but beneficial to society (McWilliams, 2015). Therefore, some CSR definitions do not mention the discretionary feature. From the perspective of economic development, The World Business Council for Sustainable Development (2016) defines the commitment in business that contributes to the economic development sustainably with ethical behaviours and improving the life quality of the employees and their families, the local communities and the broad society. The

organisation of Business for Social Responsibility describes CSR as a business operation manner or commitment that meets or surpasses the legal, moral, commercial, public, and other societal expectations (Fontaine, 2013). According to the Commission of the European Communities (2006), CSR is “a management concept whereby companies integrate social and environmental concerns in their business operations and interactions with their stakeholders” and about enterprises go beyond the minimum legal requirements and obligations to help “reconcile the economic, social and environmental ambitions”. These explanations have been popular in CSR studies since the 21st century. Although with different descriptions, most conceptions try to cover the dimensions of society (or people) and environment.

2.2.1.3 CSR Conception and Implementation in the UK

Within the UK, CSR has been paid great attention by the government, which has actively revised and promoted the conception of CSR within a broader sector to enhance the relationship between the UK society, environment and market. According to the government’s updates on the CSR report, CSR is defined as the business behaviours that are out of the essential legal compliance and implemented with the consideration of their economic, social and environmental influences, and aims to highlight the main sustainable development issues (Government CSR, 2008). The CSR in the UK highlights business impacts on the economy, society and environment, and the business behaviours regulated by the essential legal compliance do not belong to CSR, which is similar to Kotler and Lee’s CSR view.

The specific CSR practice has been extended from donations to a broader range of contributions (PwC, 2016; Vistry Group, 2020). According to Companies House

(2018), four key aspects covered by the CSR activities in today's UK is highlighted: environment, people, procurement and community. Furthermore, these CSR activities are expected to consider a business's social, economic, and environmental impacts and be good for the customers, communities, and employees (Companies House, 2018). The four aspects of CSR help build a better understanding of the CSR focuses and behaviours of the enterprises in the UK.

2.2.1.4 Implications from the CSR Conception

Based on the explanation of CSR from the 1950s till today, several critical points of CSR conception are summarised.

Firstly, the CSR term has been developed to a management approach for business, which means a higher interaction between CSR purpose and business behaviours and decisions. As a result, the CSR approach confirms the role of companies in society, which could help with the problems and create values for society and the environment (Van Marrewijk, 2003; Carroll, 2008). By taking CSR as one management approach, the private housebuilders would decide whether to take CSR and how to implement the CSR with a certain autonomy, influencing the benefits of society and the environment.

Secondly, CSR practices should meet or surpass the legal requirements, which scholars have not agreed on. Nevertheless, CSR behaviour is defined out of legal compliance in the UK. Therefore, only the CSR efforts out of legal compliance would be discussed when assessing the private housebuilders' performance for the benefits of society and the environment.

Thirdly, CSR behaviours have been changed in responding to problems at different times. Although CSR usually emphasises the values in the social and environmental sections simultaneously, the significant interests and issues within the social and environmental sections in the particular period and industry could be different. This point highlights the importance of assessing performance within the social and environmental sections, which is in line with the contents of the TBL framework. Also, this point suggests the author assess the private housebuilders' social and environmental performance with considering the particular background of the UK housebuilding sector since the 21st century. Then it helps propose the applicable metrics in the performance assessment.

Fourthly, sustainable development is one of the CSR targets in the UK business, which encourages the business owner to solve the sustainable development issues. The sustainability target lets the CSR plans focus on the essential points in the UK and brings new CSR behaviours contributing to sustainable development.

For this thesis, the author suggests one definition of CSR. CSR is a business management approach that the private housebuilders operate the business with considering the impacts on the interests and issues within the British social and environmental section and take a set of CSR practices out of the basic legal requirements to contribute to the sustainability of the UK society.

Regarding the non-financial performance assessment, CSR can also be regarded as one of the approaches that discloses what and how well the private housebuilders have done to serve the social and environmental benefits.

2.2.2 CSR Role in the Housebuilding Sector

2.2.2.1 Strategic Role

The strategic feature of CSR is much evident in the 21st- century studies. From the perspective of stakeholders, Smith (2001) regards CSR as an obligation of companies to the stakeholders, as the values of these stakeholders would be affected by CSR practices. To meet the expectations of multiple stakeholders, CSR has been improved to a strategic level within the internal management. Based on Smith's view, Lantos (2001) confirms the strategic value of CSR when the CSR decisions consider the balance of returns to finance and the environment. Furthermore, from the perspective of brand management, a transformation of CSR from a "minimum commitment" to a "strategic necessity" is highlighted (Werther and Chandler 2005, p.319), as it would help maintain the brand legitimacy in the market.

Therefore, it is not surprising that CSR has been included in business strategy. The Department of Trade and Industry even regarded CSR as an "indispensable component of modern business management" (Department of Trade and Industry, 2002, p2), which is closely related to "build brand value, foster customer loyalty, motivate their staff and contribute to a good reputation among a wide variety of stakeholders" (Adams, Payne and Watkins, 2008, p2). A good combination of social responsibilities and business strategy would be helpful to improve the sales, brand reputation, public image, which further contributes to the long-term development (Yuan, Bao and Verbeke, 2011).

Many housebuilding companies have placed CSR at a fundamental level in their business management by realising the CSR practices' strategic values. In an early study, Jones, Comfort and Hillier (2006) mentioned that large companies within

the housebuilding sector have already been keen to communicate their CSR strategies with the shareholders, customers, employees and governments. Furthermore, till today, more large housebuilders have introduced their CSR practices and progress in the annual report.

2.2.2.2 Sustainable Role

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) was raised in 2015 by the United Nations, which aim to realise a more sustainable future for all human beings (United Nations, 2017). Furthermore, till today, 17 specific elements are included in the SDGs. With the growing highlights on SDGs, a positively interacted relation between SDGs and CSR has been identified. The SDGs have served as a reference framework for CSR decisions. In return, the individual companies' CSR practices have made contributions to the global sustainability agenda at the same time (Schönherr, Findler and Martinuzzi, 2017, Pedersen, 2018). Many builders have also linked their CSR plans to the SDGs in the housebuilding sector. Although the efforts towards SDGs have been varied, some specific SDGs are mainly cared for by most housebuilders: good health and well-being, decent work and sustainable economic growth, sustainable cities and communities, climate action (Jones and Comfort, 2020), which indicates the sustainable target focusing by the CSR strategy in today's housebuilding sector.

2.2.3 Constraints of CSR in the Housebuilding Sector

According to the above literature review, the critical role of CSR has been highlighted in diverse businesses, including the housebuilding sector. Nevertheless, it should be admitted that some issues relating to the CSR process have arisen simultaneously. The possible constraints of the CSR progress are

reviewed to critically assess the private housebuilders' performance for society and the environment's benefits.

The first CSR constraint in the UK housebuilding sector is the disproportionate influence of builders on the social and environmental benefits. There is a feature that the speculative supply of newly completed homes is dominated by a small number of large housebuilders in the private housebuilding sector. In 1980, about 24 significant housebuilders produced more than 500 units and occupied the 39% market share. In 2000, such housebuilders delivered 43% of total completions, and their market share was raised to 71% (Adams, Payne and Watkins, 2008). It proves the supply and capital concentrated on the few large housebuilders. Therefore, a relatively small number of housebuilders needed to be persuaded to take the CSR and realise a disproportionate influence in the housebuilding sector (Adams, Payne and Watkins, 2008). The sustainable economic growth and housing price inflation in the 2000s before the financial crisis let housebuilders achieve outstanding sales and profits. Fraser-Andrews (2004) also agreed that the early 2000s had witnessed the boom and realised similar profit performance as 1980. Based on the generous benefits, Adams, Payne and Watkins (2008) mentioned it is reasonable for housebuilders to give more consideration to CSR issues.

Although the significant housebuilders at the national level have seriously considered CSR and developed the corresponding strategies and plans leading to social benefits, the private housebuilders' participation in CSR has been slow. This CSR participation of the private housebuilders also results from the long-established organisation, business operation process and culture (Adams, Payne and Watkins, 2008). About this result, Wellings's research (2006) brought an implication that the dominant persons in the successful housebuilding companies

have their management experience entirely in the housebuilding sector instead of across different sectors.

Another reason that might constraint housebuilders' CSR performance is the critical material of the housebuilding process, land, which directly influences the housing construction and supply (Barker, 2004). Adams, Payne and Watkins (2008) highlighted that the housebuilding business's core is the land rather than customer or community orientation. Therefore, about the CSRs that could not contribute to land bank and company profits, housebuilders might hesitate to realise them.

2.2.4 Influence of CSR

When companies take CSR, two aspects are mostly affected. One aspect is the company itself, and another aspect is about the society, which includes people's well-being, economic development, environmental protection and other relevant matters.

2.2.4.1 Influence on the Business Itself

It is found that the good CSR strategy makes contributions to the brand recognition, brand reputation, and public image, which finally be good for business profits (Department for Business Innovation & Skills, 2014). As the CSR study on the global companies reported (CONE Communication, 2015), about 84% of customers would like to opt the socially responsible products whenever possible, and 90% of customers would boycott a company with irresponsible or immoral business practices. Most consumers expect companies to address the social and environmental issues in their business operations instead of only

focusing on making the business profit (CONE Communication, 2015). Therefore, CSR is one of the essential elements that affect customers' attitudes, initial evaluation, purchase decisions and the recommendation after purchase (Wu and Wang, 2014).

In the housebuilding sector, customers need to consider lots of factors when they decide on purchasing a property, in which the housing affordability and housing quality might be more important than others (Koklic and Vida, 2009). The positive CSR performance of private housebuilders is expected to raise customers' confidence and trust when they assess the property product. Besides, offering the property products meeting or surpassing customers' needs aligns with one CSR's purpose: to solve social problems and raise benefits for people. Therefore, a good CSR reputation works like an intangible advertisement to build a responsible image among the existing residents and the potential buyers.

Meanwhile, CSR would improve the evaluation among local councils and local communities by raising the brand values. From the local authorities' perspective, they would like to see the business that could bring economic and social benefits to the local community. Therefore, the private housebuilders with high CSR intentions would enhance the relationship with the local authorities, which means they might acquire better support from land bidding to after-sales service (Pornpratang, Lockard and Ngamkroeckjoti, 2013). Also, the CSR reputation of housebuilding companies would affect the cost of bank loans. Furthermore, the company with a worse CSR score would pay up to 20 basis points more than the company with a higher CSR score (Goss and Roberts, 2011).

Then the CSR can increase the employee's engagement and satisfaction. The employee engagement study found that companies' social and environmental

commitment would drive employee recruitment and retention, especially among the mature Millennial employees aged 27-35. In the report, about 55% of people decided to work for a socially responsible company despite less salary, and this proportion of the mature Millennial group reached 79% (CONE Communications, 2016). In nature, people want to work for a company with a responsible initiative and a good brand reputation. In this kind of company, the reasonable social responsibilities embedded in the company value, strategy or culture indicate sustainable development, matching employee development needs (Slack, Corlett and Morris, 2015). For private housebuilders, skill shortage has been a severe issue, especially after the Brexit, making employee retention more crucial. Therefore, CSR could be an approach to retain skilled labours in housebuilding companies. This influence of CSR is not only on the internal employees but also on the sub-contractors in their construction process. An exemplary implementation of CSR, especially in the construction stage, would enhance the relationship and sustainable cooperation between the housebuilding companies and contractors (Zhao et al., 2016).

However, one disadvantage of CSR is identified, simultaneously, that CSR could be a financial pressure for companies. When integrating CSR plans with business management, a set of costs, like operation and production, might be increased. As a result, companies might need to sacrifice some profits, which would raise investors' dissatisfaction. Otherwise, companies might raise the product price, which would trigger uncertainties in sales and put the business in an unfavourable place (Książak, 2016). In addition, Škare and Golja (2014) also highlighted that CSR might impair business performance as managers need to consider a wide range of goals. Nevertheless, this disadvantage is argued, and some scholars regarding CSR as an investment believed that a good CSR strategy would finally transfer the cost into a more significant return, like growth in sales, brand values

and employee engagements as the above contents mentioned (Fauzi and Idris, 2009).

2.2.4.2 Influence on Society

In addition to the influence on the business itself, CSR is supposed to contribute to society's values. As Perry and Towers (2013) highlighted, offering benefits to society should be the primary driver for companies to start their CSR behaviours. The purpose of CSR well demonstrates the expected influences on society, like philanthropic giving, environmental sustainability, ethical business practice, sustainable economic development, volunteer efforts and good community (Carroll, 2015).

With the CSR practices of reducing the carbon emission and waste in the supply chains, using renewable resources and raising energy efficiency, companies help with the environmental problems and boost environmental sustainability. By donations, companies support the charities and help the needy, and the local communities raise the locals' wellbeing (Carroll and Buchholtz, 2008). The CSR plan also lets companies reduce product defects in the production stage. As a result, this CSR practice reduces the costs caused by defects and customer complaints, contributing to customer satisfaction. CSR also helps protect employees' rights and interests via providing the workplace, training, compensation and others as required. This CSR effort decreases unemployment and raises populations' knowledge and skills (Księżak, 2016). Although few studies ever found the negative influence of CSR on society and the environment, scholars still warned against the hypocrisy of CSR. Some companies disguise the CSR slogan but create few benefits to society, in which CSR tends to work as a public relations approach (Banerjee, 2014, Księżak, 2016).

2.2.5 Summary

The literature review on CSR is an initial stage of understanding the private housebuilders' performance and practices for the social and environmental benefits and building the theoretical framework for assessing the private builder's performance. The theoretical explanation regarding CSR helps the author and readers develop a better understanding of the CSR practices in the real business world and identify the significant CSR practices of the private housebuilders in the UK. Also, the features and influence of CSR prove that private housebuilders can create benefits for society and the environment via taking CSR. When assessing the private housebuilders' performance for the benefits of society and the environment, the corresponding CSR rationale and prices would be discussed, which would provide practical shreds of evidence for their performance. A dissatisfactory performance assessment of the private housebuilders for the benefits of society and the environment might result from the failures of the CSR implementation.

2.3 Triple Bottom Line (TBL)

2.3.1 TBL Explanation

The term Triple Bottom Line was coined by John Elkington in 1994 to advance his sustainability study. Elkington (1994, p397) explained that sustainable development includes the "pursuit of economic prosperity, environmental quality and social equity" simultaneously. In the traditional business performance measurement, finance and profits used to be highlighted and often regarded as the only bottom line. Nevertheless, Elkington (1994) indicated that companies

pursuing business sustainability need to act against the three bottom lines rather than the financial bottom line. Beyond the existing explanations of sustainable development and CSR, Elkington (1998) described the TBL as an integrated method highlighting the economic, social and environmental performance in business management. Furthermore, in Elkington's definition, the economic, social and environmental lines were referred to as profit, people and planet, respectively (Elkington, 1998).

Before the 1990s, TBL was barely known by scholars. Since then, scholars have contributed more explanations about this framework. The TBL is regarded as a method to measure business performance and success via the environmental, social and financial perspectives (Goel, 2010). Slaper and Hall (2011) defined TBL as an accounting framework incorporating three dimensions of performance: finance, society and environment. After reviewing some TBL definitions, their essence is similar and consistent with Elkington's view despite different phrases. First of all, the TBL framework has taken sustainable development as the top goal. Then, the economic, social and environmental elements are indispensable, and none of them could be neglected to realise the sustainable dream. The specific indicators within the economic, social and environmental dimensions would be referred to Henriques (2010), Rogers and Hudson (2011) to measure the business performance and success towards sustainability.

Thirdly, scholars used the Venn diagram to draw the TBL framework (Figure 1). Sustainability is positioned at the overlap of the three elements. Ideally, sustainability would be realised when the three elements are considered (Rogers and Hudson, 2011).

Figure 1. TBL framework (Rogers and Hudson, 2011)

2.3.2 The Relationship between CSR and TBL

According to the above explanation of CSR and TBL, a shared premise for CSR and TBL is found that enterprises' considerations only on the financial performance and impacts are not enough. Therefore, both theories suggest emphasising the performance within the whole society. The target of TBL is to realise sustainable development while CSR aims to make contributions to society as a whole, which are essentially similar in terms of being beneficial to society and the environment. Based on the commons highlighting the social and environmental performance other than only the financial performance, some scholars identified a close relationship between CSR and TBL (Żak, 2015, Księżak and Fischbach, 2017, Hussain, Rigoni and Orij, 2018).

Księżak and Fischbach (2017) took TBL as a classification of CSR to present the key areas, but some scholars did not accept it because the three perspectives of TBL were too general. As mentioned above, the CSR plan usually covers a broad range of topics and specific behaviours (Carroll, 2008); therefore, many individuals and groups are affected. From the classification perspective, TBL has been a systematic approach to divide these CSR practices and influences into three

groups: economic, social or environmental sectors (Księżak and Fischbach, 2017), which is accepted by this thesis. Furthermore, for Žak (2015), TBL was regarded as one of the foundations of CSR and could be adopted to analyse the business practices and performance towards sustainability. This view is similar to Hourneaux Jr, da Silva Gabriel and Gallardo-Vázquez's (2018) conclusion and supported by some scholars focusing on the particular industries (Azevedo and Barros, 2017, Lim and Biswas, 2018). To realise the benefits of society and the environment, the conception of CSR introduces a broad range of practices. Furthermore, based on the relation between CSR and TBL, these CSR practices could be categorised by the three dimensions of TBL. Moreover, TBL is regarded as a foundation for the theoretical framework in this research.

2.3.3 Critical Evaluation of the TBL framework

2.3.3.1 Advantages

In addition to the TBL definition and its relation with CSR, this framework's advantages also explain why TBL is taken as an academic foundation in this study.

The purpose of the TBL theory is favourable, which tries to realise the sustainable development of business and society at the same time. Considering the community's economic, social and environmental interests, companies have made contributions to the sustainable agenda via taking the TBL framework. This positive side has been confirmed by many scholars who explained the influences of TBL in the real business world. For example, Porter and Van der Linde (1995) found that by taking the practices towards environmental protection, the chemical companies have acquired more paybacks; Wilson (2015) also confirmed

companies' sustainable progress under the TBL framework via examining in the retailing sector.

In addition, TBL is also praised as an approach to measure business performance. In terms of sustainable development, researchers had different emphasises. For example, some researchers take sustainability as an environmental requirement (Yan, Chen and Chang, 2009), and some scholars regard sustainability as a topic focusing on the societal area (Alhaddi, 2015). Compared to these views, TBL presents a more balanced, coherent and holistic approach to sustainability by simultaneously focusing on the three bottom lines (Elkington, 1998, Epstein, 2008, Alhaddi, 2015, Purvis, Mao and Robinson, 2019).

2.3.3.2 Limitations

However, TBL is not perfect, and scholars also have raised some criticisms about this approach. To reduce or eliminate the negative impacts on the research conclusion caused by TBL's shortcomings, the literature providing the corresponding solutions is also reviewed.

Sridhar and Jones (2013) regarded the complication of TBL measurement as one drawback, especially in measuring social performance. Norman and Macdonald (2015) and Robins's (2006) study also mentioned that it is hard to quantify the indicators within the social dimension, like reputation, customer loyalty, public awareness. Meanwhile, TBL does not provide a specific method or formula to define the business performance within the three dimensions. Based on Elkington's claims about TBL, Sridhar and Jones (2013) also mentioned that it would be possible to quantify the economic and environmental performance, while it would not be easy to quantify the social performance of TBL. Similar to

CSR criticism, scholars also mentioned another criticism about the challenges of replacing the single economic target with the three different targets of TBL. Multiple objectives and stakeholders need to be considered, which would cause a burden and low efficiency for a company.

This study agrees with the criticism that no common system of TBL measurement (indicators) cannot be applied to every business, and it is not easy to quantify social performance. Many remarkable performance measurement frameworks cannot fit all companies with one system. Nevertheless, the TBL can be an efficient tool for performance assessment in this study. Sridhar and Jones (2013, p91) were concerned about the conservative measurement of social impacts because “institutions are constantly changing and improving”. Furthermore, thoughtful consideration of the specific circumstances of the particular industry or company might avoid this limitation, which is proved by the application of TBL in the study focusing on the particular case or industry (Stoddard, Pollard and Evans, 2012, Morioka and Carvalho, 2016, He et al., 2017). In other words, this study believes the three dimensions of TBL are necessary for sustainable development and appropriate for assessing company performance, while the core elements within the three dimensions could vary based on the particular industrial context. This thesis will examine the private housebuilding industry in the third chapter to ensure the TBL framework is feasible and implementable in assessing the performance of private housebuilders. With the analysis of the industry, it is expected to identify the quantitative metrics to assess the social performance of the private housebuilders.

In addition, the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) has been discussed a lot to clarify the specific indicators (core, additional and sector-specific) for measurement. Although agreeing with this solution, Sridhar and Jones (2013) were still

concerned about how to decide the core and additional metrics as it could be varied based on different industries or even companies. The GRI gives relatively holistic metrics to assess performance in sustainability, which has been regarded as the most widely accepted framework for business sustainability. According to the KPMG sustainability survey result in 2020, about three-quarters (73%) of the world's largest 250 companies' sustainability reports follow the GRI standards (Threlfall et al., 2020). Nevertheless, no research and the GRI system itself has ever required that companies examine every indicator of GRI. Overall, to overcome the limitations of TBL, this research will review the background of the private housebuilding industry in the UK and the individual housebuilder in the following contents and confirm the significant metrics for the sequent data collection and analysis.

Another shortcoming of the TBL framework is lacking integration between the three dimensions of TBL and the real concerns of citizens. Firstly, Gibson (2006) were concerned that people might be well trained in the individual economic, social, and environmental aspects other than across all three. As a result, the interdependence of the three elements might be ignored (Sridhar and Jones, 2013). Besides, citizens (people) is supposed to be the beneficiaries, but their common concerns could not be well integrated into TBL and necessarily addressed (Ho and Taylor, 2007). Regarding this integration shortcoming, other studies raised the opposite view. Many scholars have confirmed an interdependent relationship among the three TBL dimensions (Jeurissen, 2000, Goel, 2010, Savitz, 2013), which could be regarded as the overlapped part in the TBL Venn diagram. This study accepts that the interdependence relationship exists in TBL elements, as no evidence has suggested peoples' skill level would directly decide the relationship among the economic, social and environmental aspects.

Meanwhile, according to the System Theory (Skyttner, 2005), the system usually includes cohesive groups with interdependent and interrelated parts. This suggests that each aspect of TBL should be interdependent and related to the sustainability target; otherwise, Elkington and other scholars would not take them into the TBL system. The failure in addressing people's concerns is controversial because some scholars have presented the evidence to confirm the progress made by TBL in the social and environmental issues (Aras and Crowther, 2013, Longoni and Cagliano, 2018). Moreover, instead of the general issues and concerns, this study will identify the crucial matters of people in the UK real estate market via the industry analysis (third chapter), which will also avert this drawback.

2.3.4 Implementation of TBL

Since deciding to use the dimensions of the TBL framework to assess the private housebuilders' performance, the literature regarding how to implement TBL via the three dimensions are reviewed, which provides more specific instructions for building the theoretical framework for this study.

About the implementation of TBL, it finds no generally applicable or widely accepted standards to measure business performance within each dimension (Adams, Frost and Webber, 2013), which means the TBL model adopted in other studies might not be suitable for this thesis. A gap in the theoretical framework is identified that no performance assessment framework with the specific criterion was ever developed based on the TBL model for the private housebuilding sector in the UK. Agreeing with the gap of lacking widely accepted standards in TBL, some scholars suggest the standards of TBL three dimensions should be decided based on the particular situation of the organisation (Mintz, 2011, Slaper and Hall, 2011).

Therefore, the board literature covering diverse standards is firstly reviewed in this chapter, then the standards in each TBL dimension will be refined after reviewing the housebuilding industry.

2.3.4.1 Social (People) Dimension

The social line of TBL describes the beneficial and fair business practices to the labour, human capital and the community (Elkington, 1998). Similarly, Žak (2015) explained the social dimension as the fair business practices towards employees, community and the region where business is operated. Goel (2010) summarised that these practices would finally provide value to society and local communities. Within the social dimension, the specific elements to measure companies' social performance are reviewed, which helps identify factors to measure the companies' performance in the social dimension.

Some studies highlight the social performance from the perspective of employees, in which operating within the social dimension means treating employees based on the principles of fairness and honesty, building a good work environment, giving training and development opportunities, never using child labour (Žak, 2015, Schulz and Flanigan, 2016). Meanwhile, some scholars also discuss the social performance from the perspective of local communities. Making voluntary and charitable contributions, helping with the significant societal challenges and developing the local communities (Schulz and Flanigan, 2016), supporting the communities and raising the standard of life (Žak, 2015), using the local contractors and suppliers (Norman and MacDonald, 2004), are the typical indicators for companies' social performance.

With the TBL framework, Rogers and Ryan (2001) examined the impact on sustainable community development. Furthermore, within the social dimension, the human well-being and needs elements are highlighted to measure progress and find improvement approaches. Meanwhile, it also mentioned that well-being and needs would be varied based on different individuals and groups (Rogers and Ryan, 2001), which reminds the author to consider the individual needs and well-being in the UK housebuilding sector from the 2010s before deciding on the criterion to assess social performance.

According to Uddin, Hassan and Tarique's framework (2008), an enterprise's performance in the social dimension could be measured from the three perspectives of responsibilities towards customers, employees and community, which is also accepted by Książak and Fischbach's research (2017). The three elements are social individuals or groups, and the emphasis on the three elements is based on their role that would influence or be influenced by the business practices (Uddin, Hassan and Tarique, 2008). Customer is a core and fundamental part of companies and meeting their needs and satisfaction (Schulz and Flanigan, 2016). Especially the growth of "new customers" in the 21st century, who highly value companies' credit and responsibility for society and the environment (Akbari et al., 2019). The labour source is also a key for business management, as they drive to develop the business competitive advantage and sustainability. The community is essential because it is where inhabitants live, and the companies and businesses operate (Schulz and Flanigan, 2016, Książak and Fischbach, 2017, Masud et al., 2019). Uddin, Hassan and Tarique present a relatively inclusive framework that summarised the social impacts from customers, employees, and community views.

Furthermore, based on these elements, it finds the social dimension of TBL has significant overlaps with the CSR decisions. CSR suggests that companies consider the business practices beneficial and favourable to the employees and local communities (Schönherr, Findler and Martinuzzi, 2017). Alhaddi (2015) also mentioned that the disregard of CSR could result in the decreased social performance and business sustainability of TBL. The CSR aims to develop and maintain a good relationship between society, the environment, and an enterprise, while the social dimension of TBL is expected to examine how well these practices with CSR purposes have been taken.

After reviewing the above literature, the social dimension covers a relatively broad range of elements. Although Uddin, Hassan and Tarique categorised into three groups, the particular aspects of each group could be varied based on the specific business. Meanwhile, the specific social elements confirm the limitation of TBL: complication and hard to quantify. This makes it necessary to review the stakeholder theory in the following contents to identify the essential elements within the social dimension so that the social metrics would be decided afterwards.

2.4.3.2 Environmental Dimension

The environmental line of TBL is generally referred to as the planet, which is focused on the natural habitat for people and companies. According to explanations of Goel (2010), Alhaddi (2015) and Gupta (2011), the environmental line requires business practices to create benefits for the planet as many as possible or at least reduce or eliminate negative influences on the planet. Environmental sustainability has been highlighted, like climate change, melting glaciers, pollution, and resources in the 21st century (United Nations, 2020). Correspondently, a set of business decisions and practices have been taken to help

with these issues. For example, companies have used renewable resources and raised energy efficiency, controlled carbon emission, segregated and recycled waste and so on (Goel, 2010, Źak, 2015). Regarding protecting the environment, TBL and CSR have a high level of coherence in terms of purpose and practices.

Many existing studies regard the criterion as the companies' influence on both the "living and non-living nature system" to assess the performance in the environmental dimension (Schulz and Flanigan, 2016, p451). Specifically, Uddin, Hassan and Tarique (2008) introduced two metrics: environmental impacts and the win-win situation. About the environmental implications, Uddin, Hassan and Tarique (2008) explain it as the harm to the environment brought by the business operation. It is challenging for the enterprise not to harm the environment because the environment would be influenced by human and business behaviours more or less in the supply chain. Furthermore, to eliminate some environmental issues, some business decisions that might bring additional negative influence are inevitable (Księżak and Fischbach, 2017). By realising the inevitable harms to environment, Uddin, Hassan and Tarique (2008) further mentioned that the environmental performance would be better when the company reduced its harmful influence on the environment. Therefore, when assessing the environmental performance, it is about examining the impact of business decisions on the environment and companies' progress in reducing the negative consequences. The win-win situation is for both sides of a company (business) and the environment. Uddin, Hassan and Tarique (2008) regarded the practices that create values for both sides as one indicator for satisfactory performance, like removing the environment unfriendly practices in production would reduce negative impacts on environments and improve the company's reputation at the same time (Księżak and Fischbach, 2017).

Focusing on the environmental dimension, Rogers and Ryan (2001) proposed relatively general measurements of ecological footprint, which compares what people would consume and what the natural environment could provide. Also, the metrics for environmental performance were described as the impacts on natural resources and a company's sustainability (Slaper and Hall, 2011). Similarly, Źak (2015) emphasised that a company with good environmental performance should protect the natural environment, control its impacts, or not damage the environment. Compared to Uddin, Hassan and Tarique's (2008) framework, these explanations seem to be more focused on the impacts on the environment than the company itself. Based on the general measurements of the environmental performance, the author takes business impacts on the environment as the principal metric in this thesis. In the environmental performance assessment, it should be noticed that the critical environmental metrics and issues could be considerably different based on the particular business and industries (Schulz and Flanigan, 2016). From this point, this study agrees to assess the four private housebuilders' performance via examining their impacts on the environment, but the specific environmental indicators will only be decided after the industry and company analysis.

2.4.3.3 Economic Dimension

The economic line is an essential requirement for companies, which ensures the possibility of business development (Księżak and Fischbach, 2017). The capability and performance in the economic dimension are regarded as the subsystem helping with surviving and evolving into the future for the following generations, which is finally for sustainability (Spangenberg, 2005).

Based on the traditional measurement, the economic line of TBL is extended to examine the influence of business practices on the economic system (Elkington, 1998). Nevertheless, it does not mean the traditional financial measurements are excluded in this dimension. Oppositely, the financial indicators are firstly included in the economic dimension, which might cause a misunderstanding that the economic dimension of TBL is still the same as the traditional measurements of financial performance (Żak, 2015). It is clarified by Alhaddi (2015) that the economic line of TBL connects the economic performance of organisations with the social and economic growth at the same time. In other words, the organisational financial indicators would help with the further analysis regarding economic values created by the business practices for the society. Based on this explanation, it believes TBL has a shared view with CSR that regards the economic dimension more to do with the influence on the society, which includes the company and other stakeholders at the same time (Uddin, Hassan and Tarique, 2008).

Regarding the specific metrics of the economic dimension, many scholars presented their opinions. With the approach of TBL, Książak and Fischbach (2017) highlighted three aspects to measure companies' performance in the economic dimension. The first aspect is the multiplier effect, highlighting the economic impacts of business practices on multiple stakeholders. The higher financial performance of companies is expected to draw more economic values to society and the multiple stakeholders. For example, higher profits allow companies to spend more on CSR practices.

The second aspect is the taxes. Companies that make more revenues and profits would contribute more taxes. At first sight, the author includes taxes in the first aspect. Then it agrees to keep the taxes as a separate aspect because the first

aspect highlights the influences of initiative and voluntary business practices, like donations, while the taxes aspect emphasises the obligation more.

The last element is avoiding actions that damage trust. This aspect is more to do with compliance in business operations. Some practices within the economic dimension, like bribery and corruption, are believed to cause damages to companies' trusts and credit in society. According to Źak (2015), the economic dimension is concerned with the economic and financial performance; therefore, the economic dimension includes the specific indicators of profit, cost-saving, economic growth, research and development. Willard (2012) listed seven elements in the economic dimension, summarised as revenue, cost, productivity and risks. After reviewing the elements of the economic dimension in some studies, it finds this dimension mainly contains two groups of factors: one group is the financial indicator, another group is the impact on social economy. In different studies, measuring the business impacts on the social economy is varied. However, the major financial indicators, like revenue, profits, cost, are commonly regarded as a signal for the impacts on the overall economy in the society. As KsiężaK and FischBach (2017) said, a company's financial performance would directly influence its financial capability to contribute to social benefits, and the better financial performance is expected to draw more benefits for the society like more taxes and job opportunities. Besides, compared to the companies' description of their contributions to the overall economic system, the financial indicators are more objective to assess their performance.

One of the research objectives in this thesis is to assess the private housebuilders' financial performance, focusing only on business profits. Therefore, the financial performance in the thesis is different from the performance within the economic dimension of TBL. Nevertheless, the literature on the economic dimension still

builds the knowledge about how to assess a companies' financial performance. According to the suggestions in terms of the typical financial indicator, the total revenue, profit before tax, the dividend payment is selected to measure the private builder's financial performance in the thesis. However, the builder's contributions to the social economy are not discussed in this thesis, which might be a possible topic for future studies.

Dimensions	Source	Standards
Social dimension	Zak (2015)	Standard of living Education Community Equal opportunity
	Rogers and Ryan (2001)	Human wellbeing's Human needs (Varied based on different context)
	Schulz and Flanigan, 2016	Career retention Volunteerism and charitable contributions Employee education and training Access to social resources Well-being and health Social performance of suppliers and social capital
	Uddin, Hassan and Tarique's framework (2008) Książka and FischBach's research (2017)	responsibilities towards customers, employees community

Environmental dimension	Uddin, Hassan and Tarique's framework (2008)	environment impacts (harms to the environment) the win-win situation
	Rogers and Ryan (2001)	ecological footprint: compares what people would consume and what the natural environment could provide
	Zak (2015)	act to protect the natural environment, control its impacts or at least not to damage the environment
Economic dimension	Ksiezak and Fischebach (2017)	Multiplier effect (on multiple stakeholders): the higher economic performance will draw more economic value to society Tax: more revenues and profit will contribute to more tax to the county Avoiding actions damage trust
	Zak (2015)	Profit Cost-saving Economic growth Research and development
	Willard (2012)	Increase revenue Reduce energy expenses Reduce waste expenses Reduce material and water expenses Increase employee productivity Reduce hiring and attrition expense Reduce strategic and operational risk

Table 1. Summary of Standards of TBL Three Dimension

2.3.4.4 Summary

Based on the explanation of TBL, it finds this framework is developed towards sustainability by considering three dimensions of economy, society and environment. Many studies have taken this framework to assess the business performance, classify and analyse the CSR practice, examine the sustainability progress, and raise solutions for the business sustainability. The author of this study also adopted the TBL framework to explore private housebuilders' performance for society, the environment's benefits, and financial performance.

After reviewing the explanations on the three dimensions, part of the significant metrics to assess the social, environmental and financial performance in this thesis is confirmed. The performance in social and environmental dimensions will be included as a combined conception to evaluate the private housebuilders' performance for the benefits of society and the environment. The combined performance is also described as non-financial performance in some parts of this thesis to separate it from the financial performance. The environmental dimension will focus on the impacts on the natural environment, and the specific ecological indicators will be decided in the industrial analysis. The social dimension notices that the broad social metrics are categorised into three groups of customers, employees, and community in Uddin, Hassan and Tarique's framework (2008), which are also the key stakeholders to housebuilding business. Compared to the other two dimensions, the social dimension is relatively complicated and hard to quantify. Finally, confirming the social metrics, the literature on the stakeholder theory and the industrial analysis in the next chapter will help. Revenue, profit before tax, and dividend payment will be used to examine how well the four private housebuilders have made business profits.

2.4 Stakeholder Theory

2.4.1 The Conception of Stakeholder Theory

The stakeholder theory was fully explained for the first time by R. Edward Freeman in his book *Stakeholder Management: A Stakeholder Approach* (Laplume, Sonpar and Litz, 2008). Previous to this, there were some discussions about the stakeholder theory, but Freeman (1984) argued that the existing stakeholder explanations had failed to address the changes in the business environment. With realising the changes had occurred in both internal and external stakeholders, Freeman (1984) raised the stakeholder approach that business managers were suggested to consider groups that could affect or were or would be affected by the business practice. Since then, more scholars have redefined and developed the stakeholder theory. For example, Freeman and his colleagues have refined and defended their views about stakeholder theory, stakeholder actions, and responses. The specific stakeholders in the modern corporate were also explained by Freeman (2001). Laplume, Sonpar and Litz (2008) analysed 179 studies on the stakeholder theory and identified different themes. Besides, Miles (2017) conducted a bounded systematic review of 593 other explanations about the stakeholder theory. Based on these systematic findings and conclusions, this research finds that although with different expressions, the principle of the stakeholder theory has been well kept. In the stakeholder theory, an interrelated and interactive relationship between the organisation and its stakeholders exists, and the organisation should consider and value the benefits of diverse stakeholders rather than only the shareholders.

2.4.2 The Stakeholder Perspective in Performance Assessment

The stakeholder approach has been discussed in the business performance topic, especially in examining the corporate social performance. Raised by Donna J. Wood in 1991, the Corporate Social Performance (CSP) model regards stakeholder management as a critical corporate social responsiveness (Wood, 1991). In this model, diverse stakeholders are engaged with the three outcomes of social impacts, programs and policies to assess the corporate social performance. What the social effects of business behaviours on diverse stakeholders (social influences), what programs used to give the responsiveness to stakeholders (social program), and how well the business policies handle the social issues and stakeholders' interests (social policies) would decide the social performance assessment (Wood, 1991). Clarkson (1995) also raises a framework to analyse and evaluate the corporate social performance via the stakeholder approach. By reviewing lots of studies, Clarkson (1995) summarised about 20 stakeholder issues and indicated how has the company performed on these issues would help evaluate the social performance.

From the stakeholder perspective, Gomes and Miranda Gomes (2011) suggested assessing the performance by the stakeholders' expectations. Moreover, Nason, Bacq and Gras (2018) evaluated the social performance by analysing the gaps between the stakeholder's expectations and the companies' actual practices and performance. As the explanation of "expectation" in the two studies, this term could be understood as a more comprehensive conception including stakeholders' needs and issues. The more the company could satisfy stakeholders' needs and expectations, the better their social performance (Nason, Bacq and Gras, 2018). With a similar view, Brower and Mahajan (2013) also found that companies with

higher sensitivity to stakeholders' demands drove a more upbeat performance in CSR.

In addition, many studies taking the stakeholder approach and examining the performance other than the social performance have also been developed. Atkinson, Waterhouse and Wells (1997) measured the business performance via analysing and evaluating the companies' contributions to different stakeholders. Furthermore, from the stakeholder's perspective, Yoon and Chung's study assessed the firm's financial performance.

The wide adoption of the stakeholder approach in business performance results from the critical role of different stakeholders. For example, the shareholders' benefits could be an indicator of the financial performance, and the improvement of local communities could be an indicator of companies' social performance. Therefore, both CSR and TBL frameworks highlight incorporating the stakeholders in different business dimensions into internal management, which is in common with the principle of stakeholder theory (Freeman and Dmytriiev, 2017).

Many studies regard the stakeholder theory as a foundation of TBL, as the stakeholders, especially the customer, are the main reason organisations take the practices against the three TBL dimensions (Elkington, 1994, Jamali, 2006, Høgevold et al., 2015). When assessing the business performance with the three dimensions of TBL, Pires et al. (2016) suggested considering the significant stakeholders' feedback as meeting their expectations is a common goal for organisations. Moreover, Høgevold et al. (2015) emphasised that the stakeholder approach provides an easier way to quantify performance, like shareholders value, customer satisfaction, employees retention, which might help make up the

limitation of TBL. Meanwhile, Kuchta and Mrzygłocka-Chojnacka (2020) took a reverse thought and mentioned that the stakeholders close integrating with the three dimensions of TBL should play a critical role for business, which helps identify the core stakeholders for the companies.

Generally, the scholars confirm the feasibility of the stakeholder approach in corporate performance assessment, especially the social performance. Furthermore, some studies further identify a positive relationship between the concentration on stakeholders and the performance (Galant and Cadez, 2017). It also finds that the stakeholders' expectations, needs, and concerns are mainly highlighted and how well have the company behaved towards them would usually affect the performance assessment to a great extent (Galant and Cadez, 2017).

The theoretical framework and application of the stakeholder approach provide the author with a perspective of the stakeholder in performance assessment, which also helps refine the metrics in the social dimensions of TBL based on the primary stakeholders' view. As a result, when assessing the private housebuilders' performance for the social benefits, how well have the private housebuilders served the significant stakeholders' interests and helped with their concerns would be regarded as a typical metric in this thesis.

2.4.3 Identifying the Major Stakeholders

The stakeholder theory has been adopted by companies in their business management, which provide a strategic perspective that manages by taking account of all the stakeholders. Based on the stakeholder theory, companies should identify the stakeholders as much as possible and recognise the significant stakeholders in the first place before coming up with specific strategies to manage

these stakeholders (Miles, 2017). Since it takes the stakeholder's perspective to refine the metrics for the performance assessment of the private housebuilders, the core stakeholders within the UK housebuilding sector need to be confirmed.

According to Freeman (1984, p46), the stakeholders are "any groups or individuals who can affect or is affected by the achievement of the organisation's objectives". However, scholars challenged Freeman's views on stakeholders that the "can affect or is affected" criterion could be ambiguous and less feasible in the real business practice (Phillips and Reichart, 2000, Laplume, Sonpar and Litz, 2008). Hence, a further elaboration of stakeholder roles has attracted the interest of scholars. Laplume, Sonpar and Litz (2008) summarised the corresponding literature under two normative questions "which stakeholders should manager pay attention to" and "which stakeholders do manager care about", which is the identification of typical stakeholders and the core stakeholders. For example, Delmas and Toffel (2004) identified the typical stakeholders like governments, regulators, customers, competitors, communities and groups with environmental interest, industrial associates from an institutional theory perspective. Considering stakeholder management as a strategic element, Parmar et al. (2010) regarded the groups whose support is necessary for business existence as the common stakeholders. Furthermore, the study on business ethics regarded stakeholders as the groups the organisation has the moral obligation to (Phillips, 2003).

Robins (2006) highlighted that the primary stakeholders with a contractual relationship with business include shareholders, employees, customers, and suppliers. Furthermore, the government, local communities, and the general public are regarded as the secondary group of stakeholders. Similarly, about the sustainability target and the assessment of CSR outcomes, some scholars also

considered the shareholders, financiers, employees, customers, suppliers, competitors, government, local communities, natural environment as the core stakeholders (Turker, 2009, Clifton and Amran, 2011).

Under the different themes, the description of the stakeholder could be varied. There is still no generally agreed with the definition of stakeholder in various studies. However, the existing research has provided many perspectives and evidence for stakeholder identification, which helps the author recognise the most essential and typical stakeholder for the private housebuilders in terms of the benefits of society.

2.4.3.1 Major Stakeholders for the Private Housebuilders

Developing and maintaining a housing property could be considerably complicated, and the individuals and groups who have interests and needs in this process should be considered a stakeholder (Sousa, 2012). Specifically, Sousa (2012) divides stakeholders into primary and secondary groups within the housing context. The primary stakeholders include “tenants (users of the service), board of directors, professional management, housing associations and development groups, and government housing agencies”, and the secondary stakeholders are “independent funding organisations or foundations, community agencies, and community representatives” (Sousa, 2012, p32).

Based on Soetanto and Pan’s (2009) study, the typical stakeholders for a private housebuilder include employees with diverse skills for housing construction, housing design, land purchase and other business stages, the internal shareholders, buyers, local communities, government and local councils, suppliers, and outsourcing contractors. Furthermore, according to Caput (2013), the

potential stakeholders for a real estate development project include customers, suppliers, workers, shareholders, financial sponsors, local communities, etc.

After reviewing the studies of stakeholder identification with highlighting the benefits of society and the housebuilding sector at the same time, the typical stakeholders for the private housebuilders in the UK are summarised.

- Customers/ property buyers (existing or prospective inhabitants)
- Employees/ workers
- Shareholders
- Suppliers
- The UK Government
- Local communities
- Financial institutes
- Housing associations or organisations
- Environment associations or organisations

The above stakeholders are all relevant to the private housebuilders. However, their importance might vary based on the housebuilding context in the particular period. For example, after the Global Financial Crisis, shareholders' values are highly valued in the housebuilding companies. Many private housebuilders have set return on per capital employed as an indicator to assessing the director's performance and remuneration (Archer and Cole, 2016). Meanwhile, considering the limited research time and resources, it is impossible to consider all these stakeholders. Therefore, only the stakeholders with high importance, relevance, and representativeness with the research aim would be further studied and regarded as the top priority by this study. This thesis is focused on assessing the performance of the private housebuilders for the benefits of society and the

environment, and their financial performance. To refine the metrics in the social dimension, the stakeholder who has represented chiefly the benefits of the community, mostly affected or been affected by the private housebuilders' practices, will be focused on in this thesis.

2.4.3.2 The Stakeholder Perspective of Customer (or Inhabitants)

The core stakeholder in terms of the benefit for society is decided as the customer (inhabitants). In the private housebuilding sector, the customer can be regarded as the inhabitant who has already purchased the property or the prospective customer who plans to purchase the property. Selecting the inhabitants as the most typical and persuasive stakeholder to examine private housebuilders' performance for the benefit of society is based on the following reasons.

First of all, the customer is regarded as one extremely significant stakeholder for most companies, including the private housebuilders (Sousa, 2012). Constantly meeting customers' needs and driving their satisfaction directly affects the sustainable development of business (Robins, 2006). Therefore, the customer is usually a strategic role in business management, which also confirms the importance of customers in all three dimensions of TBL. For example, customers' purchases would influence the business revenue, and customers would be beneficial from the companies' contributions to the overall economic system, local community and natural environment at the same time. The customers' needs and expectations would influence business, but the business practices would also affect customers' interests within different areas. Considering the customers' great exposure and access to outcomes of companies' practices in the social, environmental and financial areas, taking the views of customers (inhabitants) to examine the private housebuilders' performance for the social benefits should be

reasonable (Schulz and Flanigan, 2016). Besides, based on the strategic role of the customer, this perspective is expected to bring practical implications for future business practices.

Secondly, when discussing the benefits for society, the author agrees with humanism, which highlights the role of human beings and considers the human being as a starting point (Melé, 2012). Therefore, creating benefits for society could be understood as the benefits for human beings. Focusing on the housebuilding sector, the customers (inhabitants) group should have a larger population than other stakeholders because the accommodation is regarded as an essential product required by almost every individual in the society (Ozaki, 2003). Meanwhile, purchasing a property is different from other daily transactions because the exchanged values between the customers (inhabitants) and the housebuilder are usually relatively high and lasting for a particular time. Based on the large population of customers (inhabitants) and the high transaction values the inhabitant would pay for, it believes how well have private housebuilders created benefits for the customers (inhabitants) would represent their performance for the benefits of society to a large extent.

2.4.4 Evaluation of Stakeholder Theory

The stakeholder theory plays a strategic role in business management. By considering the values and helping with the issues of diverse stakeholders, a good relationship would be built, which could become a competitive advantage for the company (Harrison, Bosse and Phillips, 2010). In addition to the positive influence on social performance, Berman et al. (1999) also emphasised that stakeholder management could raise the corporate financial performance. The stakeholder theory proves the importance of stakeholders and suggests a new perspective to

examine business performance. Clarkson (1995) believed the stakeholder approach could assess performance from the view of the particular individuals or groups, and the satisfaction of these stakeholders would be a valuable indicator for whether their interests and values have been well considered. Hence, the stakeholder approach is practical. Besides, the core stakeholders for different companies in different periods would be varied, therefore identifying the core stakeholders and focusing on their responses would help confirm and analyse the key performance metrics for the specific company or sector (Clarkson, 1995, Costa and Menichini, 2013). The TBL provides a systematic framework for assessing the private housebuilders' performance; the stakeholder approach helps identify the highly prior performance assessment metrics by focusing on the specific stakeholders' needs and concerns.

However, the limitations of the stakeholder theory should be noticed. Because considering the diverse stakeholders' values, the stakeholder theory might reduce the efficiency in business management. The consideration of various stakeholders might cause extra costs and disperse managers' attention, which could be an issue for the performance assessment (Cooper, 2017, Freeman, Harrison and Zyglidopoulos, 2018). The performance assessment could be general and time-consuming when examining the diverse stakeholders' responses. This thesis only focused on the private housebuilders' most significant stakeholder (customers) in assessing the social performance during the particular period between 2010 to 2020 to overcome this issue.

Besides, scholars also mention one limitation: the stakeholder theory might create collisions as the values of some stakeholders are conflicting. For example, taking environmental actions would raise the benefits of society but cost the shareholders (Harrison, J. S., & Wicks, 2013, Mansell, 2013, Freeman and

Dmytriyev, 2017), which might become a confusion when assessing the overall performance. However, this limitation ignores the interdependent and interactive relationship of stakeholders in the business. The reduced values of one group of stakeholders might be temporary; in return, sustainable values might be achieved, like the environmental actions would raise the public relation, brand image and employee loyalty, which would further contribute to the financial returns for shareholders (Parmar et al., 2010, Queen, 2015, Freeman and Dmytriyev, 2017). The confusion in overall performance assessment created by the conflicts among the different stakeholders is not like to happen in this study because the only inhabitants would be focused on in the performance assessment for the benefits of society and the environment.

2.5 Summary

Based on the research aim and questions, the author reviews three groups of literature: CSR, TBL and stakeholder theory. First of all, the literature review clarifies the CSR conceptions practices in the UK since the 21st century and the positive and negative influence of CSR strategy. Therefore, it is confirmed that today's companies can influence the benefits of society and the environment via taking CSR practices. Furthermore, the CSR theory also helps enrich the author and reader's understanding of social and environmental performance via relating the performance to the specific CSR efforts.

Then, since the research objectives are focused on the private housebuilders' performance, the TBL assessment frameworks and the stakeholder approach are reviewed. By highlighting the three dimensions of economy, society and environment, TBL has been regarded as a tool to examine corporates' progress towards the sustainability target. For this study, the private housebuilders'

performance for the benefits of society and the environment would be mainly examined by the metrics in the social and environmental dimensions. In contrast, the metric would discuss the financial performance in the economic dimension in the TBL framework. After the systematic reviews of metrics in each dimension, it decides to take the key financial indicators for financial performance the impacts on the environment for the environmental performance.

However, it is not easy to examine all the social elements for assessing the social performance within the limited research time. By realising this issue, the author then reviews the studies on the stakeholder theory. The stakeholder theory raises a new perspective of diverse stakeholders and suggests assessing social performance via analysing how well the primary stakeholders' interests have been served. Meanwhile, the stakeholder literature also helps the author confirm the most important stakeholder for the private housebuilders in terms of the social benefit: customer (inhabitant). Meeting inhabitants' needs and helping with their concerns are finally selected as the metric to assess the performance within the social dimension. Moreover, inhabitants' perspective also helps refine the significant aspects of the UK's private housebuilders in the next chapter.

Based on the literature review on CSR, TBL and stakeholder theory, a framework for assessing the housebuilders' performance in serving social and environmental benefits and creating their business profits is finally built (Figure 2). This framework is developed based on the TBL and stakeholder theory and confirms the metrics to assess this study's social, environmental, and financial performance. However, it notices the social and ecological metrics would be varied based on the specific period and industry (Rogers and Ryan, 2001, Sridhar and Jones, 2013). Therefore, in the following contents, the author conducts the literature review focusing on the UK housebuilding sector and the private housebuilders. The most

highlighted problems within this sector would be identified and taken as the more specific metrics for performance assessment.

Figure 2. The Theoretical Framework for Performance Assessment (the author)

CHAPTER 3, LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE UK HOUSEBUILDING INDUSTRY

3.1 Introduction

To comprehensively understand the private housebuilders and their business performance, it is essential to learn the context of the private housebuilders. Meanwhile, as the last chapter emphasised, the specific metrics to examine the private housebuilder's performance would vary based on different industries and contexts, making the review on the UK housebuilding industry more necessary here.

This chapter reviews the history of the UK housebuilding industry, covering the background from the Second World War until today. Furthermore, the housebuilding sector from 2010 to 2020 is particularly highlighted under the research topic. Then the development history of the private housebuilders in the UK is examined, which helps build a good understanding of the private housebuilders' businesses decisions and performance since the last century. Based on the review on the significant issues of the UK housebuilding sector, the specific metrics within the economic, social and environmental dimensions are refined.

3.2 Development of the UK Private Housebuilding

Industry

3.2.1 UK Private Housebuilding Sector before the 2010s

After the first World War, the period witnessed the mass emergence of the owner-occupations and the housebuilding firms, and the private housebuilding sector was in an initial stage in the UK. The Second World War outbreak in 1939, and the British housebuilding sector was severely damaged at that time (Wellings, 2006). Nearly half a million homes were destroyed or uninhabitable due to the bombing in World War (NHBC Foundation, 2015). Therefore, the UK housebuilding market was confronted with the issue of housing shortage after the war. The unsatisfied needs for houses raised a rapid expansion of the housebuilding industry in the 1950s and 60s. According to the National Statistics data, the total completions of new housebuilding in England increased from about 160,000 in the early 1950s to around 350,000 in the late 1960s (Ministry of Housing, Communities & Local Government, 2019). For the other parts of the UK, Scotland, Wales, and North Ireland, the total completions of new housing have been increased to around 40,000, 17,000, 11,000 respectively at the end of the 1960s (Ministry of Housing, Communities & Local Government, 2019). Under the growing trend, the completion of housebuilding reached a peak level of over 425,000 across the UK, and half of the families owned their own homes in 1968 (NHBC Foundation, 2015).

The newly completed house was mainly from three tenures of local authorities, house associations and private enterprises. Firstly, the local authorities had been the significant housebuilder with the largest number of dwellings in England until 1979 (Ministry of Housing, Communities & Local Government, 2019). The housing outputs of the local authorities had decreased from around 200,000 units in the

mid-1950s to below 100,000 units per year in 1979. Meanwhile, the private housing enterprises had increased the housing supplies as well, and their housing supplies ever surpassed the local authorities' in the late 1950s (Ministry of Housing, Communities & Local Government, 2019). Compared to the other two tenures, the house association had produced the smallest number of housing (Ministry of Housing, Communities & Local Government, 2019). Generally, the British economy and the housebuilding sector had been in a rhythm of development after the war. Meanwhile, significant changes have happened since then, some of which were the historical factors for the decisions of today's housebuilders.

Before 2010, the UK housebuilding sector has experienced three significant recessions. The first housing bubble, named the Barber Boom of 1973, happened in the UK during the 1970s (Scott, 1996). Because of the supportive monetary and fiscal policy, the UK housing market was in a short-term boom in the early 1970s. However, affected by the OPEC Oil Crisis in October 1973 and the new capital tax rate, the increased loan interest rate and restrictions for personal loans cooled down the housebuilding sector (Scott, 1996, Wellings, 2006). The total housing completions in the UK decreased from about 360,000 in the early 1970s to about 250,000 in the late 1970s (Woodhill, 2021a), and the sales of private housing dropped by 50% by 1974 (Wellings, 2006).

The British currency joined in the European Rate Mechanism in 1990; therefore, the global economic recession triggered a slump in the British economy and the second recession in the UK housebuilding sector. In such an economic context, the interests rate went up, and the demand for housing dropped down, which caused a rapid decrease in property value (Wellings, 2006, Pitros and Arayici, 2017). Afterwards, the UK existed from the European Rate Mechanism, and the housing

market slowly recovered. According to Wellings (2006), 1996 was a signal of the end of the economic recession and the recovery of the housebuilding sector. The late 1990s prepared for further development in the 2000s.

In addition to the recessions, the Right to Buy scheme was another major event that resulted in the housebuilders' marketing position change. Under Thatcher's government, the plan of Right to Buy was soon introduced and implemented via the Housing Act 1980 in England and Wales areas, and the Housing Tenants' Rights, Etc. (Scotland) Act 1980 in Scotland (Alan, 2015). A similar scheme with minor differences has been implemented in Northern Ireland, which was the House Sales Scheme (Alan, 2015). The Right to Buy scheme has been regarded as a landmark policy in the UK property sector (NHBC Foundation, 2015) and a centrepiece of Thatcher's political pitch to aspire the working classes (Scott-Samuel et al., 2014). This scheme was applied to all council homes owned by the councils, new town, non-charitable housing association and other public sector bodies and offered the qualified tenants the opportunity to buy their home with a generous discount (Housing Act 1980, 2002). Despite some opposing voices, the scheme was extraordinarily popular in the UK, and about 90,000 council homes were sold in the first year of publication. In 1982, the sales of council homes reached a peak of more than 240,000 units (Mark et al., 2016), and by the end of the 1990s, about 1.9 million council homes had been sold (NHBC Foundation, 2015) (Figure 3). The Right to Buy scheme changed the marketing position of the two major builders. The local authorities retreated from the housebuilding industry, and the private housebuilders became the major player since then (NHBC Foundation, 2015).

Figure 3. Right to Buy Sales, England, 1980/81 to 2013/14 (Cole et al., 2015)

From the 21st century, globalisation has been a critical trend supported by the highly developed technology, internet and communication around the world, which has resulted in commercial and social changes (NHBC Foundation, 2015). Meanwhile, the housebuilding industry also stepped into a fast-developed stage. The low-interest rate, high employment, fewer loan constraints, grown populations all accelerated the development of the housebuilding sector. The base rate of the Bank of England dropped from 6% in 2001 to 4% in 2003 (Pitros and Arayici, 2017). Moreover, the availability of global loans added new channels for the mortgage, which further raised the housing demands (Whitehead and Williams, 2011). According to the national statistics of permanent dwellings in the UK (Woodhill, 2021a), the total completion of new homes gradually increased from about 175,000 in 2000 to about 215,000 just before the Financial Crisis.

The third recession of the UK housebuilding sector happened in the 21st century. 2008 was regarded as a signal that ended the quick expansion of the housebuilding sector and the start of the recession within the UK real estate market (Whitehead and Williams, 2011). The UK housebuilding market experienced a significant financial catastrophe, and the completion of new-built homes rapidly decreased and was kept at a low level in the following few years.

The average housing price in the UK doubled from £ 89,597 in 2000 to £ 185,196 in 2007 before the financial crisis (Office for National Statistics, 2021). Then the price sharply declined to the lowest point of £ 154,000 in the first quarter of 2009 (Office for National Statistics, 2021). During that period, the completion of new homes and transactions from almost every housebuilder in the UK was relatively low.

3.2.2 UK Private Housebuilding Sector after the 2010s

The development of the UK housebuilding industry since 2010 is the main background to assess the private housebuilders' business practices and assess their performance. The external business environment contains multiple factors affecting the strategy development and implementation, business operation, decision-making and final performance of a housebuilder (Baron, 2013). As Buchanan and Gibb (1998) said, it is hard to understand the development of the particular organisation or its management solutions without information about the specific business environment. Therefore, the housebuilding industry and the significant issues during the target period of 2010 to 2020 is focused on. This review would offer the author and reader knowledge about the housebuilding sector and help confirm the metrics for performance assessment.

The impacts of the Global Financial Crisis on the UK housebuilding sector have lasted for several years. In the early 2010s, housebuilders preferred to take the traditional strategy to maintain their financial accounts. The actions for creating profits, generating cash, acquiring the land with a higher margin and securing funds were widely adopted by housebuilders (Payne, 2015). After the recovery in the early 2010s, the total completions and housing selling price returned to the level before the crisis. However, it did not mean the impacts of the Global Financial

Crisis had ended. According to Payne (2016), the housebuilders seemed to be more persistent in accumulating profits and cash after returning to the condition before the crisis. Although the total supply of newly built houses increased after a recovery period, it was still far below the low levels before 2000 (Woodhill, 2021a). The average house price gradually recovered from 2013 and surpassed £ 200,000 in the second half of 2015. According to the report on house prices, the average price of a property in the UK is £ 249,309 at the end of January 2021 (Office for National Statistics, 2021).

Figure 4. The Average Price of a Property in the UK, 2010 to 2022 (Office for National Statistics, 2021)

3.2.2.1 Brexit

The Brexit negotiation was officially launched in 2017 (Walker, 2019). Brexit is the scheduled withdrawal of the UK from the European Union (EU), which was initiated from a referendum with 52% votes supporting withdrawal (BBC News, 2020). The Brexit negotiations between the British government and the EU have brought political tensions and uncertainties for the private housebuilders in the UK. After several years' discussion, the Brexit was completed, and the UK existed from the EU at the end of January 2020. And after the 1-year transition period, an agreed deal defining the relationship between the UK and EU came into effect on the last day of 2020 (Walker, 2019). Since sensing the challenges of Brexit, the housebuilders in the UK have already considered or taken the related strategies to deal with the possible threats and opportunities. As a result, housebuilders'

business decisions and performance have been influenced (Cleary, Baseley and Barclay, 2018). Therefore, understanding the significant influences of the Brexit event is critical to assess housebuilders' performance.

Brexit – Skilled Labour

Since the Brexit negotiation was initiated, the tension regarding skilled labour in the construction sector has been raised. The Chief Executive of the Federation of Master Builders (FMB), Brian Berry, mentioned that the UK housing construction has been heavily dependent on migrant labours from the European countries for decades (Federation of Master Builders, 2017). For example, the national housebuilding and construction firms, like Barratt Developments and Roger Stirk Harbour, said 40% of their professionals are from the EU area. The Royal Institute of British Architects (RIBA) also highlighted that the UK registered architects from the EU accounted for 25%. In the transition period of 2020, the number of workers from the EU countries and working in the UK construction sector has already decreased by one quarter. Furthermore, in the 3rd quarter of 2020, there were only 127,000 EU-born workers in the construction sector, which was 176,000 1 year ago (Price, 2021).

With realising the potential risks of the immigrant restrictions from the Brexit, Berry suggested that to meet the housebuilding targets, the British government should ensure that the new immigration system would provide reasonable migrant approaches for the labours from the European countries (Mohamed, Pärn and Edwards, 2017). The Association for Consultancy & Engineering CEO, Dr Nelson Ogunshakin, even said that without the construction skills from the European labours, the national infrastructure pipeline would be facing severe setbacks (Guthrie, 2017). The immigration rules after the transition period tried to offer a solution to this issue. For the new employment of EU-born workers, the

skill level requirement was lowered from RQF Level 6 to RQF Level 3, and some roles that were not qualified for sponsorship before are open for the skilled worker visa now, like the building technicians, building contractors, builders, roofers, fencer, electricians and other technicians (Secretary of State for the Home Department, 2020).

Generally, the concern about the ability to recruit, train and retain skilled workers from Europe has been raised in the construction sector. Furthermore, it is predicted that the immigration system after Brexit would discourage some of the skilled labours from Europe, which would result in a skill shortage for housebuilders in the next few years. Lacking skilled migrant labours would postpone the construction project and increase overall construction costs (Smith, Ahmed and Saboor, 2020). Although the new immigration system provides related solutions, the employment of EU-born workers is more complicated and even more costly than before. Moreover, Brexit might reduce the intention of the EU workers to work in the UK as well. Considering the immigration and visa rule, EU workers would select other EU countries to work rather than the UK (Guthrie, 2017). Therefore, Brexit is believed to be a challenge for housebuilders regarding the employment of skilled labours based on the current situation.

Construction Material

The Brexit would affect the EU labours and affect the import of construction materials. In 2016, 62% of construction materials were transferred from the EU area to the UK, while 60% were exported from the UK to the EU countries (Department for Business Energy & Industrial Strategy, 2018). The data discloses that UK house construction relies on importing the materials from EU counties to a large extent.

Based on the Trade and Cooperation Agreement between the EU and the UK, purchasing the construction goods and materials will still be free of charge, tax and tariff or quotas (House of Commons Library, 2021). This releases housebuilders' concern about the increased cost of material before. Nevertheless, Brexit still raises some changes in the material trade. The free movement of goods was ended on 1st January 2021, and the customs check and control are built at the board (Joe, 2021). This means the supply chain of construction goods and materials would take a longer time than before, which would cause extra costs in the construction projects (Sheena, 2021).

On the positive side, Sam (2016), Alicia and Jianwei (2016) pointed out that Brexit could be an opportunity for the UK to build its trade agreements with other countries outside the EU. However, ElCheikh et al. (2020) held a different view that Brexit would reduce the UK's bargaining power and trading influence when developing a trading partnership with others. Brexit can become an opportunity for the housebuilders in the UK if the builders would successfully develop a beneficial partnership outside the EU, which might take time and effort. Therefore, Brexit is more likely to challenge the housebuilding companies' material imports.

Red Tape

In addition to the negative influence, Brexit is also beneficial to private housebuilders. The Brexit would help release the housebuilder from some red tapes, regarded as one of the hinders for the UK housing construction (Oliver and Nick, 2018). After the UK joined the EU in 1973, the British housing building sector must comply with the relevant laws and regulations mandated by the EU. Because of the geographical difference between the two areas, some laws and regulations are not applicable in the UK housebuilding industry (HM Government, 2017, Oliver and Nick, 2018). The director of Millwood Designer Homes considered

Brexit to be beneficial for the UK housebuilders and raised an example of the negative influences of the EU Habitats Directive on the UK housebuilding construction process. Unlike Northern Europe, where the great crested newts or slow worms are rare and specially protected, many of these insects can be found in the South East England. Nevertheless, according to the EU Habitats Directive, the insects have to be caught and transferred to another place for release before initiating the construction project, which caused a couple of months delay for the whole process (Ray, 2016). This example highlights the positive impacts of Brexit via removing some red tapes, which could be a good sign for the private housebuilders' future construction and supply.

Currency Rate

Compared with the other time in the 21st century, the Sterling exchange rate has badly decreased since the Brexit negotiation was raised. On the day when the UK voted to leave the EU, the currency rate of Sterling against the US dollar was dropped by 8%, which was the biggest daily fall since the early 1970s (Josh and Swati, 2019). Meanwhile, the UK lost its AAA credit rating and raised internal inflation (Eicheikh et al., 2020). These changes cause two issues for UK housebuilders. Firstly, the pound's devaluation made the most extraordinary inflation of the materials cost since 2011, which is also one of the reasons for the low pace in housing construction (Eicheikh et al., 2020). Secondly, some investors left the real estate market and some big private housebuilders, like Barratt Development and Taylor Wimpey, incurred losses in their shares. After the referendum, the uncertainties of Brexit discouraged investment in UK business (Eicheikh et al., 2020). Moreover, Mugarura (2016) predicted that the housebuilding investment would be decreased in the next few years.

3.2.2.2 Covid-19 Pandemic

The first Covid-19 case was identified in January 2020 in the UK. Then this pandemic has widely spread, and until now, it is still ongoing all over the country (Gov.UK, 2022). It is no doubt the Covid-19 pandemic has brought a considerable threat to the diverse business, including the housebuilding and construction sector in the UK, and this influence is likely to continue afterwards (Manjula Bai, 2020).

Industrial Economy

One apparent influence of the Covid-19 pandemic is on the national economy, which also affects the housebuilding sector at the same time. Before the pandemic, the British economy was ranked in the top ten globally but grew sluggishly (PwC, 2018). Then the outbreak of the Covid-19 and the related policies like stay-at-home, business closure, social distance caused an alarming decline in its Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The GDP of the UK was £2172.5 billion in 2019, while it fell to £1958.6 billion in 2020 (Michael, 2021). During the 12 months of 2020, UK GDP dropped down and witnessed the three most significant falls since 1997, in which the decrease in April 2020 was the worst one by 18.8% (Stephens, Wright and Luckwell, 2021). In February 2021, the monthly GDP was raised by 0.4%, while it was still 7.8% lower than one year ago. Meanwhile, the monthly construction was grown by 1.6%, which was still 4.3% below the construction last year (Beckett, 2021). Uchegara et al. (2020) mentioned that the Covid-19 pandemic negatively influenced the British economy and worsened the vulnerability of the housebuilding sector.

Disrupting Construction

The Covid-19 pandemic disrupts housebuilders' construction projects badly. In April 2020, around 723,600 construction workers were furloughed because of the

lockdown rule, and 42% of residential construction sites were closed (HM Revenue & Customs, 2020, Lucy, 2020). With the reopening of construction sites, some construction workers returned to work from May 2021, and the number of employments furloughed dropped to 159,600 at the end of October 2020. However, the damage is still in the way. After that, the subsequent lockdown rules allowed the construction site to be open but required the workers to work under a set of rules (HM Government, 2020).

In addition to the housebuilders, other stakeholders also struggle under the Covid-19 pandemic, like housebuilders' contractors, materials suppliers, logistics, clients, financial institutions (Uchehara et al., 2020). The indirect influence of Covid-19 on the related parties is regarded as one of the primary reasons that cause the construction project delay. For example, the delay was caused in the stage of the planning application because one of the planning authorities could not work from home (Stride, Suresh and Renukappa, 2020).

As a result, the extra time and money were raised, and the general working efficiency was decreased. The number of housings started or completed between April and June 2020 fell to the lowest point since 2000. In the June quarter of 2020, the number of dwellings started and completed was 15,930 and 15,950, which was 59% and 67% lower than the same quarter of last year (Neil, 2020).

Figure 5. New-build Dwelling Starts and Completes, England (Gillespie, 2021)

Supportive Policies for the Housebuilding Business

Relief of Stamp Duty

Although the Covid-19 discourages the national economy and housebuilding sector within the UK, the housing price is surprisingly increased (Uchegara et al., 2020). According to the price statistics, the average housing price was £231,940 in January 2020. Then it climbs to £249,309 after one year (Office for National Statistics, 2021). Unlike the Global Financial Crisis, when the housing price fell to a terrible level, Covid-19 seems to help raise the housing price because the UK government have adopted some timely solutions in response to this pandemic. In the UK housebuilding sector, the three-month interest relief for housing mortgage and the cut of Stamp Duty Land Tax (SDLT) was offered to the buyers (Uchegara et al., 2020). The increased housing price believes the reduction of SLDT in England and Northern Ireland have played a crucial role. The UK government announced that nil rate of the SDLT is applied to the property value up to £500,000 from 8th July 2020 to 31st March 2021, then it has been extended to 30th June 2021 (HM Revenue & Customs, 2021), which means the buyers would save up to £15,000 in purchasing a property (BBC News, 2021). This initiative aims to boost

the national economy and the real estate market, which is successfully based on the increased housing price and housing sales.

Change of Customer Housing Demands

In the growth of average housing prices, the detached properties made an outstanding contribution in 2020. In England, the average price of a detached home was £375,353 in December 2019, which increased by 10.1% to £413,341 in December 2020 (HM Land Registry, 2021). The situation is similar in other parts of the UK (Murdo and Charles, 2020, Cunningham, 2021). It believes the Covid-19 pandemic has changed buyers' housing preferences and needs. Because of the stay-at-home policy, most people have spent much more time at home during the pandemic, raising their needs for a bigger space. The University of Sheffield and Ulster University research found that people's depression and anxiety have been raised because of the lockdown policy (Sophie, 2020). Shevlin et al. (2020) also mentioned a modest increase in mental health problems during the pandemic. Moreover, Amerio et al. (2020) highlighted that life and liveable outdoor spaces are essential to maintaining mental health. The particular lockdown period and the mental needs explain people's growing needs for detached properties with bigger spaces.

Fluctuant Mortgage

There is a similar trend with the housing selling price of the bank mortgage. In the early period of the Covid-19 pandemic, the housebuilding sector was facing the challenges and uncertainties of the depressed economy. Although the Bank of England cut its interest rates to 0.1%, the lowest rate in the bank's 325-year history, the national economy was still not promising by then (Phillip, Richard and Mark, 2020). Given the fiscal risk, the leaders are more cautious about the mortgage for business and house purchases (Uchegara et al., 2020). In the Bank of

England, the number of mortgage approvals for house purchases dropped to 15,800 in April 2020, which was 80% lower than the approvals in February of the same year (Bank of England, 2020).

Meanwhile, the strict mortgage resulted in a decrease in the sales of residential properties in the UK. However, with the deblocking and new stamp policy, people's demands for house purchases seemed to wake up, encouraging banks' confidence in the mortgage. The mortgage value and house purchase approvals have increased since June 2020. The mortgage approvals in the remaining months after June surpassed the highest approval level since October 2007, and the number of mortgage approval in November reached a peak of 105,000 (Bank of England, 2021). This positive performance of mortgage compensates the decline brought by Covid19 to some extent, which is regarded as a good signal for the recovery in the housebuilding sector (Küçük, Lenoël and Macqueen, 2021).

3.2.2.3 Other Significant Factors related to the Housebuilding Business

Growing Population and Households

The total population of the UK is estimated as 66.8 million by the middle of 2019 (Analytical Impact Team, 2021). Along with the population, the number of households has been raised. The total of households was estimated as 27.8 million in 2020, which was 5.9% higher than the number of households in 2010. The statistician found that people's lifestyles changed based on the household data. Firstly, as the most common family type, households with the married and civil partnered couple was decreased, and more people decided to live together before or without being married. Secondly, the average household size has been kept stable (2.4 per household), but the percentage of people living alone has increased by 4.0% during the 2010s (Amanda and Pamela, 2021). Both of the two changes

have raised the demands for purchasing or renting a property. It is projected that the UK population will be over 70 million by mid-2031 (Andrew, 2019). Furthermore, the number of households in England is estimated to increase by 1.6 million (7.1%) by 2028 (Andrew, 2020). The increase in population and household further predicts the growth of housing demands in the future (Bentley, 2016a).

Ageing Population

One of the most critical population features in the UK is the ageing population. The age structure is decided by fertility and mortality, and the two indexes have been decreased in the UK. In 1999, the population aged 65 years old and over was about 15.8%. Then it was increased to 18.5% in 2019. According to the population data, it is estimated that the population aged 65 years old and over will reach 23.9% by 2039. However, differing from the ageing group, the population aged under 16 years old is about 20.4% in 1999 and falls off to 18.5% in 2019. By 2039, this population is projected to be about 16.9%. In the UK, the working population mainly concentrates on the age from 16 to 64 years old, among which the minimum age for a full-time job is 18 (Analytical Impact Team, 2021). Therefore, the ageing population has caused concern for the shortage of skilled labour for diverse industries in the UK, including the housebuilding sector. Furthermore, for the private housebuilders, this issue is very likely to get worse in the future based on the population estimation and the Brexit.

Public Attitude

Another important social factor is the public attitudes towards residential property in the UK. For example, would people like to buy or rent a house and would people like to buy a new house or a second-hand house would affect the business strategy and performance of the private housebuilders. The British Social

Attitude Survey is used to explain the level of changes in the public attitudes, values and beliefs, and in the housebuilding sector, the public attitudes towards a series of issues are examined.

According to the latest finding of the 2018 survey, 57% of people supported more homes being built in their local area while 23% of people opposed it, which was 28% and 46% respectively in 2010. Regarding the need to buy a newly built home, the 2018 British Social Attitude Survey pointed out that a significant majority of people will buy instead of renting if they have a free choice, and this result has been stable over the last 30 years. The renters and younger people (aged between 18-25 and 26-35 years old) are more likely to buy a newly built home (Kate and Tajkia, 2019). Another point is about how well the house was designed and built. 46% of people thought that the new homes were well designed, while 23% of people selected poorly designed. The home quality seemed to be an issue, about which 36% of people responded as well built, and 30% responded as poorly built (Kate and Tajkia, 2019).

Overall, the survey results indicated a growth of the public's attitudes towards building more new homes, and the renters and the younger people had a more substantial need for the new homes than the others. For the private housebuilders, the change of the public attitudes towards purchasing a property is a positive sign for the growing demands in the real estate market.

Technology

Technological development has dramatically changed almost all walks of life. As one of the most technologically advanced countries globally, the UK pays close attention to technology development in different sectors. A supportive environment for developing technology and innovation has been built for many

industries (Marketline, 2014). According to the 2019 Global Innovation Index (GII), the UK has ranked fifth among 129 countries (Dutta, Lanvin and Wunsch-Vincent, 2019). In such a supportive context, the UK private housebuilders have changed the way of operating businesses and adopted more advanced technologies and innovations. From house planning to after-sales service, digital technologies play an essential role. For example, the first digital BIM library for the off-site timber building systems of Stewart Milne Group has been launched, which covers over 100 systems of wall, floor and roof to help designers create the “smart” digital models and reduce the accuracy discrepancies of the 2D design process (Ramsay, 2017). Through the construction phase, drones are widely applied, like detecting geological elements and accessing dangerous or hard-to-reach places (McPartland, 2017). When selling the property, the technology can support the sales process and after-sales service, like displaying the property with virtual reality skills and promoting responses with the chat bot on the website (CITB Research, 2018). Furthermore, during the Covid-19 pandemic, some technologies, like video conferences, are helpful for seamless remote works (Stride, Suresh and Renukappa, 2020). Generally, these advanced technologies would positively influence the business of the housebuilders, like raising the efficiency of construction and improving clean production (Jha and Iyer, 2006).

In 2019, the British government provided the funding of £72 million to the Construction Innovation Hub for the transforming construction and aimed to drive the innovation and technological progress in the construction sector, which mainly includes commercialising digitals and new manufacturing technologies (Construction Innovation Hub, 2018). One board member of the Construction Innovation Hub further explained that the transformation of construction would change the way that buildings and infrastructure are designed, manufactured and integrated with higher productivity, and the more innovative, greener and more

efficient buildings are expected to be delivered afterwards (Construction Innovation Hub, 2018).

3.3 Development of the Private Housebuilding

Companies in the UK

3.3.1 Business of the Private Housebuilders in the UK before the 2010s

From the outbreak of the Second World War to 1954, the speculative housebuilding industry was severely constrained, in which the business of the private housebuilders was severely damaged as well. During wartime, the speculative housebuilding market has confronted a collapse. At that time, the private housebuilders began to involve in war constructions, like building military camps, airfields, barrage stations, navy bases and so on (Wellings, 2006). The particular war backgrounds and the political constraints after the second war resulted in profound changes in the structure of housebuilding companies (Wellings, 2006). As a result, the private housing completions were at a low level.

Affected by the second war, it was recorded that about 200,000 homes were destroyed, and over 3.5 million homes were damaged (Merrett and Gray, 1982). The whole country was in great demand of new dwellings, which was supposed to be a good growth opportunity for the private housebuilders. However, the new government made a political decision that it was the public, not the private sector, that would take the responsibility of rebuilding the houses in the UK. Under this policy, the licenses for private housebuilders, the supply of timber and steel, were hard to acquire (Wellings, 2006). This political action was a severe hit for the

private housebuilders. For example, Taylor Woodrow ever prepared itself to complete 4,000 houses per year after the second war, however in the three consecutive years after 1946. It was only allowed to build 205 houses for private sales (Wellings, 2006). This regulation poorly constrained the private housebuilders' business until 1954, when it was revoked. During this period, the public housebuilders' completion was far beyond the private housebuilders' (Wellings, 2006). Furthermore, based on this fact, the government can significantly affect the private housebuilder's business and performance via the specific policies related to builders' construction projects.

Before the second war, about twenty private housebuilders built over 500 units every year (Wellings, 2006). Moreover, some private housebuilders never returned to this sector after the war. Meanwhile, some larger private housebuilders like Idea Homes, Davis and Estates, tried to stay in this industry and waited for a better time to revival. A common option for the private housebuilders was to expand the public housing projects (Wellings, 2006). As a result, the private housebuilders' business strategy was adjusted to focus on the local authority housebuilding program. In most circumstances, the private housebuilders worked as contractors for the local authority housebuilding project. However, the work could sometimes be the cooperation when the private housebuilders owned the land, demonstrating the importance of land from the beginning.

The political element also created certain benefits via the public housing project during that time, which pushed the housebuilding industry towards industrialised construction methods (Wellings, 2006). With the support of the local authorities, the public housebuilding programs offered the opportunities to adopt the new construction methods. For example, the Scottish housebuilder, Miller Homes, designed its own non-traditional house, the 'no-fines' house (Harrison et al., 2004).

Another positive side was from the profitable operation of the participations in the public housebuilding programs. Few of the detailed transaction evidence could be found, but none of the private contractors complained about the loss in the contract at the same time. Therefore, it assumed that the private contractors made some money, which provided the cash flow for their land purchase (Wellings, 2006).

In addition to the public housing projects, some private housebuilders that the dynamic entrepreneurs operated were reluctant to only wait in the domestic market and began to develop their overseas market at the same time, which also made them become the leading national or even international house contractors (Wellings, 2006). The profitable development in the overseas market made these British private housebuilders stronger, but they did not grow as speculative housebuilders. Also, it was noticed that many outstanding engineers had the priorities on the construction project than the private housebuilding (Wellings, 2006).

Because of relief from the political control, the supply of private housebuilders had increased, and the top ten output of the private housebuilders could reach 14,000 to 16,000 units per year around the 1960s (Wellings, 2006). However, the influence of the political factor had been lasting after the deregulation. It noticed that the rank of the top ten housebuilders changed, and some new housebuilders stood out at that time. The first reason for this phenomenon was that some of the housebuilders had a substantial income from the wartime construction, the post-war housing project of local authorities or even the international construction projects so that the motivations of the speculative housing market in the UK was not high for them. Also, with 15 years' development in construction, some senior managers and directors had less foresight in business development. For some

housebuilders, the political control interrupts the succession plan from the first generation to the second generation. These housebuilders either developed other businesses or declined or even vanished from sight. Meanwhile, some 'new' housebuilders that had grabbed the political opportunities gradually developed (Wellings, 2006).

From the 1960s, the business performance of the top ten housebuilders had been generally improved. In the first half of the 1960s, the quantity of housebuilders with an annual output of over 1,000 units increased substantially. Furthermore, the supply of the top ten housebuilders was increased to 17,000 to 18,000 by that time. From 1960 to 1973, this period could be regarded as a booming time for the private housebuilders' performance in the UK. There were 26 housebuilders with an annual output of over 1,000 units, and five of them built over 2,000 houses every year. Meanwhile, the output of the top ten housebuilders was about 32,000 to 33,000 units. With the growing completion of the new dwellings, two main phenomena were raised among the private housebuilders' business (Wellings, 2006).

Firstly, the geography of the completed properties was also extended to a broader range. Although London and its suburbs were still an active market, the larger housebuilders intended to develop in the Northern area due to the sufficient large sites. For example, Barratt Developments had developed its Newcastle base to a more comprehensive northern England and Scotland. Secondly, the takeover was more used as an expansion approach by the housebuilders. Wimpey was an exception with the development depending on its own business. The two phenomena were integrated as the geographical extension was usually accompanied by the business acquisition (Wellings, 2006).

Company	Late 1930s	1960	1973
Ideal Homes	5000–7000	2000–3000	7000–8000
Henry Boot	1500–2000	c.200	350
Wates	1500–2000	200–300?	1000–1500
Taylor Woodrow	1200–1500	c.750	500–750?
Davis Estates	1200	500–1000	c.1000
Wimpey	1200	6000	11,500
Mactaggart & Mickel	1000	c.500	200–300
Costain	1000+	c.200	c.1000
G.T. Crouch	1000	c.400	c.500
Laing	800	300	310

Figure 6. The Top 10 Housebuilders in the Late 1930s, 1960, and 1973 (Wellings, 2006).

Housebuilder	2000	Housebuilder	2004
Wimpey	11,437	Barratt	14,021
Barratt	10,636	Persimmon	12,360
Beazer	8223	Wimpey	12,232
Persimmon	7035	Taylor Woodrow	9053
Bellway	5714	Bellway	6610
Westbury	4435	David Wilson	5588
Wilcon	4215	Berkeley	4839
McAlpine	4007	Westbury	4400
Bryant	3961	Redrow	4284
David Wilson	3604	Bovis	2700
Top ten	63,267		76,087
Redrow	3330	Crest	2524
Berkeley	3210	Miller	2505
Bovis	2360	McCarthy & Stone	2055
Countryside	2122	Lovell	2051
Taylor Woodrow	1919	Fairview	1990
Miller	1844	Bloor	1916
Lovell	1815	Countryside	1911
Crest	1731	Gladedale	1874
Fairclough	1707	Fairclough	1547
Bloor	1700	Cala	1505
Top twenty	85,005		95,965
Prowting	1579	Cruden	1200
McCarthy & Stone	1539	Kier	1158
Fairview	1459	Morris	1100
Wain	1371	Linden	1018
Laing	1235		

Figure 7. the Private Housebuilders with an Annual Supply of 1,000 or More in the UK during 2000 and 2004 (Wellings, 2006, p100).

3.3.2 Impacts of Three Recessions on the Private Housebuilders

First Recession

The above contents discuss three times of recession for the housebuilding business in the UK. Here, the primary influence of these recessions on the significant private housebuilders' profile, business strategy and performance are reviewed.

The external context during the recession of the 1970s was a bad hit for the private housebuilders (Buxton et al., 2005). As a result, land value was reduced as some housing projects were halted and the construction costs were increased. Affected by this recession, many damages were caused for the private housebuilders. By the end of the 1970s, there were only thirteen private housebuilding companies with annual outputs over 1,000, which was less than the twenty-six housebuilders before the recession. For some companies, the situation was worse as it caused a collapse in their finance. Budge Brothers was the first quoted company that failed, and after that, the fourth housebuilder Bovis was brought down by the financial debts (Vistry Group, 2020).

Similarly, the national second-largest housebuilder at that time, Northern Developments, also failed due to its debts issue (Wellings, 2006). This recession brought a decrease in housing outputs and changed the leaders in the UK housebuilding industry. Wimpey's housing output in the UK market was decreased and was no longer the industrial leader. The overseas business has grown profits in the Middle East market (Valerie, 1980). At the same time, Barratt

Developments became the new leader by creating a national business presence. In addition to the property itself, Barratt Developments impressed its customers with the multiple advertising and marketing approaches and soon became a familiar brand during that period (Wellings, 2006). Furthermore, after recovering from this recession, four of the top ten housebuilders did not survive at the beginning of the 1980s (Wellings, 2006). Generally, it finds the business performance of the private housebuilders is significantly affected by the favourableness of loan and external economy, which enhances the viewpoint that assessing the builders' performance with considering the particular economic backgrounds

Second Recession

Like 1974, the housebuilding industry experienced another recession in the early 1990s (Muellbauer and Murphy, 2012). The mortgage rate was raised, and housing completion was dropped by 30% compared with 1988's (Wellings, 2006). Affected by it, the housebuilders suffered write-offs in their balance, which again caused the risks of forced bankruptcy. However, the two recessions differed because the banking systems were more supportive; therefore, fewer bankrupt companies (Wellings, 2006). Furthermore, the acquisitions were fewer among the housebuilders as they were more concerned about their survival, and the land could be purchased at a depressed price. After realising the unsatisfactory profit margin of the house, some housebuilders began to purchase the land. Furthermore, housebuilders decided to encourage sales even at a lower price (Muellbauer and Murphy, 2012). In this way, Bellway and Persimmon generated fast growth and became the top 10 housebuilders (Wellings, 2006).

Third Recession

Another significant recession that shaped the business practices of housebuilders was the Financial Crisis in 2008. Before it, housebuilders rapidly developed their business via mergers and acquisitions, which also changed the profile of the top ten housebuilders in the UK. For example, Barratt Developments acquired the smaller competitor Wilson Bowden in February 2007 and became the largest housebuilder (Kollewe, 2007). Before the war, Ideal, the housing leader, Persimmon, and Wimpey purchased another leader, McLean. In the 2000s, Barrette, Wimpey, Persimmon Taylor Woodrow and Bellway became the industrial leaders based on their sales and completions (Wellings, 2006). After the fast extension, the real estate market was shaken firstly by the Northern Rock crisis afterwards, the sales and price of the house badly dropped. Since 2008, the leading housebuilders have stopped the new housebuilding projects in all or partly. Worse than the recessions in the 20th century, the financial institutions were involved and became less supportive. Persimmon closed all new housebuilding projects due to the reduced market sales and called on help from the government. Taylor Wimpey's value was wiped off by about £7 billion and sleeked for the emergency cash injection (Wearden and Kollewe, 2008). Meanwhile, some medium and small housebuilders went bankrupt because of this Financial Crisis (Nistorescu and Ploscaru, 2010).

3.3.3 Business of the Private Housebuilders in the UK after the 2010s

Based on the previous recessionary experiences, the private housebuilders developed new recovery approaches to handle the crisis. Unlike the business behaviours in the booming period, the private housebuilding companies emphasised the efficient capital return and economic management of cash flow (Payne, 2016). Especially for the investment on the land, the more substantial

cause and due diligence were placed. To gradually restore the strategic land bank, the private housebuilders were attracted by the sites with predictable sales and prices and low planning risk (Payne, 2016). In addition to improving business performance via more efficient internal management, the private housebuilders also widely discussed the issues raised by the external factors, like the planning problems and political ambitions. The private housebuilders claimed the procedural delays of acquiring the planning permission interrupted their output. Moreover, supportive actions from the UK government and local councils were required by the housebuilders (Payne, 2016). It finds that the private housebuilders' business has been significantly affected by the external context, especially the political and economic context, since the last century. However, the role of private housebuilders in the relationship with the government has been changed from a relatively passive position in the last century to a more proactive position during the last decade.

After recovery from the crisis, the housebuilding sector embraced business growth again. The total housing completions reflect that housebuilders' primary business option is reinvesting in construction projects to grow their housing output. In addition to the supply, the average margin of housebuilders has been raised simultaneously. Furthermore, the generous annual profits of the large private housebuilders mainly raise the discussions among the public and other different parties. For example, BBC News (2019) reported that Persimmon's profit was boosted to 13% with £1.091 billion for the 2018 financial year. Meanwhile, Barratt Development's profit before tax also experienced an 8.9% increase and reached £909.8 million (Kollewe, 2019). Despite ups and downs, the UK housebuilding market value has significantly been raised after the 2008 Financial Crisis (Williams, 2019). Although the private housebuilders have been still sensitive to the external context, it seems their vulnerability has been increased

and higher than in the last century. The significant challenges of Brexit and Covid-19 badly influence housebuilders' operation and finance performance, in which the top national housebuilders have more capacity to solve the related issues.

Another noticeable trend among housebuilders in the UK is the changes in the small and medium housebuilding companies. Compared with the last century, a noticeable change in today's housebuilding industry in the UK is the number of private housebuilders. According to Lyons (2014), over 10,000 small and medium housebuilders were active within the UK housebuilding sector in 1980, which delivered about 57% of newly built housing. Over the last forty years, the housebuilding sector has lost thousands of SMEs. By 2017, only about 2,500 SME housebuilders were still active in the market and reasonable for 12% of newly completed houses (Home Builders Federation, 2017). With the shrinkage of SME housebuilders, the large national housebuilders have quickly grown simultaneously. The most significant ten private housebuilders completed 28% of the newly completed housing supply in 1980 (Welling, 2006), and later in 2015, their supply accounted for 47% of all the new housing supply in the UK (Archer and Cole, 2016). Consolidation and merger were practical approaches (Wellings, 2006).

This change indicates a concentration of market share in the large housebuilders; therefore, the top housebuilders have a better development context based on the advantages created by the outstanding market share than the SME housebuilders. Furthermore, the housing shortage issue highly depends on the small number of top housebuilders' supply for a long time, which is later identified as a risk in the UK housing supply (Department for Communities and Local Government, 2017).

3.4 Summary of the Private Housebuilding Sector and Housebuilders

According to the literature review on the development of the housebuilding industry as well as the private housebuilders in the UK, it finds the private housebuilders' business decisions and performance have been greatly influenced by the external environment, like the government policies, the economic situation, changes of customer needs, the environmental issues, technological development. In the last half-century, the private housebuilding sector in the UK has experienced tremendous changes. After the Second World War, property demands increased, and the private housebuilding sector grew simultaneously. Especially after the Right to Buy scheme, the private housebuilder became the most crucial role with the most significant housing supply in the UK market. Furthermore, in industrial development, the private housebuilders Barratt Developments, Persimmon, Bellway and Million Homes were founded and soon developed to be the leading companies in the UK market (Wellings, 2006). The development of the housebuilding industry demonstrates that considering external factors' influence is necessary when assessing the private housebuilders' business strategy and performance. During the 21st century, private housebuilders have further developed their business to a dominating position in the UK market, and they have more decisive power to influence the housing supply and price than other groups of housebuilders. Thousands of SMEs vanished, and the large housebuilders have improved their influences to an unprecedented level.

The review of the UK private housebuilding sector and the housebuilders finds the influence is interactive between the external context and the private builders, confirming the builders would affect the benefits of society and the environment.

Meanwhile, the external context would be considered in the housebuilders' performance assessment based on its influences.

3.5 Metrics for Private Housebuilders' Performance

Assessment

According to the TBL framework, the specific metrics to examine the private housebuilder's performance would be varied based on different industries and market contexts (Rogers and Ryan, 2001, Sridhar and Jones, 2013). Therefore, a wide range of literature, news, reports and statistics about the housebuilding sector and private builders are reviewed to identify the most significant and urgent issues or needs in the UK housebuilding sector. In the second chapter, the customer (inhabitant) stakeholder is regarded as the typical role representing social benefits. Therefore, when examining the major issues in the housebuilding sector, the author would also stand on the angle of customers (inhabitants) and find out what is most needed or concerned.

3.5.1 Criteria in Social Performance: Major Inhabitant's Needs or Concerns

In the theoretical framework, the social performance of the private housebuilders would be assessed by analysing how well have the private housebuilders met the inhabitant's needs or helped with the inhabitant's concerns. Focusing on the UK housebuilding sector, three housing aspects are identified as the most needed or concerned by the local inhabitants: housing supply, housing affordability and housing quality.

3.5.1.1 Three Aspects Mostly Highlighted among Inhabitants

3.5.1.1.1 Housing Supply

As a critical topic, the housing supply has been widely discussed among the inhabitants. In the briefing paper of the House of Commons Library, the completion of new homes has been regarded in an under-supply condition in England. This conclusion is raised by the gap between the estimated housing need and the real completion of a new home every year (Wilson and Barton, 2020). Housing need is described as the amount of housing required by all the households to live in the accommodation meeting a set of standards. Therefore, the housing need refers to the first-time buyer and the household living in unsuitable accommodation — for example, the overcrowded accommodation and the bad accommodation condition. Besides, the housing supply also results from the housing demand, which is different from housing needs (Barton and Wilson, 2021). The housing demand means that the number of houses buyers would like to purchase based on their preferences and affordability. The buyers might purchase more than one house as long as they have the purchasing power. The households without homes owned by themselves, the households living in accommodation under a normative standard, and the buyers with demand and affordability for another house all result in the growing housing supply gap. Based on the survey of National Statistics, about 65% of households in England owned their own homes from 2019 to 2020, which means about one-third of households still do not own their own home in England (Rottier, 2020). With the development from 2010 to 2020, the ownership rate has been kept at a similar level, but this rate is generally lower than before the 2010s (Rottier, 2020).

People's concern about the housing supply issue is reasonable by considering its adverse impacts on society. The government document suggests that the supply

of newly built homes would affect house affordability. Increasing the housing supply has been listed as a priority to release the fastly increased house price and raise the housing affordability (House of Commons, 2006). This is developed based on the essential supply and demand model that the higher supply, the lower price (Boelhouwer and De Vries, 2005). Similarly, Legal & General (2014) highlights that the housing shortage raises a set of problems, like the escalated house price, unaffordable house ownership, temporary accommodation. Therefore, the shortage of house supply would decide the availability of the home that people would like to purchase and affect the buyers' affordability. Especially for the young buyers, they find it difficult to get on the housing ladder (House of Lords Library Notes, 2016).

3.5.1.1.2 Housing Affordability

Housing affordability is another server issue widely concerned by inhabitants in the UK. According to the briefing paper of the 2017 UK housing review, no matter in the private or the social housing sector, the issue of affordability is emphasised at high importance as a supply issue, but rather more neglected (Wilcox et al., 2017). The 2017 Institute for Public Policy Research report also mentioned that an effective housing strategy should focus on the quantity of new-built houses and affordability (Lyons et al., 2017).

The affordability issue is usually discussed based on the result of the proportion of a household's disposable income that is spent on housing' (Wilson and Barton, p12, 2019). In this measurement, the Affordable Housing Commission (2019) points out that hardship and stress, like financial difficulties, areas, debts and other personal financial problems, are likely to be caused when the housing cost is over one-third of a household income. Furthermore, these problems would be critical when this ratio reaches 40%. According to the survey on understanding

the UK society, about 8.4 million people are living in an unaffordable, insecure or unsuitable condition, which means this issue is not only about being unable to pay for the rent or mortgage but also about the people living in overcrowded or unsuitable homes because of their low affordability for a bigger or suitable home (National Housing Federation, 2019).

The house affordability issue has a broader impact than expected. Wilson and Barton (2020) take the affordability issue as one of the pressures for the government's home supply target. From the perspective of social benefit, Berry (2010) describes housing affordability as a key in the national economy because this issue would raise economic and social problems, especially for first-time or young buyers. The outcomes might hinder the efficiency and competitiveness of the national economy and social cohesion. Additionally, this issue causes high pressures to inhabitants with low affordability and reduces their happiness in life, particularly severe among young adults aged 25 to 34 years old. According to BBC News (2018), even with a 10% deposit, about 40% of young adults cannot afford to buy one of the cheapest houses in their area. Shelter supports the development of more social houses from the social perspective and mentions that about 268 000 people, including 123 000 children, were homeless in England (Strachan, 2018).

3.5.1.1.3 Housing Quality

According to the Office of Disease Prevention and Health Promotion (2020), there are five social determinants of people's health issues, and neighbourhood and built environment are some of them. Furthermore, the quality of housing is a critical element in this domain. It defines that house quality includes 'the physical condition of a people's home and the quality of the social and physical environment in which the home is located, and is affected by the factors, like home

design, home structure (Office of Disease Prevention and Health Promotion, 2020), which the housebuilders could control in advance. Through the study on the relevance between housing conditions and people's health, Bonnefoy (2007) finds that the housing condition is a fundamental element affecting human health. The home design of steps, balconies and windows would threaten people's safety. The poorly constructed steps, breakable glass and unprotected balconies might cause people's injuries (Krieger and Higgins, 2002, Keall et al., 2010). Besides, home quality issues are related to the apparent parts resulting from hidden places. For example, interior leaks and inadequate ventilation would increase interior dampness, further building the environment for viruses (Krieger and Higgins, 2002). Furthermore, Dedman et al.'s (2001) study found a modest relevance between inadequate ventilation and the mortality of the children in the UK. Therefore, considering the inhabitants' health and living conditions, housing quality has always been cared for by inhabitants.

3.5.1.2 Current Situation of the Three Housing Aspects

It is crucial to understand the progress and current condition of the three housing aspects within the industrial range to assess the four private housebuilders' social performance. So that the hypotheses regarding the target housebuilders' performance assessment and comparison would be developed based on the overall performance. Meanwhile, the development of the three housing aspects would also help compare the target housebuilder's performance and the overall performance in the industrial range. It might demonstrate whether the target builders have performed better than the average industrial level.

3.5.1.2.1 Inhabitants' Housing Demands

Looking from the past, the demand for residential property has been exceeding the supply for a long time, and the severity of this issue reaches a high level now.

As a fundamental problem in the British housebuilding industry, the issue of housing supply and demand is highlighted by many public documents and policies (Thompson, 2015). As the UK government white paper on housing stated, “the housing marketing in this country is broken, and the cause is straightforward: for too long, we have not built enough homes” (Department for Communities and Local Government, 2017). From the public statement and attitudes, it is found that the UK housing building sector is facing severe concern about the shortage of new housing supply and even regarding this problem as a destructive factor for the housing market.

The UK’s foremost developers of newly completed dwellings include private housebuilders, housing associations, and local authorities (Barton and Wilson, 2021). According to the latest supply statistics, the private enterprise’s permanent dwellings completed in the UK have been increased from 105,250 in 2010 to 172,010 in 2019 (Woodhill, 2021a). Although it was an increase, the annual supply of private housebuilders from 2010 to 2019 is averagely lower when compared with the last few decades before 1960. Considering the effect of the Global Financial Crisis, it is understandable that the annual supply in the early 2010s was lower than before. Nevertheless, after the recovery and the housebuilding has been quickly developed, the annual housing outputs of the private housebuilders was still not satisfactory (Payne, 2019). And the public also primarily blamed the private housebuilders for the under-supply issue in the UK market (Khan, 2017).

Ministry of Housing, Communities & Local Government’s net additional supply is a crucial measurement of the supply issue. According to Mulheirn (2019), the supply issues are exaggerated based on the net additional supply. In his research, the overall housing stock has been averagely grown around 211,000 considering the dwellings damaged by the bomb. Furthermore, the net additional supply has

been kept averagely at 190,000 between 1971 to 1980, which was close to the net additional supply in the last 15 years till 2019.

According to the national statistics, the private housing supply in England increased between 2010 and 2020. However, the thesis disagrees with Mulheirn's (2019) view. The national statistics indicate the constrained progress made to raise the additional net supply based on the historical level because the net additional supply from 2010 to 2020 is lower than the average level (Higgins, 2020). Besides, the concept of net additional supply includes the new build completions, conversions and demolitions (includes the housing completions by different parties), and no detailed data about the net additional supply from the private housebuilders are provided. Therefore, it believes the gap between housing supply and demands is not exaggerated.

The land constraint confirms and explains less satisfactory supply in the UK housebuilding sector (Stephens, 2011, Payne, 2019). Moreover, the industrial housing supply has been worsened by the "land hoarding" of the large housebuilders (Bentley, 2016b, Jefferys, 2016, Breach, 2020). Another factor suggesting the less satisfactory supply performance is the planning system, emphasised by Adams, Leishman and Moore (2009).

In addition, the big gap between housing supply and demands also confirmed that a part of the housing demands of inhabitants has not been satisfied. The UK government targets 300,000 additional homes every year by the mid-2020s in England (Barton and Wilson, 2021). However, the National Statistics tells that the net additional supply in England was only 243,770 during the financial year of 2019-20. Considering the impact of Covid-19 on the construction projects, the net additional supply in earlier years is also examined, and finds the additional supply

is still far from the target of 300,000 units (Higgins, 2020). Furthermore, for the future, it is estimated that about 340,000 new homes, including the backlog of existing home needs and the new households, would be needed every year in England (Wilson and Barton, 2020).

Figure 8. Net Additional Supplies in England (Higgins, 2020)

In the UK, people have the consensus that the output of the new house requires a significant increase based on its current level (Bramley, 2018). The above information demonstrates that the efforts of the private housebuilders in raising housing supply since 2010 is less satisfactory, which explains why Khan (2017) regarded the private housebuilding sector as a failure in building the properties needed.

3.5.1.2.2 Inhabitants' Needs of Housing Affordability

The Office for National Statistics has adopted the approach in England that the affordability ratio is equal to the house price divided by the gross annual earnings in the workplace. According to the published data on the affordability ratio (Woodhill, 2021b), the median affordability ratio was 6.85 in 2010, which later

increased to 7.84 in 2020. This result indicates a decreased house affordability from 2010 to 2020.

Based on the median housing price and gross earnings, it finds that the relatively faster house price growth is a critical reason for the worse house affordability in the UK market, supported by Zyed, Abd Aziz and Hanif (2016), Lyons et al. (2017). Meanwhile, many scholars believe the faster growth of price results from the shortage of housing supply. According to Grimes and Aitken (2010), the interrelated relationship between housing supply and price was identified, in which the short of supply is found to raise the housing price. Focusing on the housing sector in England, Hilber and Vermeulen (2014) find that the local housing supply is a crucial element to influence the housing price. Furthermore, the influence of supply constraints is more significant during the boom period than the depressed period.

Similarly, the government and housing organisations also confirm this view and believe the shortage of new housing completions has deteriorated the housing affordability in the UK (Select Committee on Economic Affairs, 2016, Department for Communities and Local Government, 2017). After examining the multiple factors that influence the housing price and affordability, the Home Builders Federation (2015) concluded that “undersupply is a deep-rooted, long-term structural problem, across many areas of the country, and not just a temporary cyclical phenomenon”. Therefore, solving the housing supply issue is very likely to raise housing affordability. However, the less satisfactory efforts on raising housing supply in the housebuilding sector result in inadequate contributions to raising housing affordability.

3.5.1.2.3 Inhabitants' Needs of Housing Quality

According to the national customer satisfaction survey, the questions regarding customers satisfaction about housing quality and problems are reviewed (Appendix 5). With a national range of the sample, the survey result is evidence for the private housebuilders' efforts to maintain or improve housing quality. Before the Global Finance Crisis, the average customer satisfaction on home quality was below 80%. Since 2010, customers' satisfaction with the quality of new-built homes varied between 84% to 91%, which means 8 or 9 people in 10 would be satisfied with the home quality (Home Builders Federation, 2020). Although the satisfaction has been kept at a high level, the satisfaction rate in the late 2010s is slightly lower than in the early 2010s, demonstrating a decreasing trend in terms of inhabitants' satisfaction about the housing quality.

Another evidence is from the home problems reported. The national survey results demonstrate that most people (over 90%) have reported problems with their homes (i.e. defects, snags) to their builder after moving in. From 2010 to 2020, the ratio of reporting 1-5 home problems has been dropped, while the ratio of reporting 11 to 15 and over 16 problems has been increased simultaneously. This indicates that a growing number of home problems has been found and reported by homeowners. Meanwhile, the survey result also presents a growing proportion of inhabitants stating the real home problems is much more than their expectation (Appendix 5). The national survey result confirms that the builder's efforts on housing quality are satisfactory to most inhabitants in the UK. However, their satisfaction has been decreased from 2010 to 2020.

In addition, a systematic study also mentions the growing concerns about the quality issue in the residential dwellings, especially the permitted development conversions project (Clifford et al., 2020). The housing charity Shelter (2017) also

doubts today's housing quality that over half of the homeowners have encountered significant problems after moving into their new property. The national survey result is strong evidence to confirm the private housebuilders' performance in housing quality since 2010. In the thesis, the author believes the overall efforts on housing quality in the UK housebuilding sector are still at a satisfactory level, but this satisfaction has been decreased from 2010 to 2020.

3.5.2 The Criterion in the Environmental Performance – Impacts on Environment

Environmental issues have been widely concerned all over the world. As Schulz and Flanigan (2016) highlighted in the TBL framework, the major environmental issues could be varied based on different industries and countries. Therefore, to measure the four housebuilders' performance within the environmental dimension, the environmental issues mostly cared for in the housebuilding sector during the decades of 2010s are identified and analysed here.

3.5.2.1 Climate Change

It has been widely accepted that climate change is one of the typical and essential issues in the contemporary world. Climate change is found in various environmental phenomena, which further affects human life, for example, global warming, the amount and frequency of rainfall, severe weather, the rising sea level and others. According to the World Meteorological Organization (2021), the years between 2011 and 2020 was the warmest decade on record, and 2016, 2019 and 2020 are the top 3 years with the highest temperature in the past 22 years. Meanwhile, extreme weather has emerged endlessly in the UK. Storms, strong

winds, heavy rainfall, heatwave have happened in the last few years and widely affect the business (Met Office, 2021).

Climate change has attracted much attention in the British housebuilding industry as it has affected the housebuilding process and the completed houses and the customers (or inhabitants). The construction process is directly influenced by climate change in the housebuilding sector. Extreme or unexpected climatic events, like storms, river flooding, tornado, would disrupt the building process damage the building material, which may cause the construction over the planned time or budget (Hertin et al., 2003). Some gradually changed climatic phenomenon of the drier summer, wetter winter, more winds and raised coastal shorten the working time for building houses, affect the building materials and housing design, the timeline of after-sales maintenances. For instance, some houses are equipped with air conditioners, and some houses in the wetter area require advanced drainage systems in their communities (Hertin et al., 2003).

With awareness of the climate changes, customers' attitudes, needs and preferences are also affected. Customers would take the risks of flooding, flood and storm protection, the air conditioners and some features of a house into consideration (Eves and Kippes, 2010). Meanwhile, some financial institutions have also updated their policies regarding particular climatic situations. The insurance companies are less willing to cover the flood risk for the properties in the floodplains and request higher insurance premiums for the after-sales warranty. Therefore, climate changes also indirectly influence the housebuilding sector via different stakeholders. In the land planning stage, the housebuilders are reluctant to buy the areas with a high risk of flooding due to the stricter planning policy and few insurance supports. In the designing and construction process, housebuilders have made more investments to reduce the climatic consequences

(Rymarzak and Siemińska, 2012). Furthermore, most of all, the behaviours that generate greenhouse gases have been regulated by laws.

About the serve climate change, the causes of climate change have been investigated, and many scientists believe that the emission of greenhouse gases (GHG) is one of the most important reasons for the recent climate change (The Countryside Charity, 2020). Countries worldwide have taken actions to reduce the emission of greenhouse gases to reduce the negative consequences of climate change. The British government released the Climate Change Act 2008, bonding the environmental target and law together and emphasised that greenhouse gas emissions in the UK will be reduced to zero by 2050 (Sasse et al., 2020).

Considering the negative impacts of climate change, the emission of GHG, especially Carbon dioxide, has been a critical environmental topic in the UK housebuilding sector. Some housebuilders must publish information on GHG emissions in their annual or strategic reports (Department for Business, Innovation & Skills, 2013). Therefore, the public could read GHG emissions of their housebuilder, which help them have a better understanding of the builders' contributions to the environment. Furthermore, the GHG emission would be one metric to assess the four housebuilders' performance in the environmental dimension. Bowles and McLaren's study (2021) found a decrease of private housebuilders' carbon intensity per home, suggesting the builders' environmental efforts on GHG emission.

3.5.2.2 Construction Waste

Waste is another environmental issue closely related to social sustainability and local inhabitants' benefit. Furthermore, in the UK housebuilding sector, this issue

is severely based on the growing waste from the construction, demolition and excavation in 2018. In the construction project, the spare, damaged or scrap materials might become waste after construction. The typical construction waste includes concrete, bricks, tiles and ceramics, metallic waste, dredging materials, soil contamination, wood, glass and plastic and so on (Osmani, 2011).

For the UK society and environment, the negative impacts of construction waste are apparent. They were constructing waste to increase the burden of landfills. The increased landfills would emit methane, further polluting the air and worsening the greenhouse issue. Some hazardous materials like paints and varnishes might contaminate soil and cause pollution in the groundwater. Besides, in some demolition projects, lots of loose dust and debris would be caused, which might be left around the local area or even miles away (Welles, 2020). The hazardous dust might raise the risks of respiratory illness. For inhabitants, these adverse outcomes might influence their living conditions and personal health to a large extent (Osmani, 2011). Furthermore, from the point of the sustainable environment, the failure in waste management might threaten the future development of the natural and social environment. In addition to the impacts on the environment and society, waste and disposal represent the cost for the companies because they are responsible for disposing of the wastes appropriately. In the government's environmental reporting guideline, the information on waste management is suggested to be included in the annual report or even set as a KPI to measure the environmental performance (Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs, 2019).

According to the waste data, the recovery rate of non-hazardous construction and demolition waste has been raised to 92.3% in 2018, which can be a reference when assessing the four housebuilders' performance in reducing waste. The total

generation of the construction and demolition waste has been increased, from 59.2 million tonnes in 2010 to 67.8 million tonnes in 2018 (Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs, 2021). Moreover, the latest waste data indicates that around 3/5 (62%) of total UK waste came from construction, demolition and excavation in 2018 (Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs, 2021), which is higher than other sources of waste.

Figure 9. Waste Generation by Source, UK, 2018 (Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs, 2021)

In addition to the GHG emission, waste generation also has been regarded as another major environmental issue in the housebuilding sector. After Brexit, the UK government developed a set of objectives for waste management with referring to the EU's Circular Economy Package. A recycling rate of 70% by 2020 was suggested for construction and demolition waste, and the UK realised this target many years ago (Sharman, 2018). However, considering the proportion of construction waste, Sharman (2018) believed only minor improvements had been made in waste reduction in the UK.

The GHG emission within the housebuilding sector or construction sector is not published; therefore, the overall performance in reducing GHG emission of the UK

housebuilders cannot be judged by the change in GHG emission. According to the latest statistics, the GHG emission was decreased by 43.8% between 1990 to 2019, which proves some progress has been made towards the 2050 net zero emission target in the UK (Waite, 2021). However, towards the 2050 target, the current progress in GHG emissions, including the housebuilding sector, seems inadequate.

The UK government pledged to adopt a low-carbon housebuilding policy and realise zero carbon in the newly built homes by 2016. However, this policy was abolished in 2015, and only around 9% of newly built homes achieved zero carbon in 2016 (Reality Check, 2021). Recently, the leading housebuilder Taylor Wimpey described the government's 2025 target for carbon emission as "too ambitious" based on the previous GHG emission progress (Boren, 2021).

3.5.3 The Criterion in the Financial Performance

According to the TBL framework, the key financial indicators would assess the economic performance (Książak and Fischbach, 2017). Typically, the financial indicators include revenue and profit, which the private housebuilders highlight. In addition, the dividend payment is used to examine the financial performance of the private builders, which would demonstrate the builder's decisions on money spending for future projects (Sholichah et al., 2021). Based on these financial indicators, the literature on the overall economic performance in the housing building sector is reviewed, which provide a general profile to analyse the four housebuilders' performance afterwards.

The Global Financial Crisis badly hit the UK housebuilding industry, before which the industry was in a boom period. Private housebuilders have experienced 3 phases in response to the Global Financial Crisis: investment, recovery and growth

(Payne, 2015, 2019). In the early 2010s, housebuilders held more cautious attitudes about the investment and focused on generating cash flows in their business instead of making returns to shareholders. The traditional business strategies mainly were adopted to help housebuilders gradually recover from the recession, like opening or continuing the construction on-site at a better margin, reducing operation costs (Archer and Cole, 2016). Meanwhile, the Help to Buy was introduced by the UK government to provide the households with loans to access the mortgages for purchasing new housing (National Audit Office, 2019). This program helped build housebuilders' confidence in construction and support their housing sales.

By examining the significant housebuilders' financial statements in the UK, (Archer and Cole, 2014, 2016) analysed the economic performance in the UK housing sector. The total revenue of top housebuilders was decreased between 2008 to 2010 when housebuilders suspended or stopped the construction. During that time, housebuilders efforted to develop the right recovery strategies, and many of them took the traditional actions that raised housing margin and reduced operating costs simultaneously (Payne, 2019). From 2010 to 2013, housebuilders have gradually grown the company revenue (Archer and Cole, 2014). Furthermore, in 2014, many housebuilders' revenue has returned to the level before the crisis. Since then, the group revenue in the housebuilding industry has continued the growth trend until 2019 (Williams, 2019, Archer and Cole, 2021).

Before the Global Financial Crisis, the UK housebuilding industry was in a booming period. Furthermore, compared with the builders' financial performance before the Global Financial Crisis, the 2014 probability in the UK housebuilding sector generally returned to the pre-crisis level. According to Archer and Cole (2021), the profit before tax of the national housebuilders surpassed the pre-crisis level by 45%

and 100%, respectively, in 2015 and 2017. Therefore, the first decade of the 2010s was not only a “recovery” but also a “feast” for the housebuilders (Archer and Cole, 2021), especially the large builders, as they have made historically unexpected profits during this period.

With the housebuilders’ extensions, the market value of the UK housebuilding sector has been raised at the same time. As Hardman & Co Research presented (Williams, 2019), the UK housebuilding market value was below 7.5 billion in 2010, reaching a peak at almost 45 billion in 2017. This also confirms the development of commercial size and industrial economy in the UK housebuilding sector, which relies on the national housebuilders’ financial progress to a large extent (Archer and Cole, 2021). In addition, Oakley (2016) also suggested the operating profit margin and returned on capital employed as the essential metrics to measure housebuilders’ financial performance. By examining some of the largest housebuilders’ financial accounts, it finds that the operating profit margin and return on capital employed increased at a relatively fast pace since 2010, which also outperformed the level before the crisis in 2017 (Crosby, Devaney and Wyatt, 2017). According to (Archer and Cole, 2021), large private housebuilders has raised financial returns (dividend payment) to their shareholders. However, the dividend payment did not return to the reproduction in the UK housebuilding sector.

Overall, housebuilders’ financial performance has been high or above between 2010 to 2019. Although the existing studies have focused on different financial indicators among the private housebuilders, most of them conclude that the profitability has been improved at an “unexpected rapid” rate, which also represents a high efficiency when housebuilders well performed in the finance of housebuilders to generate high or very high financial performance.

3.6 Summary

The review on the UK housebuilding industry and the major private housebuilders provides contextual backgrounds to assess the private housebuilder's performance. The private housebuilders' efforts and performance for the benefits of society, the environment, and the business profits could be well explained considering the external factors. Meanwhile, the company profiles of the four cases are also reviewed to help build a better understanding of the comparison discussion part.

Considering that the specific metrics would vary based on different industries and businesses, the author further refines some specific metrics within the economic, social and environmental dimensions of this study's proposed performance assessment framework. The advanced metrics are most needed or cared for by the inhabitants, or mainly highlighted and typical in the UK housebuilding sector from 2010 to 2020. This ensures that assessing the private housebuilders' performance for the benefits of society and the environment and their financial performance would be critical, up-to-date, and reliable. Meanwhile, the progress and the current conditions of these highlighted aspects are reviewed to understand better the industrial performance, based on which seven research hypotheses are finally raised.

Figure 10. The Theoretical Framework for Performance Assessment (the author)

CHAPTER 4, RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1 Introduction

This chapter explains the methodological underpinning and ethical considerations for the thesis. The research methodology is developed to address the research questions and meet the research aim and objectives.

Implicated from the “research onion”, the research methodology is structured by the research approach to theory development, research strategy and research method. The explanations, rationales, and possible limitations of each methodological element are included in the following contents. The questionnaire approach is taken to collect the data based on the quantitative research method. The quantitative data analysis uses SPSS and Excel to examine the data reliability and analyse the raw data, which presents the processed findings for further analysis and discussion. In the final part, the methodological limitations and ethical considerations are highlighted. Since being aware of the possible issues from the research methodology, the author raises the corresponding mitigations to avoid or reduce their impacts.

4.2 Research Approach

The research approach is referred to as theory development or approach to reasoning (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). Based on the researcher’s level of clear theory at the initial research stage, the research is usually conducted via deductive reasoning or inductive reasoning (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). A deductive approach is defined as a process to test a theory and examine whether the existed theory can be applied to the specific research questions, in

which the hypothesis would be developed based on this theory. Typically, deductive research is started with hypotheses that are developed based on the existing conclusions, and the data analysis is used to evaluate the hypotheses to finally raise the conclusion (Wilson, 2014). The process of the deductive approach includes theory, raising hypothesis, testing hypothesis, and conclusions (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2017). The collected data is used to test the hypothesis in the deductive approach while exploring the phenomenon and building a pattern in the inductive approach phenomenon (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). Therefore, deductive research is conducted to verify the existing knowledge, while inductive research builds the new theory (Hyde, 2000).

For this thesis, the deductive approach would be appropriate. Firstly, many studies have been done to discuss today's enterprises' social, environmental, and financial performance. Meanwhile, some studies present systemic approaches to measure social, environmental and financial performance. Focusing on the research topic, the author has reviewed some literature to describe the general private housebuilding sector, like the major housing issues, the progress towards these issues, the successes and failures of the private housebuilders in different dimensions. Furthermore, a few scholars studied the financial performance of housebuilders by analysing their financial statements every year. The availability of these relevant literatures ensures the feasibility of the deductive approach and helps the author formulate a reasonable hypothesis about the research questions. In the test stage, the author decides to collect and analyse the data quantitatively because it would keep high objectivity in assessing the four housebuilders' performance and match the author's philosophy. Then the data analysis and discussion are conducted to compare the outcomes and the proposed hypothesis, which would further reject or confirm the existing theories. With the deductive approach, a straightforward research process is presented in Figure 11, and the

specific methodical options are explained in the following contents.

Figure 11. Process of the Deductive Approach

4.3 Research Hypothesis

After reviewing the background research and literature review, seven research hypotheses are raised.

Based on the current situation of the housing supply in the UK market and inhabitants' housing demands theory mentioned in 3.5.1.2.1, the first hypothesis is raised as:

The four private housebuilders' performance in raising housing supply is dissatisfactory from 2010 to 2020.

The second hypothesis is raised as follow considering the industrial-wide efforts on the affordability issue and the influencing factors of affordability mentioned in 3.5.1.2.2:

The four private housebuilders' performance in raising housing affordability is dissatisfactory from 2010 to 2020.

The theoretical views about the housing quality and the national customer satisfaction survey findings mentioned in 3.5.1.2.3 help raise the third hypothesis as:

The four private housebuilders' performance in housing quality is satisfactory from 2010 to 2020.

The research focusing on the general environment performance in the UK housebuilding sector is not found. Therefore, the thesis cannot precisely define the environmental performance of the four private housebuilders in the hypothesis. However, based on the above examination of the progress have been made in the GHG emission and waste management within the housebuilding sector, as well as the current situation of these environmental issues in 3.5.2, the thesis can still raise the fourth hypothesis that

The four private housebuilders' performance for the environmental benefits is below satisfactory from 2010 to 2020.

In terms of the builder's performance in serving benefits for society and the environment, the theoretical framework suggests assessing via the criterion in the social and environmental dimension. This assessment system is also included in the data collection to ensure the respondents take the same assessment system and criterion. As a result, the performance assessment for the social and environments should be led by the result on each specific criterion. Based on the theoretical framework and the above hypothesis, the fifth hypothesis is raised as:

The four private housebuilders' performance for the benefits of society and the environment is dissatisfactory from 2010 to 2020.

According to the financial performance of the UK housebuilding sector and the builder's finance theory mentioned in 3.5.3, the sixth hypothesis is that

The four private housebuilders' financial performance is high or above from 2010 to 2020.

Accordingly, the seventh hypothesis of comparing the private builder's performance for the benefits of society and the environment and their financial performance is raised:

The target private housebuilders' financial performance has surpassed the performance for the benefits of society and the environment.

4.4 Research Strategy

4.4.1 Case Study

The thesis is taken based on the case study. The case study is “an empirical inquiry” to conduct an in-depth investigation on the contemporary phenomenon in the real-world context, “especially when the boundaries between phenomenon and context may not be evident” (Yin, 2018, p9). About whether the research could adopt the case study or not, Yin (2018) raises three conditions: the type of research questions, the extent of investigators' control over behavioural events, and the degree of focus on contemporary. When scholars take the case study, the situations should be where the research question is “how” or “why” form, no control is over behavioural events, and focuses are on contemporary events (Yin, 2018).

This thesis investigates the four housebuilders' performance in serving the

benefits of society and the environment and their financial performance from 2010 to 2020 in the UK. The British housebuilding sector and the four housebuilding companies are the “real-world context”. Meanwhile, the four housebuilders’ social, environmental, and financial performance that serve the social and environmental benefits and their profits from 2010 to 2020 belongs to the “contemporary phenomenon”. Based on the research aim, a set of “how” questions are raised in the first chapter, which matches the research questions formation of the case study. Besides, the author has no control over the actual behavioural events of the four housebuilders and their inhabitants. Based on these judgments, the case study is applicable in this research.

The advantages or characteristics of the case study encourage the author to take this research strategy as well. First, the researcher can realise various objectives through the case study. Ridder (2017) highlighted the contribution of the case study on building, developing and testing theories, which would help with the hypotheses test of deductive approach in this study. Secondly, the case study is practical to describe phenomena and further explore the specific aspects of phenomena at a deep level (Harrison et al., 2017); therefore, Yin (2018, p9) described it as an “in-depth investigation”. A case study provides the means to investigate complicated phenomena with multiple variables (Merriam, 2019). Also, in a case study, the data examination and analysis would be taken within the particular context, namely the selected cases’ context (Yin, 2018). This advantage helps the author identify the real context of the housebuilding companies instead of the context stimulated in experiment research (Zainal, 2007). Then the case study encourages an empirical and in-depth analysis with considering the specific variables and conditions in each case (Merriam, 2019). Hence, the author would examine the particular profile of the selected cases (housebuilders) and consider how the four cases (housebuilders) served the social and environmental benefits

and created their business profits from 2010. Besides, with the intrinsic, instrumental and collective data collection method in the case study, the collected data and data analysis could be qualitative, quantitative, or both (Yin, 2018), which gives the author high flexibility in the data collection stage.

4.4.2 The Procedure of Case Study Design

There is no fixed procedure for conducting case study research. Based on existing studies, Eisenhardt (1989) proposed a case study procedure including the steps of getting started with the research question, selecting cases, crafting instruments and protocol of data collection methods, entering the field to collect data, analysing data, shaping hypotheses, unfolding by comparing with existing literature and reaching closure. Another widely accepted process of conducting a case study is included in Yin's book (2018), which is particularly for the research with multiple cases. Comparatively, the two types of case study procedures are similar in basic logic.

Step	Activity	Reason
Getting Started	Definition of research question Possibly a priori constructs	Focuses efforts Provides better grounding of construct measures
Selecting Cases	Neither theory nor hypotheses Specified population	Retains theoretical flexibility Constrains extraneous variation and sharpens external validity
	Theoretical, not random, sampling	Focuses efforts on theoretically useful cases—i.e., those that replicate or extend theory by filling conceptual categories
Crafting Instruments and Protocols	Multiple data collection methods	Strengthens grounding of theory by triangulation of evidence
	Qualitative and quantitative data combined Multiple investigators	Synergistic view of evidence Fosters divergent perspectives and strengthens grounding
Entering the Field	Overlap data collection and analysis, including field notes	Speeds analyses and reveals helpful adjustments to data collection
	Flexible and opportunistic data collection methods	Allows investigators to take advantage of emergent themes and unique case features
Analyzing Data	Within-case analysis	Gains familiarity with data and preliminary theory generation
	Cross-case pattern search using divergent techniques	Forces investigators to look beyond initial impressions and see evidence thru multiple lenses
Shaping Hypotheses	Iterative tabulation of evidence for each construct	Sharpens construct definition, validity, and measurability
	Replication, not sampling, logic across cases Search evidence for “why” behind relationships	Confirms, extends, and sharpens theory Builds internal validity
Enfolding Literature	Comparison with conflicting literature	Builds internal validity, raises theoretical level, and sharpens construct definitions
	Comparison with similar literature	Sharpens generalizability, improves construct definition, and raises theoretical level
Reaching Closure	Theoretical saturation when possible	Ends process when marginal improvement becomes small

Figure 12. The Procedure of Building Theory via Case Study Research (Eisenhardt, 1989)

Figure 13. Process of Case Study (Yin, 2018)

Based on the above procedures of case study research, the case study steps are developed.

No.	Step
1	Define the research questions, raise the research hypotheses
2	Select cases
3	Design data collection
4	Collect data from each case
5	Data analysis of each case
6	Test the hypotheses, confirm or modify the hypotheses and draw the conclusion

Table 2. The Procedure of the Case Study in this Research

4.4.3 Case Selection

4.4.3.1 Number of Cases

According to Yin (2018), one single case or multiple cases could be selected for research. Researching with the single case study lets the researcher focus on one case and explore the detailed aspects in this case (Ridder, 2017). Nevertheless, finding a single critical case to test the well-formulated theory is difficult, which means a single case usually lacks generalisation (Yin, 2018). Considering the individual business profile, the author thinks the single case might not be enough to present the critical and empirical discussion on the housebuilders' social, environmental and financial performance.

Baxter and Jack (2008) mentioned that the evidence from multiple case studies is more reliable and convincing and further build a broader exploration of research questions and theoretical development. Moreover, a systematic comparison across multiple cases would be conducted to clarify the similarities and differences among multiple cases (Ridder, 2017). Given that the thesis plans to compare the performance of the different housebuilders, multiple cases are necessary. Towards the research aim, the author decides to take four cases to raise

the reliability and validity of this research. Also, the comparison among multiple housebuilders would help identify the differences and similarities in the four builders' performance for the benefit of society, the environment, and their financial performance.

4.4.3.2 Selecting Criterion

There is no general agreement on the specific metrics of case selection in the existing research, but scholars give some suggestions for the case selection. In terms of the case sample, the selection is purposeful. It is assumed that the researchers would like to get insights from the cases so that the cases that can primarily serve the research aim are usually selected (Merriam, 2019), which is agreed by Yin (2018), who suggests the case selection should consider the specific purpose within the whole range of inquiring. Similarly, Suri (2011) suggests that the selection criteria align with the research logic, purpose, and approach.

First of all, this thesis focuses on the performance assessment of the large private housebuilders during the period between 2010 and 2020. As mentioned above, private housebuilders have played the most significant role in the supply of the UK housebuilding sector since the last century. Furthermore, the group of large housebuilders has a relatively more substantial presence, while 2,500 SME housebuilders were only accounted for a small proportion of the newly completed dwellings (Home Builders Federation, 2017). Meanwhile, Perrini, Russo and Tencati (2007) highlighted that the larger companies are expected to take more CSR. Therefore, the larger national housebuilders are expected to have more outstanding performance for the benefits of society and the environment. Based on the research scope and objectives, the selected case should be the large private housebuilder active in the UK market during 2010 and 2020, and some basic

criteria are listed below.

- Enterprise type: private
- Company size: large housebuilders (annual housing supply is equal to or over 1,000 units)
- Business focus: developing dwellings
- Business range: national wide in the UK
- Publishing financial and sustainability report
- History: Founded before the 21st century

With such criteria, there are still many housebuilding companies qualified. Therefore, a further selection is conducted here. Generally, Yin (2018) divided the selection logic into two types: literal replication and theoretical replication, designed to predict similar results and contrasting results. With the purpose of literal replication, the cases that own similar settings would be selected and expected to generate similar results, while the purpose of theoretical replication let the case with different settings be selected (Yin, 2018). For this thesis, the logic of theoretical replication is followed for further case selection.

Within the scope of large private housebuilders, Barratt Development, Persimmon, Bellway and Miller Homes are finally selected as the cases in this study based on the different settings of their annual supply. The annual housing supply is regarded as a core set here because it is an essential element for contributing to the social and environmental benefits and the business profits at the same time. Although the four cases all belong to the prominent builder, they can further represent three sub-groups with different average annual supply from 2010 to 2020: over 10,000 units (Barratt Developments and Persimmon), between 5,000 to 9,999 units (Bellway) and below 4,999 units (Miller Homes). The different

levels of annual supply demonstrate the different business scales of the four builders and help the author compare the performance of builders with different supply scales.

4.4.4 Backgrounds of the Four Cases

The thesis would compare the performance of the four private housebuilders, and the four builder's company profiles would help build a better understanding of what they have done and what they could do.

4.4.4.1 Case One – Barratt Developments

Barratt Developments Plc., previously named Greensitt Bros, was founded in 1958 and is now based in Newcastle upon Tyne (Barratt Developments Plc, 2021a). Today's Barratt Developments' business development and scale are built on its relatively positive history. At the early stage, Barratt Developments was mainly led by a builder, Lewis Greensitt and an accountant, Lawrie Barratt, whose building and financial expertise helped them well lead the company. After the political restriction on the private housebuilders, the housebuilding market gradually recovered, and the completion of the dwellings was increased. Meanwhile, Barratt Developments also quickly raised its home completions and extended the business, with which Barratt Developments was listed on the London Stock Exchange in 1968 (Wellings, 2006).

According to the review on the housebuilding sector, several major crises have happened since 1970 and have damaged many housebuilders. However, the history of Barratt Developments tells people that this builder could always find ways to grow from these crises. The company leader, Lawrie, was regarded as a talented and dominant person in Barratt developments, who made customers'

purchase easier with the innovative package in Barratt Development's business during the 1970s, like introducing the Part Exchange project, building "Mayfair" one-bedroom house for the affordability need. Barratt Developments was the first housebuilder that used national TV and cinema commercials, which enhanced the traditional brand image of Barratt (Barratt Developments Plc, 2018a). With the growing market share, Barratt Developments developed a group structure that set the local operating companies with the support of national financial and management resources, which ensured high flexibility and adaption to Barratt Development changes. This extraordinary model was copied by many builders afterwards (Barratt Developments Plc, 2018a). Except for growing its own business, Barratt Developments also expanded via acquisitions. Some smaller housebuilding companies were taken by Barratt Development, which has enriched its product line. From 2010 to 2020, Barratt Developments has the housing brands to cover different markets: Barratt Home, David Wilson Homes, Barratt London and David Wilson Homes. Specifically, David Wilson Homes has been produced luxury or highly superior homes in the high-end market. Wilson Bowden Development is expertise in commercial developments (Barratt Developments Plc, 2007).

From Barratt Development's history, it finds business development has been highlighted, like expanding market share, raising housing supply, improving business profits. Furthermore, in recent decades, Barratt Developments has more highlighted customer orientation in its business. Barratt Developments sets the business vision as 'to lead the future of housebuilding by putting customers at the heart of everything we do' (Barratt Developments Plc, 2021b). This means Barratt Developments should have a high awareness of creating benefits for the customers (or inhabitants), and the thesis would disclose how Barratt Developments performed.

Barratt Developments' "green" initiative is related to the thesis. As Barratt Developments claimed, the company encourages the properties for sustainability; therefore, many solutions have been raised to meet the demands of energy efficiency, renewable technologies, reducing carbon emission, increased green space, and other sustainable issues (Barratt Developments, 2008). For example, the Barratt Green House was the first environmentally friendly home and met the criteria for zero stamp duty. Furthermore, Barratt Developments started building a zero carbon community in England (Seager, 2008).

Another point worth mentioning is land planning. Barratt Developments has created a large team of skilled planners and built a strong relationship with the landowners, local planning authorities, and communities, contributing to the 95% consent from the local planning authorities for the building projects (Barratt Developments Plc, 2018a). This information believes the planning systems should have fewer contains for Barratt Developments, which should not be an excuse to supply performance.

Through over 60-years of development, Barratt Developments has experienced several ups and downs, and it has become a leader in the housebuilding sector. The annual housing supply of Barratt Developments is in the top range. Barratt Developments is a national builder with 27 divisions and 366 active sales outlets in the UK. The profile confirms Barratt Developments' productivity, market share, and brand reputation advantages. It should be one of the most typical cases in the UK's largely successful and private housebuilding companies.

Figure 14. Brands and National Range of Barratt Developments (Barratt Developments Plc, 2020)

4.4.4.2 Case Two - Persimmon

Duncan Davidson established Persimmon in 1972, who was employed by another big housebuilder, George Wimpey, before. Then Persimmon began to expand the business based on its Anglia business since 1976. Afterwards, Persimmon operated business around Midlands, South West England, Wessex and North East. For business expansion, Persimmon acquired Sketchmead in 1984, which led Persimmon to be listed on the London Stock Exchange in the next year (Persimmon, 2020).

With the steady expansion in the regional market, Persimmon aimed at a more extensive business range. Since 1995, a set of acquisitions has been made by Persimmon: Ideal Homes, Beazer Homes, Westbury Homes and some small

acquisitions on Laing Homes, Tilbury Douglas Scottish Homes, Merewood Homes and others. The acquisitions of Ideal Homes helped expand Persimmon's business in the southeast market, and the acquisitions of Beazer Homes brought the Charles Church brand for Persimmon (Wellings, 2006).

From 2010 to 2020, Persimmon has been one of the largest national builders in the UK, making it a typical case for this thesis. Till 2020, Persimmon has 31 regional offices throughout the UK and owns three home brands: Persimmon Home, Charles Church and Westbury Partnerships (Persimmon Plc, 2020). Persimmon Home is the core brand of this group, which delivers a wide range of homes all over the UK. Charles Church focuses on offering "large, higher specification homes in premium locations across the UK" to meet the demand for the premium home. Furthermore, Westbury Partnerships majorly deliver affordable social houses sold to the housing associations in the UK (Persimmon Plc, 2020). Besides, Persimmon has four brands related to the building business: Space 4 to produce timber frames, Brickworks to produce concrete bricks, Tileworks for manufacturing concrete roof tile and FibreNest for ultrafast and full internet connection (Persimmon Plc, 2020).

Figure 15. Home Brands of Persimmon Plc (Persimmon Plc, 2020)

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Figure 16. National Coverage Local Presence of Persimmon (Persimmon Plc, 2020)

4.4.4.3 Case Three - Bellway

Bellway Plc. was established by John Thomas Bell in 1946 when the Second World War was just over and the housing market was recovering. Bell's three sons joined the business successively, making it a family business early. In 1964, Bellway went public on the London Stock Exchange, and now it is one of the companies in the FTSE 250 Index. Founded in Newcastle upon Tyne, Bellway first operated the business in North England and Scotland. Furthermore, since the early 1970s, Bellway started the business expansion to Southeast England and London and the nearby regions. Until the 1980s, Bellway became a national housebuilder with autonomously operating regional divisions. Although the crisis in the housebuilding sector hit many housebuilders during the 1990s, Bellway was still able to make profits and keep a certain of house sales (Wellings, 2006) (Bellway, 2021).

Since the 2000s, the British housebuilding industry has seen many consolidations, mergers and acquisitions among the private housebuilders to compete. More minor participating in this competition, Bellway focused more on organic growth by improving its market share. Furthermore, this business model has taken Bellway as one of the top housebuilders in the 21st century. Same with Barratt Developments and Persimmon. Bellway was also founded in the last century and developed to the top large builders in the UK. However, Bellway's business scale and market share are relatively smaller than Barratt Developments and Persimmon's.

Figure 17. National Coverage of Bellway (Bellway p.l.c., 2019)

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further details.

4.4.4.4 Case Four - Miller Homes

Miller Homes was founded in 1934 by Sir James Miller and his family. Affected by his father, Miller was trained as an architect, which laid the professional knowledge for his housebuilding business (The Herald Scotland, 1999). During the 1930s, this housebuilder was at a leading position in Edinburgh with annual supplies of about 500 homes. Then after experiencing the Second World War and political control on the private housebuilding sector, Miller Homes resumed the housebuilding business on a small scale (Wellings, 2006). Later Miller Homes expanded the business from Edinburgh and some Scottish areas to South East England and Yorkshire, but the business was not good. Based on Wellings' (2006) records, Miller Homes had experienced a relatively slow development before the 21st century, whose housing supplies had been kept below 1000 most of the time. Then Miller Homes took some regional acquisitions to grow their business, which helped improve its business scale and sales (Wellings, 2006).

Figure 18. National Coverage of Miller Homes (Miller Homes, 2020)

4.5 Research Method

Generally, the research method includes qualitative, quantitative and mixed (Creswell, 2017). The research method decides the type of data collected approach of data collection, which further affects the data analysis. The decisions on the research method are in line with the author's philosophy and are expected to realise the research aim in this thesis.

4.5.1 Quantitative Research

In this thesis, the quantitative research method is employed. The quantitative method was initiatively developed for natural science. Then it has been widely used in social science research (Creswell, 2017). The first reason to take the

quantitative method is that it assumes the social facts are objective and independent and the researcher is the objective outsider (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2013). Creswell (2017) gives a more concise explanation about the quantitative research method as explaining the phenomena by collecting numerical data and analysing them via the mathematically based methods. Generally, the quantitative method is appropriate for the thesis with quantitative, numerical research answers and involves the quantified options, attitudes and behaviours (Sukamolson, 2007). Based on the above explanation of the quantitative method, it believes this research method is fitted. The quantitative method is scientific because it would collect a large amount of data and analyse them statistically, which would help increase stability and consistency. According to Daniel (2016), quantitative research is replicable, making the collected data more reliable. The author wants the performance assessment of the four private housebuilders to be quantified, especially the social performance assessment, to draw objective outcomes. Meanwhile, Bryman (2012) also highlights that the quantitative data would help save time and resources with the data analysis tools, which release the pressures from the limited time and resources for this study.

4.5.2 Data Collection Approach

Data collection is a critical step in the research methodology, as it provides evidence to answer the research questions, test the hypotheses and raise the conclusions. With the quantitative research method, the data collection is mainly applied to describe or measure the level of occurrences based on numeric calculations (Blaikie, 2003). In collecting the quantitative data, scholars raise several approaches, like questionnaire, experiment, and questionnaire is the most adopted approach in social research (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). In this thesis, the questionnaire approach is adopted to obtain the quantitative description of the four housebuilders' social, environmental and financial

performance assessment from the perspective of their inhabitants. Several elements involved in this method are explained below with the questionnaire approach.

According to Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2016) and Julien (2008), the questionnaire is developed to systematically collect data from a range of respondents and is typically used for descriptive or explanatory research. For example, researchers would use the attitude or opinion survey to describe the variability in different phenomena. In this thesis, the questionnaire is designed to collect the inhabitant's view to assess four housebuilders' social, environmental and financial performance.

According to Gillham (2008), the questionnaire approach allows the respondents to complete it by themselves; therefore, it provides more flexibility to the respondents, keeps the limited contact between the researcher and the respondents, and reduces the possible pressures of respondents. Meanwhile, compared to experiment and interview, the questionnaire approach could efficiently, conveniently, and economically access a relatively large scope of samples. This advantage is particularly important with the broad access to the internet during the pandemic period. In this study, both the offline and online questionnaires are distributed. These advantages of the questionnaire encourage the author to take this approach. Few involvements of the author help reinforce the objectivity in this thesis. The questionnaire could collect the objective and quantified results from an enormous scope of homeowners of the four housebuilders, which increases the generalisation and validity of the results. Also, the flexibility, convenience, concision the questionnaire approach offered is higher than others, making it a preferred approach for this study that is required to complete the data collection within a limited timeline and with little funds.

However, the drawbacks of the questionnaire approach should be noticed simultaneously. First of all, the development of a questionnaire could be complex, for which lots of literature have been reviewed to design the appropriate questions. Secondly, despite access to a broader range of samples, the poor response rate and validity could be a problem as no one monitors this process. Regarding this issue, the author regularly reminds the respondents with the uncompleted questionnaire, like sending emails and posting reminders on social media. Meanwhile, the author also constantly shares the questionnaire link on various websites and online communities. The questionnaire is designed with close-ended questions and a clear structure to raise the response rate, which allows the respondents to complete it within 10 minutes. Furthermore, a large proportion of the questionnaire is distributed online, letting the respondents answer the questions at their own time and pace. Patten (2016) mentions another disadvantage: subjective judgment might be raised when selecting the participants, which might not always reflect reality. To overcome this problem, the author sends out the questionnaire randomly among the customers (inhabitants) of the four housebuilders all around the UK.

4.5.2.1 Target Sample (Respondent)

The questionnaire is targeted at the customers (inhabitants) of Barratt Developments, Persimmon, Bellway and Miller Homes all over the UK. Based on the TBL framework, the private housebuilders' performance for the benefits of society and the environment would be assessed via examining their performance within the social and environmental dimensions. Specifically, the metrics in the social dimension are defined as the builders' performance in raising housing supply, housing affordability and housing quality. Furthermore, the environment

metric is the builders' impacts on the environment, which is examined by the efforts on reducing GHG emission, waste and building environmentally friendly properties.

The target respondents should have adequate knowledge about these aspects of their home builders. Typically a series of information of the housebuilders, like available housing stocks, housing selling price, housing quality, after-sales service, is usually studied before the customers make the purchase (Al-Nahdi, Ghazzawi and Bakar, 2015). Considering the values of a property, customers are usually careful in purchasing the property product and comparing properties produced by more than one builder. Therefore, the purchasing experience of these respondents firstly prepares them to answer this questionnaire. After living in the property for some time, the respondents should have more knowledge about the property's quality and energy efficiency based on their daily life experience. As the above chapter explains, the interest of the inhabitants is an essential element in terms of social benefits. Therefore, this thesis highlights inhabitants' perspectives when assessing the four private housebuilders' performance in serving the social benefits. In addition to having good knowledge about the research questions, the inhabitant is also the most convincing and representative respondent for assessing the builder's performance for the benefit of society.

4.5.2.2 The Approach of Questionnaire Distribution

Based on different ways of distributing, completing and returning the questionnaire, Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2016) suggested some approaches to distribute the questionnaire, as Figure 19. The online and face-to-face questionnaires will be distributed to collect the data for this research. It is planned that 100 pieces of the questionnaire for each housebuilder would be sent out to

collect the inhabitants' views about their performance. The online questionnaire is distributed by email, social networking websites, and internet forums. For the face-to-face questionnaire, the author distributes it in the local communities and nearby shopping malls, supermarkets and parks, which helps engage the people with few accesses to the computer or smartphone.

In the target respondents, the samples would be selected randomly, which aims to reinforce the generalisation of each builders' result as Patten (2016) is concerned the poor response rate could be a drawback of the questionnaire, which did cause some troubles for the author. Firstly, the author distributed the questionnaire on social media platforms (e.g. Facebook, Twitter, etc.). Nevertheless, the response rate is relatively low because of the author's limited social circle. Therefore, the author asked for help from friends and colleagues who have been living in the UK for a longer time. These friends and colleagues helped share the questionnaire in a broader range. Meanwhile, the author also found some communities occupied by the Barratt Development, Persimmon, Bellway and Miller Homes' properties and dropped the offline questionnaire in the inhabitants' mailbox, which was a direct way, but few responses were received from this way. The author also sent out the questionnaire in the major shopping centres close to these communities, which helped collect some data but cost a long time. Since the outbreak of the Covid-19 in the UK, distributing the offline questionnaire has been stopped.

The access to the contacts of the target inhabitants of the four housebuilders should help collect more data. The author realised it was almost impossible to acquire these contacts considering the customers' privacy. Nevertheless, the authors still sent emails to the four housebuilders and sought their help to share the questionnaire with their customers on behalf of the author. Unfortunately, none of the housebuilders has replied to the author. The author expands the online

channels to share the questionnaire to raise the responses rate further. In addition to the social media platforms, the author posted the questionnaire on the public forums (e.g. PropertyHub, Property Forum, etc.) and topic discussion communities (e.g. Quora), which proved to be an efficient way to access respondents.

Figure 19. Survey Distribution Approaches (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016)

4.5.2.3 Design of Questionnaire

An appropriate questionnaire design is vital. The brief introduction, structure, questions should help respondents understand and answer the questions clearly and quickly to realise success in data collection (Creswell, 2009). The questionnaire design is based on the literature review and industry review in the second and third Chapters so that the authors would collect the data for the research questions in this thesis.

The questionnaire is divided into three sections with eleven questions in total. The first section collects the respondents' demographic information, including age, sex, occupation, and property type. The second section is designed to assess the four housebuilders' performance to benefit society and the environment.

The fifth to seventh questions focused on assessing the four housebuilders' performance for meeting the inhabitants' demands and helping with their concerns. The three questions are developed based on Rogers and Ryan's (2001) TBL approach to assessing the social performance and the significant role of customers (inhabitants) in the UK private housebuilding sector (Soetanto and Pan, 2009, Sousa, 2012, Schulz and Flanigan, 2016). Specifically, the three questions examine housing supply, affordability, and quality to assess the housebuilders' performance for the social benefits raised from the above industry review. The eighth question is about the four housebuilders' environmental performance, following the approach of examining the companies' influence on the environment (Uddin, Hassan and Tarique, 2008, Żak, 2015, Księżak and Fischbach, 2017). The author identified significant environmental issues (GHG emission and waste generation) in the UK housebuilding sector since 2010 to assess the four housebuilders' environmental performance. The respondents have limited knowledge about their builders' performance in the two environmental issues. Therefore, the eighth question remarks assessing the housebuilder's environment performance based on the environmental-friendly features of their property, like the energy performance certificate (EPC), the green community, etc. Based on the homeowner's (respondents) daily life, the respondents could provide credible assessments.

Comparatively, the homeowners assess their builder's environmental performance, usually based on their daily life experience regarding property's energy saving. However, about the business operation, the published secondary data of the specific environmental indicator provides another evidence to assess the builders' environment performance. The carbon intensity could represent each builders' performance to reduce the GHG emission, which accounts for the

annual supply. The intense waste ratio and recycled waste are collected from the company's annual report about waste management.

The third section is a summary and covers the overall performance assessment of the four housebuilders for the benefits of society and the environment and their financial performance, and the comparison between the financial and non-financial performance. Instead of directly collecting the response regarding the four housebuilders' performance for the benefits of society and the environment and business profits, the authors include the specific metrics and develop the related questions in the second section because the conception of the benefits of society and the environment could be relatively broad and vague for each respondent. Therefore the questions in the second section present a united assessment criterion for the respondents to finally assess their housebuilders' performance for serving the benefits of society and the environment. Furthermore, such a design of the questionnaire should ensure the comparability, consistency and credibility of the responses.

The Five-Point Likert scale is adopted when designing the answers to each survey question. The Likert scale is a typical method to collect data and is easy to understand for respondents. Instead of requiring the respondents to take an abstract stand on one particular topic, this scale allows the participants to respond with a degree of satisfaction. Furthermore, the responses under the Likert scale are easy to code with the particular numbers, which provide quantifiable results for the statistic analysis (Chyung et al., 2018). Also, a unipolar scale is used to design the responses as it is easier for respondents to focus on the degree of satisfaction at one time (Cai, Lin and Zhang, 2016). For the four housebuilders' performance in serving social and environmental benefits and creating business profit, the assessment includes five levels: 1) very satisfactory, 2) satisfactory, 3) neither

satisfactory nor dissatisfactory, 4) dissatisfactory, 5) very dissatisfactory. Furthermore, the assessment also includes five levels from very low to very high for the financial performance. The better efforts or performance the housebuilders have realised, the assessment would be better, and the satisfaction level would be higher the same time.

4.5.3 Secondary Data

In addition to the primary data, secondary data is also collected in this study. To ensure the validity and credibility of the research, the author is extremely cautious about the secondary data source. Therefore only the source with high authority and credibility is taken.

The option of the secondary data depends on the research objectives and questions. Firstly, secondary data regarding the overall UK housebuilding sector profile, like housing supply, housing selling price, and national customer satisfaction survey, is referred to. The data is mainly derived from the national statistics and the reports by the UK governmental bodies or organisations, which ensure data reliability. The secondary data of the builder's overall performance within the UK housebuilding sector clarifies the private housebuilders' overall performance in the particular social, environmental and financial aspects. This secondary analysis provides one perspective of assessing and comparing the four housebuilders' performance in the UK housebuilding sector. In addition to assessing the housebuilders' performance individually or among the four cases, such secondary data helps assess the four builders' performance in an industrial range, which also raises implications of the enormous private housebuilders' performance. Secondly, the secondary data about the four housebuilders, like their annual housing supply, housing average selling price, environmental index,

financial figures, is analysed in the discussion chapter. The secondary data is mainly acquired from the four housebuilders' annual reports and consolidated financial statements, the trusted channel. Using the company's secondary data provides further evidence to answer the research questions and finally draw credible and critical conclusions for this study.

The secondary data relevant to the research objectives and questions is available to the public, ensuring the author can access it conveniently. All the referred secondary data in this study are downloaded from the official websites. Including the secondary data is expected to reinforce the credibility, reliability, validity of this study. The secondary data would collaborate with the primary data and provide credible evidence to answer the research questions in the discussion part. Also, using secondary data would extend the angles to analyse the research findings. For example, the secondary data of annual housing supply directly points out the housebuilders' efforts with the supply issue, and the secondary data of land bank size also explains the gap between the builders' production capacity and real supply. Furthermore, the secondary data of greenhouse gas emissions and waste generation also clarifies the builders' performance in the two environmental issues, presenting more objective evidence for environmental performance assessment. Moreover, the financial figures should be the most accurate data to prove how the housebuilders have created their business profits since 2010. In addition, the secondary data method is time-efficient and cost-effective as these data have been collected by others (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). It is appropriate and beneficial to use it in this thesis, considering the possible benefits of using the secondary data and its limited costs.

4.5.4 Research Analysis

This thesis carries out the quantitative data analysis method to analyse the data collected from the questionnaires. The quantitative data would be analysed by the Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS) and Excel, the most used and helpful statistical software packages to help with an extensive range of statistical procedures (Sweet and Grace-Martin, 1999).

4.5.4.1 Expected Data

From the survey, three groups of primary data are expected to be collected. The first type of data is demographic information, which presents the different profiles of the respondents participating in the questionnaire. The second type of data focuses on the research question and indicates respondents' assessment of housebuilders' performance (second and third sections). The third type of data compares the four housebuilders' performance for the benefits of society and the environment and their financial performance.

4.5.4.2 Analysis

In data analysis, descriptive statistics are broadly adopted, defined as the "numerical procedures or graphical techniques" that summarise and describe the features of a given sample (Fisher and Marshall, 2009, p93). Before using descriptive statistics, the level of measurement of how the data is scored needs to be clarified. Typically, there are three levels of measurement: nominal, ordinal, and continuous. Furthermore, this thesis mainly measures the data with the nominal and ordinal levels. The nominal (or categorical) level of measurement is explained as scores of participants into broad categories. In this research, the answers to the participants' age, sex, occupation, and housing type are all

measured by the nominal level. The ordinal level of measurement is the “scoring of research participants into hierarchically ordered categories” (Fisher and Marshall, 2009, p94). The performance assessment with the hierarchy belongs to the ordinal level of measurement. Once the measurement level of data is confirmed, the analysis is carried out with specific descriptive statistics, like mean, mode, median, and frequency.

Firstly, frequency statistics provide information about the respondents’ profiles. Then, the respondents’ assessment of housebuilders’ performance would be described by the mean and frequency statistics, which would test the research hypotheses. Based on the mean and frequency result, a better understanding of the central tendency of the assessment would be built, and an accurate score to help define the performance level would be obtained. Moreover, the performance score would present a more accurate comparison when the builders receive the same level of assessment. The frequency analysis is conducted for some data so that the accurate proportion of each level of assessment would be obtained, which would help build on the data analysis and discussion.

For the secondary data, the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) is primarily used in data analysis and the formula is presented in Figure 20. CAGR is a common conception to examine the average annual growth rate of an investment for a certain period; however, the usage of CAGR has been extended to a broader range. As Chan (2012) highlighted, CAGR is an accounting conception and can analyse the elements of business, like revenue, production, number of customers, etc. CAGR is regarded as one of the most accurate ways to calculate the growth rate and particularly help improve the understanding of profitability performance (Chan, 2012).

$$CAGR = \left[\left(\frac{EV}{BV} \right)^{\frac{1}{n-1}} - 1 \right] \times 100$$

Where:

$EV = \text{Ending Value}$

$BV = \text{Beginning Value}$

$n = \text{Number of Years}$

Figure 20. CAGR Formula (Jones, 2010)

CAGR's common drawbacks in assessing the investment are not concerned in this study, but one challenge is that the original formula of CAGR does not consider the negative values. However, the negative value of the initial year or ending year exists in reality. For this issue, the author adjusted the original formula but kept the adjusted formula equal to the original one in the calculation (Figure 21).

$$\begin{aligned} CAGR &= \left[\left(\frac{EV}{BV} \right)^{\frac{1}{n-1}} - 1 \right] \times 100 \\ &= \left[\left(\frac{EV}{BV} - 1 + 1 \right)^{\frac{1}{n-1}} - 1 \right] \times 100 \\ &= \left[(\% \Delta + 1)^{\frac{1}{n-1}} - 1 \right] \times 100 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} CAGR_{adj} &= \left[(\% \Delta_{adj} + 1)^{\frac{1}{n-1}} - 1 \right] \times 100 \\ &= \left[\left(\frac{EV - BV + ABS(BV)}{ABS(BV)} \right)^{\frac{1}{n-1}} - 1 \right] \times 100 \end{aligned}$$

Where:

$EV = \text{Ending Value}$

$BV = \text{Beginning Value}$

$n = \text{Number of Years}$

Figure 21. Adjusted CAGR Formula (the author)

To assess the private housebuilder's profitability, Archer and Cole (2021) suggested a formula: profit before tax to housing outputs, in which the profit before tax and housing outputs are collected from the annual report. This ratio is regarded as an indication of to what extent housebuilders have transferred their business strategies to a more financialised model (Archer and Cole, 2021).

The ratio of dividend pay-out and profitability per home completed is calculated in analysing the profitability. Considering the different business scales of the four cases, comparing the four housebuilders' financial performance only with the dividend payment would not be critical. Meanwhile, the dividend pay-out ratio could explain the dividend policy and indicate the retained funds for reproduction Sholichah (Sholichah et al., 2021).

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Dividend Payout Ratio} &= \frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Dividends Paid}} \\
 &= 1 - \text{Retention Ratio} \\
 &= 1 - \frac{(\text{EPS} - \text{DPS})}{\text{EPS}} \\
 &= \frac{\text{DPS}}{\text{EPS}}
 \end{aligned}$$

Where:

$\text{EPS} = \text{Earnings per Share}$

$\text{DPS} = \text{Dividends per Share}$

Figure 22. Dividend Pay-out Formula (Baker, 2009)

4.6 Research Validity and Reliability

A suitable research methodology is supposed to have validity and reliability. Validity is the level that the research method can accurately measure what it is intended to measure. Furthermore, reliability is explained as the extent of the measurement, process, approaches generating the same results via the repeated trials (Yin, 2018). It is necessary and essential to consider the validity and reliability of the data, as it demonstrates the rigour of the research process and the trustworthiness of the research findings (Heale and Twycross, 2015). Therefore, the validity and reliability of the findings are tested before the data analysis.

About the validity, the validity of the contents is examined. Content validity is the extent to which the measurement (questions in the questionnaire) provides adequate coverage on all facets of a given construct (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). According to the judgment of “adequate coverage” in the conception, it believes the thesis is qualified. The questions are designed based on the intensive literature review, which means each question has an academic trace. Meanwhile, the author also discusses the questions' appropriateness, effectiveness, and clarity with the research supervisor, peers, and several target respondents (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). For example, the target respondents explain their understanding of the questions and put forward their confusion. For each question, the author also asks for an evaluation of how essential each question is and only the questions with over 70% rating of “essential” are finally kept (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016, Almanasreh, Moles and Chen, 2019). Based on these judgments, the validity of the questionnaire is confirmed.

In terms of reliability, Cronbach's alpha is used in this study. According to Peterson (1994), the alpha values should reach at least 0.7 to consider the scales as reliable. The finding chapter's alpha values are higher than the required level; therefore, the reliability is confirmed.

4.7 Methodological Limitation

Some methodological limitations are identified in this chapter that might influence the research process and results. The corresponding mitigations are also raised to reduce the negative impacts of these limitations. First, a concern about the sample size (response rate) is highlighted as the failure in sample size might not draw the quality conclusion for each case. This is also one typical drawback of the questionnaire approach. In addition to the mitigations mentioned above, the author takes more approaches and longer times than expected to distribute and collect the questionnaire wider. Secondly, the questionnaire approach might cause some bias about the terms in questions based on the individual's inconsistent understanding and different personal backgrounds, such as the term "benefits of society". Moreover, the author would be less involved in the data collection stage via a questionnaire, especially the online questionnaire, which might worsen this drawback. About this negative side, the mitigation is to clarify the specific metrics that help assess the overall performance for the benefits of society and the environment in the second section. The author also includes a clear explanation of how to measure them and the relevant metrics about other terms that possibly cause bias, like the environmental impacts and financial performance.

4.8 Ethical Consideration

In addition to the methodological limitation, some ethical considerations are also highlighted for this study. The relevant solutions are raised for each ethical consideration to avoid the unethical issue. For the study with the primary data, the protection for the participants is one of the most typical elements to raise ethical issues (Gajjar, 2013). For example, protecting the participants from physical harm, respecting the participants' will and consent, protecting participants' privacy, etc. This thesis collects the primary data via offline and online questionnaires. A detailed participant consent form is attached ahead of the questionnaire. Therefore, the data would be collected and used only when the participants give their full consent. With the online data collection approach, the author uses the trusted distribution channel (survey hero) to ensure that the whole data collection process is virus-free and advertisement-free. The authors only conducted the offline data collection approach before 2020, when the Covid-19 pandemic did not start in the UK. Furthermore, during the Covid-19 pandemic period, no data was collected offline to avoid any health concerns. Then to protect the participant's privacy, the response to the questionnaire is anonymous. Besides, all the collected data is stored on the Survey Hero website with a password. Also, the downloaded data is saved in the OneDrive account under the protection of the University of the West of Scotland. All the files are saved in the draw with a locker for the offline data.

4.9 Summary

This chapter explains the methodological process. The philosophy of positivism firstly presents the rationale for the research approach and strategy decisions. This research is conducted in a deductive approach. Towards the research

objective to assess the private housebuilders' performance for the benefits of society and the environment and the financial performance, the case study is considered as the suitable strategy as the data collection and analysis in the four selected cases is expected to provide an in-depth investigation with considering the specific contexts in each case. The research method is quantitative, based on data collection and analysis decisions. As this chapter introduced, 100 pieces of the questionnaire are distributed to the customers (inhabitants) of Barratt Developments, Persimmon, Bellway and Miller Homes, respectively. There is an explanation about how to collect the data via the quantitative method, questionnaire approach and specific elements in the questionnaire, and all these decisions are made based on serving the research objectives and the intensive literature review. Except for the primary data, this research includes secondary data in industry examination (chapter 3) and research discussion (chapter 6), which helps reinforce the primary data discussion and creditable conclusions. In the data analysis part, the analytical tool of SPSS is used, by which the validity and reliability, descriptive statistics (frequency and mean) are all examined. Finally, the methodological limitations and ethical considerations are highlighted. With realising these possible issues, the author raises the corresponding mitigations to avoid them or reduce their negative impacts on the research process.

CHAPTER 5, RESEARCH FINDINGS

5.1. Introduction

In this chapter, the research findings are presented. For the primary data collection, the questionnaires were designed to assess the four private housebuilders of Barratt Developments, Persimmon, Bellway and Miller Homes' performance for the benefits of society and the environment and their financial performance. Considering the critical role of the inhabitant in the social benefit, the respondents of questionnaires are the customer (inhabitants) of the target housebuilders. One hundred questionnaires about the assessment of the housebuilders' performance were sent out to each group of respondents, and four hundred questionnaires in total were distributed.

The secondary data is collected from trusted and published sources. According to the research questions, the secondary data demonstrates the builders' social, environmental and financial performance. The secondary data is mainly from the builders' annual report about the four cases. Furthermore, about the general performance within the UK housebuilding industrial range, the secondary data is mainly collected from the Office for National Statistics, reports of the UK government, reports of the National House Building Council, which provides the statistics with high credibility and consistency.

5.2. Demographic Information of the Primary Samples

For each private housebuilder, the valid sample is listed in Table 3. Moreover, the demographic information in the questionnaire includes age, sex, occupation and the type of dwelling, which is presented in the table below. Descriptive statistics

were utilised to calculate frequencies and percentages of the profile of respondents in the sample.

Housebuilders	Questionnaires	Valid responses and rate
Barratt Development	100	84 (84%)
Persimmon	100	90 (90%)
Bellway	100	84 (84%)
Miller Homes	100	88 (88%)

Table 3. Valid Samples in Data Collection

Although the four housebuilders are different in business scale, their inhabitants have a similar profile. In term of age, most of the inhabitants are aged from 35 to 64, and only a tiny part of inhabitants is aged between 25 to 34 or 65 and above. It finds that most inhabitants are employed or self-employed, which means they have a relatively steady income to support their housing purchase and mortgage. Furthermore, only a tiny part of the samples is in the statute of unemployment and retirement. In terms of the type of dwelling, most of the respondents live in semi-detached houses. As for the detached property, the portion of inhabitants of Barratt Developments is the highest in the four housebuilders, while persimmon has a minor portion of inhabitants living in this type of property.

Characteristics	Barratt Developments		Persimmon		Bellway		Miller Homes	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Age								
Under 24	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
25-34	8	9.5%	16	17.8%	4	4.8%	2	2.3%
35-44	22	26.2%	28	31.1%	26	31.0%	24	27.3%
45-54	24	28.6%	30	33.3%	28	33.3%	34	38.6%
55-64	24	28.6%	12	13.3%	22	26.2%	22	25%

Over 65	6	7.1%	4	4.4%	4	4.8%	6	6.8%
Sex								
Male	46	54.8%	44	46.7%	44	48.9%	44	50.0%
Female	38	45.2%	46	53.3%	40	51.1%	44	50.0%
Occupation								
Student	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
Self-employed	30	35.7%	26	28.9%	22	26.2%	30	34.1%
Employed	48	57.1%	58	64.4%	56	66.7%	50	56.8%
Unemployed	0	0.0%	2	2.2%	2	2.4%	2	2.3%
Retirement	6	7.1%	4	4.4%	4	4.8%	6	6.8%
Other	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
Your dwelling								
Detached house	24	28.6%	10	11.1%	22	26.2%	26	29.5%
Semi-detached house	34	40.5%	30	33.2%	26	31.0%	38	43.2%
Terraced house	14	16.7%	30	33.3%	24	28.6%	24	27.3%
Flat	12	14.3%	20	22.2%	12	14.3%	0	0.0%
Other	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%

Table 4. Demographic Profile of Respondents

5.3. Reliability Test

The reliability test is focused on the variables of performance for the benefits of society and the environment, which are the assessment of the four private housebuilders' performance in the housing supply, housing affordability, housing quality and environmental impacts. With SPSS, the Cronbach's alpha value of the

four variables is analysed. If Cronbach's alpha value is over 0.7, the internal consistency and scale reliability would be proved. For the performance variables for the benefits of society and the environment in the four housebuilding companies, Cronbach's alpha values are presented in Table 5. Furthermore, it finds that all the Cronbach's alpha values are higher than 0.7, which confirms the reliability of data collection in this study.

Sample group	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Barratt Development	0.80	4
Persimmon	0.798	4
Bellway	0.80	4
Miller Homes	0.848	4

Table 5. Reliability Statistics

5.4. Assessment of the Private Housebuilders'

Performance

With the SPSS, the five scales of performance assessment for serving social and environmental benefits, very satisfactory, satisfactory, moderate, dissatisfactory, very dissatisfactory, are assigned with 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, respectively. Furthermore, about the performance in creating business profit, the measurements are very high, high, moderate, low and very low, which are also assigned with the number from 5 to 1 respectively. With the numerical data, the mean is calculated, then the private housebuilders' performance within the social, environmental and finance could be graded, which can help compare the performance of the four builders. Considering the mean result might not be an integer; therefore, the numerical range for each assessment is raised in Table 6. As a result, the mean of inhabitants' answers would help define the builders' performance with the specific level.

Performance assessment	Numerical interval
Very satisfactory (or very high)	$4.5 \leq \text{result} \leq 5$
Satisfactory (or high)	$3.5 \leq \text{result} < 4.5$
Moderate	$2.5 \leq \text{result} < 3.5$
Dissatisfactory (or low)	$1.5 \leq \text{result} < 2.5$
Very dissatisfactory (or very low)	$1 \leq \text{result} < 1.5$

Table 6. The Numerical Result of Performance Assessment

In this scale, the options of very satisfactory and satisfactory performance to help with the particular housing aspects indicate that respondents believe housebuilders have taken effective practices and positively impacted particular housing or environmental issues. On the opposite, the options of dissatisfactory and very dissatisfactory imply two possibilities that the housebuilders have made few or no efforts in helping with the particular housing aspects, or the housebuilders have made efforts but with less valuable outcomes.

5.4.1 Performance for the Benefits of Society

In the performance assessment framework, the social performance is assessed by how well the private housebuilders have meet inhabitants' needs or helped with their concerns. From 2010 to 2020, three housing issues are identified as mostly cared for by inhabitants in the UK: housing supply, housing affordability, housing quality. Therefore, the data of housebuilders' efforts in the three aspects are collected.

5.4.1.1 Performance in Meeting Supply Demands

5.4.1.1.1 Primary Findings

The primary data indicates Bellway has the most satisfactory assessment of the four housebuilders' performance in housing supply. With a mean of 3.6, Bellway's performance in raising housing supply is assessed as satisfactory from 2010 to 2020. The other three builders' score is lower, and their performance is moderate. Although in the same assessment category, Barratt Developments' assessment is higher than Persimmon and Miller Homes'. As one of the largest housebuilders in the UK, Persimmon's supply is assessed with the lowest score, which will be further discussed in the next chapter.

	Barratt Developments	Persimmon	Bellway	Miller Homes
Mean	3.40	2.96	3.60	3.16
Result	moderate	moderate	satisfactory	moderate

Table 7. Supply Performance of the Four Housebuilders (the author)

5.4.1.1.2 Secondary Findings

The secondary data of the total home completions by each housebuilder is summarised in Appendix 2, and the overall supplying trend is presented in Figure 23. Also, the four housebuilders' total completion from 2010 to 2020 is calculated, which takes the 11-years performance as a whole and helps compare the average supply performance of each builder.

The secondary result suggests that from a relatively low point of housing supply in 2010, the four housebuilders' housing supplies have been raised in the following decade. Firstly, the number of new dwellings completed supports the statement of Barratt Developments that “the biggest housebuilder in the UK”.

Barratt Developments' annual completion has been the highest of the four housebuilders from 2010 to 2020, contributing 163,106 units of new homes within the 11 years (Appendix 2). Meanwhile, Barratt Developments has been a leading housebuilder with an enormous volume of home completions in the UK housebuilding industry for many years. The annual home supply of Persimmon has been slightly lower than Barratt Developments' but still higher than other builders most of the time, which has delivered 145,349 units of new homes during the same time (Appendix 2). Compared with them, Bellway and Miller Homes have a smaller business scale. The home completed by Bellway was only 4,959 units in 2010, then it was considerably raised over 10,000 units in 2019. Bellway's 11-year (2010 to 2020) home supply is 82,084. Miller Homes is the smallest housebuilder in the four cases, and its total home completion is 26,208 units from 2010 to 2020 (Appendix 2).

Source: Data collected from annual reports of Barratt Developments, Persimmon, Bellway, Miller Homes, 2010 to 2020 (Appendix 2)

Figure 23. The Annual Supply of the Four Housebuilders, 2010 to 2020

Just considering the completed units, Barratt Developments' performance in house supply should be the best, which means the needs of plenty of inhabitants have been met from 2010 to 2020. However, as the above contents highlighted, the annual completions would be varied with different business scales and development. The Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) is used to analyse the housebuilders' average housing supply pace, considering the different business scales. The CAGR calculating the housing supply helps compare the supply performance among the four builders and the average industrial growth. The CAGR highlights the supply from 2010 to 2019, as this result presents an average supply trend since 2010. Most of the housebuilders, including the four cases, have been affected by the Covid-19. Therefore, the CAGR from 2010 to 2020 might not be an appropriate indicator for the general performance since 2010. It finds that Barratt Developments and Persimmon's completion has been averagely increased by 5.1% and 6.0%, respectively. Meanwhile, the smaller housebuilders, Bellway and Miller Homes, have a higher growth rate. The GACR of 10.1% indicates Bellway's total home completion has been boosted more than the other three builders. Furthermore, Miller's home completion has been averagely raised by 6.9% within the same period. Compared to the CAGR of the UK housebuilding industry, Persimmon, Bellway and Miller Homes all have a better performance in increasing the home supply during 2010 to 2019, especially Bellway has the outstanding performance to help with the supply issue. Despite being lower than the industrial level, Barratt Developments' performance is still moderate based on its total housing supply since 2010.

Period	Industria l range	Barratt Developments	Persimmon	Bellway	Miller Homes
2010 to 2019	5.6%	5.1%	6.0%	10.1%	6.9%

2010 to 2020	N/A	1.0%	3.8%	5.1%	3.2%
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Note: CAGR refers to the calculation and statistics in Appendix 2

Table 8. CAGR of the Industrial and the Four Housebuilders' Annual Housing Supply, 2010 to 2019 (the author)

Four Housebuilders' Supply Capability - Land Bank

According to the review on the development of the private housebuilding sector, it finds land is one necessary material for the private housebuilders' annual supply (Payne et al., 2019). Without the appropriate land management, the housebuilders cannot start the construction project and deliver target supply every year despite enterprisers' goodwill to meet the local housing needs. Therefore, when assessing the private housebuilders' performance in raising housing supply, the secondary data regarding the land bank is collected from each housebuilders' annual report, which helps explain the builders' performance via the perspective of the production capability in the following chapter.

In Barratt Developments, the land bank supporting the forward supply dropped from 5.5 years in 2010 to 4.7 years in 2019, close to Barratt Developments' land bank target of 4.5 years (3.5 years owned land and 1-year controlled land (Barratt Developments Plc, 2019). According to Barratt Development, the company aims at a shorter land bank than the average level in the UK housebuilding industry, reflecting its focus on return on capital and a business model of faster build and sell (Barratt Developments Plc, 2020).

Persimmon has a relatively longer land bank than others. Since 2010, Persimmon has made aggressive progress in land acquisition, and its land bank reached a peak point in 2012, which was able to provide 6.9 years' forward home supply (Figure

24). In the last few years, Persimmon has reduced the size of the land bank, but the 2019 land bank would still cover 5.9 years forward supply, which is higher than the other three housebuilders (Figure 24).

With the business development, both the land bank and home outputs of Bellway have been increased, resulting in a shorter time for the forward supply. According to Bellway's annual report data, the land bank's time for the forward supply was around 6.0 to 7.0 in the early 2010s. Then it was reduced to 5.2 in 2014. Until 2019, the land bank would support future development for 3.9 years (Figure 24).

Miller Homes has the smallest amount of land and home supply among the 4 cases, but the time for forwarding home supply based is not the smallest one. Miller Homes reported the land would support forward supply for 5.4 years in 2015, and it was later reduced to 4.1 years in 2019 (Figure 24), which is generally higher than Bellway's.

Source: Data is collected from annual reports of Barratt Developments, Persimmon, Bellway, Miller Homes, 2010 to 2020 (Appendix 3)

Figure 24. Land Bank of the Four Housebuilders (years), 2010 to 2020

5.4.1.2 Performance in Solving Affordability Issue

5.4.1.2.1 Primary Findings

Based on the result about the four housebuilders' performance in raising housing affordability, respondents gave the highest grades on Persimmon. Persimmon's mean of 3.38 demonstrates its performance in raising housing affordability is neither satisfactory nor dissatisfactory for respondents. Compared to Persimmon, the assessment on the other three housebuilders is lower. The mean grades of Barratt Development, Bellway and Miller Homes are 2.43, 2.40 and 2.48, regarded as dissatisfactory.

	Barratt Developments	Persimmon	Bellway	Miller Homes
Mean	2.43	3.38	2.40	2.48
Result	dissatisfactory	moderate	dissatisfactory	dissatisfactory

Table 9. Affordability Performance of the Four Housebuilders (the author)

5.4.1.2.2 Secondary Findings

In addition to inhabitants' responses, the average selling price of the property is another finding helping assess and compare the four housebuilders' performance assessment in raising the housing affordability. The CAGR of the average selling price is also calculated to examine the four builders' price management in terms of the affordability concerns, which is presented in Table 10, considering the different profiles of the four housebuilders.

The biggest housebuilder Barratt Developments has a different pricing history with Persimmon, which has always sold a house at a higher price than the national average level. Especially in 2018, Barratt Developments' average selling price was

almost £60,000 higher than the national price. Compared with the other three housebuilders, Barratt Developments' price is higher than theirs most of the time. In 2012, 2019, and 2020 Barratt Developments' average selling price was below Bellway's.

The average selling price of Bellway has experienced a significant change, which was increased from £163,200 to £293,054 from 2010 to 2020. Except for 2010, Bellway's average selling price has consistently surpassed the industrial level. Considering the impacts of the Global Financial Crisis, the author reviews the average selling during the 2000s and finds Bellway's average selling price had been lower than the national level at that time. Therefore, it is a fundamental change for Bellway in terms of housing price after 2010, rather than a “return” to the price level before the crisis. Bellway's average selling price has been kept higher than Persimmon and Miller Homes most of the time and surpassed Barratt Developments in some years.

In the first two years of the 2010s, Miller Homes' average selling price was lower than the national level, and afterwards, Miller Homes has kept its average selling price higher than the national level. Compared with the other three builders, Miller Homes' average selling price was close to Persimmon's in the early 2010s and surpassed Persimmon's since 2014. Meanwhile, the affordability of Miller Homes' home has always been higher than Barratt Developments and Bellway.

Source: Data collected from the Office for National Statistics (2021), annual reports of Barratt Development, Persimmon, Bellway, Miller Homes, 2010 to 2020 (4)

Figure 25. The Average Selling Price of England and the Four Builders, 2010 to 2020

Period	National	Barratt Developments	Persimmon	Bellway	Miller Homes
2010 to 2019	3.6%	5.2%	2.7%	6.7%	4.5%
2010 to 2020	4.0%	4.9%	3.1%	6.0%	4.5%

Source: CAGR refers to the calculation and statistics in 4

Table 10. CAGR of the Average Selling Price

5.4.1.3 Performance in Meeting Quality Needs

5.4.1.3.1 Primary Findings

In the result about the four housebuilders' performance in housing quality, Barratt Developments and Bellway are assessed as satisfactory with 3.79 and 3.57. According to the data result, Barratt Developments is doing better than other

builders, and over 70% of respondents feel satisfied with the housing quality. Persimmon and Bellway are assessed as neither satisfactory nor dissatisfactory. The mean of Miller Homes is 3.25, while Persimmon is only 2.62, which is the lowest one of the four builders. Comparatively, most of the respondents (78.6%) feel neutral about Miller Homes' efforts in housing quality, while most of the respondents (44.4%) are dissatisfied with Persimmon's, indicating Persimmon's housing quality is at a relatively low position.

	Barratt Development	Persimmon	Bellway	Miller Homes
Mean	3.79	2.62	3.57	3.25
Result	satisfactory	moderate	satisfactory	moderate

Table 11. Mean Analysis of Housing Quality of Four the Housebuilders (the author)

Performance	Barratt Developments	Persimmon	Bellway	Miller Homes
Very satisfactory	19.0%	0.0%	14.3%	9.5%
Satisfactory	54.8%	11.1%	31.0%	11.9%
Moderate	11.9%	42.2%	52.4%	78.6%
dis satisfactory	14.3%	44.4%	2.4%	4.8%
very dis satisfactory	0.0%	2.2%	0.0%	0.0%

Table 12. Frequency Analysis of Housing Quality of Four the Housebuilders (the author)

5.4.1.3.2 Secondary Findings

The questionnaire respondents in this thesis give their assessment in terms of the housing quality. Meanwhile, the secondary data is collected from the customer satisfaction survey about the newly built home, which provides a relatively general assessment of the housing quality in the industrial range. About the four housebuilders, customers' evaluation of the housing quality and the number of reported quality problems are presented in Figure 26 and Figure 27 (Appendix 5). Overall, the national customer satisfaction survey indicates that most customers feel satisfied with the home quality in the UK. However, the number of reported quality problems has been raised. In the survey between 2010 to 2011, the reported quality problems of up to five were accounted for 44%. Then it dropped to 31% during the year between 2019 and 2020. At the same time, 16 or more reported quality problems have been raised from 14% to 25% between 2010 and 2020. This secondary data demonstrates that customers have found more quality problems in newly built homes than before. Although people are satisfied with the home quality, it finds that the proportion of very satisfaction has decreased while the proportion of fair satisfaction has increased.

Source: data is collected from the HNBC national customer satisfaction, 2010 to 2021 (Appendix 5)

Figure 26. National Customer Satisfaction Survey- Home Quality Satisfaction, 2009/10 to 2019/20

Source: data is collected from the HNBC national customer satisfaction, 2010 to 2021

Figure 27. National Customer Satisfaction Survey- Report Quality Problems, 2009/10 to 2019/20

Some secondary data directly related to the four cases are collected to assess the four builders' quality performance. Firstly, focusing on the property quality, the internal efforts of the four housebuilders for housing quality, like the strategy and target, practices and feedback for housing quality, are summarised. Secondly, one indicator that proves the quality of site managers and further affects the housing quality is collected from the Pride in the Job award of the National House Building Council (NHBC).

Internal Efforts toward Housing Quality

The four housebuilders all placed the housing quality at a prior and strategic position in the business. For example, the Board of Barratt Developments requires “regular updates on customer satisfaction and quality scores and details of what the business is doing to continue to improve company position” (Barratt Developments Plc, 2019, p27). Persimmon sets “improving the quality of homes we build” as one of the top priorities, purposes and strategies. Similarly, Miller Homes also takes high quality as the first objective in its business strategy. Bellway includes homes' high standard of quality in its business model. According to these claims, the four builders all have a high awareness of quality. Nevertheless, only Barratt Developments and Bellway's efforts in raising housing quality since 2010 are confirmed by the research findings as satisfactory. Meanwhile, The quality objective of Persimmon seems to be not well realised based on the lowest grades on its efforts in housing quality.

Firstly, the satisfactory result confirms Barratt Developments and Bellway have met inhabitants' needs on housing quality and demonstrates the effectiveness of the two builders' efforts on quality. Barratt Developments develops its design initiative, 'Great Places', which aligns with the government metrics, Building for Life, to assess the design quality of homes. Furthermore, regular project monitoring and evaluations have been conducted through the construction process (Barratt Developments Plc, 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018b, 2019). To ensure the specific plans would be well implemented, Barratt Developments also includes the “quality and service improvement” as one of the performance targets related to the annual bonus of directors (Barratt Developments Plc, 2017, 2018b, 2019). Furthermore, in 2019, this target requires divisions to achieve the customer recommendation score of 90% or above, which is almost totally completed in Barratt (Barratt Developments Plc, 2019). To meet customers' quality standard

needs, Barratt Developments also builds effective local communication via online channels and offline sales teams (Barratt Developments Plc, 2015, 2020).

The research finding of Barratt Developments and its relevant practices supports scholars' conclusions regarding the positive impacts of innovation and project management on housing quality. Specifically, innovation in home design and construction technologies would improve the housing quality, as it would deal with the new coming quality issues. Besides, strict evaluation and monitoring of a construction project are necessary to ensure property quality (Jha and Iyer, 2006, Callistus and Clinton, 2018).

The satisfactory assessment on Bellway demonstrates the effectiveness of the two approaches that the builder particularly highlighted to raise housing quality: skilled labours and a strong relationship with suppliers and manufacturers. The two approaches are regarded as the essential elements to ensure the construction quality by some scholars (Arditi and Gunaydin, 1997, Doshi, 2019). Firstly, skilled labours, including sub-contractors, are necessary for the construction process, as they would directly affect the quality and efficiency of building works (Arditi and Gunaydin, 1997). Bellway (Bellway p.l.c., 2019, p. 39) highlights the importance of its people as “the quality of our new homes and the high levels of customer service we deliver is dependent on the people who work for us”. Secondly, a good relationship with suppliers and manufacturers would ensure the builder's availability and quality of building materials (Doshi, 2019), which is also confirmed by Bellway (Bellway p.l.c., 2018).

In Miller Homes, few specific practices on raising house quality are published. Although being assessed as moderate, the mean of Miller Homes' quality performance is much higher than Persimmon and close to the level of satisfaction.

This is consistent with the national customer satisfaction result and Construction Quality Review (CQR) score of Miller Homes. In terms of national customer satisfaction, Miller Homes has made significant progress from its lowest rating of 2 stars in the early 2010s to 5 or 4 stars in recent years (Home Builders Federation, 2012). This is a shred of evidence for Miller Homes' efforts on raising home quality. Furthermore, in NHBC's annual assessment of construction quality, "Construction Quality Reviews" (CQR), Miller Homes is scored 3.96 in 2019, which is regarded as an upper-quartile level in the housebuilding industry (Miller Homes, 2019).

According to Persimmon, the builder has also taken some actions to raise the housing quality. Persimmon highlights the investments to install digital technologies in the building and inspection process (Persimmon Plc, 2012, p. 14). According to Jha and Iyer (2006) and Callistus and Clinton (2018), digital innovation is expected to raise the housing quality; therefore, the housing quality of Persimmon should be raised. However, the research finding of Persimmon's lowest grade on quality performance challenges Jha and Lyer and Callistus and Clinton's conclusion to some extent. Multiple factors, like lacking practical training on digital technologies poor adaptability to the construction standards, might result in the ineffective implementation of the digital technologies in the construction project (Gaith, Khalim and Ismail, 2012, Emmanuel, Omoregie and Koloko, 2018). With the available files, the thesis cannot confirm the reason for the low effectiveness of digital innovation in Persimmon, but the implementation of the digital innovation should be examined based on the previous literature.

Quality of the Site Managers

According to the Pride in Job Award, Barratt Developments has acquired 1010 Pride in Job Awards and 264 Seal of Excellence, ranking as the highest in the four cases of this research and the whole UK housebuilding industry until 2020 (brand-

new homes, 2021). Bellway has an outstanding performance in the Pride in Job Award with a smaller business scale, which acquired 403 Pride in Job Awards during the same period (2010 to 2020), just behind Barratt Developments and Taylor Wimpey. Especially in the last few years, the number of Pride in Job Award in Bellway has been dramatically increased. Despite being less than Barratt Developments and Bellway, Miller Homes still has a moderate performance with 186 awards from 2010 to 2020 (brand-new homes, 2021). Persimmon has less satisfactory performance than the other three builders, and its number of awards has been dramatically decreased during this period. Until 2020, Persimmon has only acquired 182 Pride in Job Awards (brand-new homes, 2021), which is even lower than Miller Homes, which has a much smaller business scale.

5.4.2 Performance for the Benefits of the Environment

5.4.2.1 Primary Findings

About the environmental performance of the four housebuilders, Barratt is doing better than the other three builders with a mean of 3.52 and over 61% satisfaction. Persimmon, Bellway and Miller Homes are assessed as neither satisfactory nor dissatisfactory based on the scale. Nevertheless, the mean indicates Bellway has the worst performance with only 2.52 grades in terms of its environmental impacts. Most of the respondents feel neutral about Persimmon and Miller Homes' environmental performance, while Persimmon has a higher proportion of satisfactory results (24.4%) and Miller Homes has a proportion of satisfactory results (11.9%).

	Barratt Developments	Persimmon	Bellway	Miller Homes
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Mean	3.52	3.18	2.52	2.93
Result	satisfactory	moderate	moderate	moderate

Table 13. Environment Impact of Four the Housebuilders (the author)

Performance	Barratt Developments	Persimmon	Bellway	Miller Homes
Very satisfactory	4.8%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Satisfactory	57.1%	24.4%	2.4%	11.9%
Moderate	26.2%	68.9%	52.4%	73.8%
dis satisfactory	9.5%	6.7%	52.4%	19.0%
very dis satisfactory	2.4%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%

Table 14. Frequency Analysis: Four Housebuilders' Performance for Environmental Benefits (the author)

5.4.2.2 Secondary Findings

Based on the hot environmental topics widely cared about by the government, organisations and the public in the UK housebuilding market, the performance in reducing GHG (Green House Gas) emission and waste generation is focused on assessing the environmental performance. The primary research findings indicate the environmental performance of Barratt Developments as satisfactory and Persimmon, Bellway and Miller Homes as moderate. Regarding this assessment, the housebuilders' performance in the specific GHG reduction and waste management is focused on here.

Comparatively, the homeowners assess their builder's environmental performance usually based on their daily life experience regarding the “green” property and community. However, about the business operation, the published secondary data of the specific environmental indicator provides another evidence to assess the builders' environment performance. The carbon intensity could represent each builders' performance to reduce the GHG emission, which accounts for the annual supply. The intense waste ratio and recycled waste are collected from the company's annual report about waste management.

5.4.2.2.1 Performance in GHG Reduction

The published statistics of carbon intensity are not always measured with the same metrics, but Barratt Developments' progress would be confirmed after converting to the same metrics. Barratt Developments issued the carbon intensity legal completed unit in 2010 and 2011, around 1.8 tonnes. Furthermore, from 2013 to 2018, the carbon intensity per 1,000 sq. ft (equal to 92.9 sq. m.) proves Barratt Developments' efforts, which decreased from 2.77 tonnes to 1.87 tonnes (Bellway p.l.c., 2013, 2018). Then in 2019 and 2020, the carbon intensity per 100 sq. m. is 1.92 and 1.82 tonnes, respectively (Bellway p.l.c., 2020), which is about 2.00 tonnes per 1,000 sq. ft.

Persimmon's carbon intensity per legal completed unit has been published since 2014, which has been well maintained from 2.06 to 2.33 tonnes till 2019 (Persimmon Plc, 2020).

In Miller Homes, GHG emission and waste data in some years are missing. The remaining data indicates that Miller Homes' carbon intensity per 100 sq. m. home

built has been kept at the level of around 2.0 tonnes, which is acceptable when compared to the other three builders.

The carbon intensity data of Bellway has been published only from 2014. The carbon intensity per legally completed unit has increased from 1.9 tonnes to 2.8 tonnes between 2014 to 2020, which challenges Bellway's efforts to reduce GHG emissions. Bellway's carbon intensity should be the highest compared to the other three builders.

Year	Barratt Developments	Persimmon	Bellway	Miller Homes
2010	1.8 per unit	N/A	N/A	N/A
2011	1.79 per unit	N/A	N/A	N/A
2012	N/A	1.37 per unit	N/A	N/A
2013	2.77 per 1,000 sq. ft	1.38 per unit	N/A	N/A
2014	2.78 per 1,000 sq. ft	2.06 per unit	1.9 per unit	2 per 100 sq. m
2015	2.36 per 1,000 sq. ft	2.17 per unit	1.9 per unit	1.9 per 100 sq. m
2016	2.23 per 1,000 sq. ft	2.15 per unit	2.6 per unit	1.9 per 100 sq. m
2017	2.17 per 1,000 sq. ft	2.09 per unit	2.6 per unit	2 per 100 sq. m
2018	1.87 per 1,000 sq. ft	2.33 per unit	2.5 per unit	
2019	1.75 per 100 sq. m	2.14 per unit	2.4 per unit	1.95 per 100 sq. m
2020	1.92 per 100 sq. m	2.16 per unit	2.8 per unit	2.03 per 100 sq. m

Source: Data is collected from annual reports of Barratt Developments,

Persimmon, Bellway, Miller Homes, 2010 to 2020

Table 15. Four Housebuilders' GHG Emission Intensity, 2010 to 2020

5.4.2.2.2 Performance in Waste Generation

Since 2010, Barratt Developments has maintained a good record on construction waste diverted from landfills, ranging from 91% to 97%. The waste intensity per legally completed unit was around 6.5 tonnes during the first five years of the 2010s. Then from 2015, Barratt Developments has measured the waste intensity per 100 sq. m. build. In general, the waste intensity of Barratt Developments has been reduced except for the increased ratio in 2020, which was resulted from the Covid-19 and construction delay.

Persimmon and Miller Homes' result is lower than Barratt Developments, but their grades are much higher than Bellway's. According to Persimmon, the construction waste diverted from landfills has improved from only 82% in 2010 to 96% in 2020. Persimmon has a slightly higher than Barratt Developments but acceptable record about the waste intensity per legal completed unit. Except for 2020 affected by the Covid-19, the waste intensity of Persimmon has been kept below 7.5 tonnes. Moreover, in Miller Homes, the intense waste ratio per 100 square meters of home built was at a higher level of 9.2 tonnes in 2014, then it dropped to 7.1 tonnes in 2020, which confirms Miller Homes' efforts to reduce waste in recent years. Comparatively, Bellway has a much lower performance in waste management. Although Bellway has improved its skill in recycling wastes, its waste intensity is higher than the other three. The intense waste ratio per completed unit in Bellway has been raised from 8.6 to 11.1 tonnes between 2016 to 2020, which is higher than the other three builders.

Year	Barratt Development		Persimmon		Bellway		Miller Homes	
	Waste intensity	Recycled waste	Waste intensity	Recycled waste	Waste intensity	Recycled waste	Waste intensity	Recycled waste
2010	6.45 per unit	91%	6.9 per unit	82%				
2011	6.36 per unit	95%	6.6 per unit	84%				
2012	6.47 per unit	96%	6.4 per unit	88%				
2013	6.25 per unit	94%	5.7 per unit	90%				
2014	6.39 per unit	95%	6.4 per unit	90%		89.30%	9.2 per unit	
2015	7.09 per 100 sq. m (6.63 per unit)	95%	6.3 per unit	92%		92.90%	9.6 per unit	
2016	7.11 per 100 sq. m	95%	6.6 per unit	93%	8.64 per unit	95.90%	8.2 per unit	94%
2017	6.18 per 100 sq. m	95%	7.25 per unit	92%	9.25 per unit	97.80%	9.4 per unit	97%
2018	6.06 per 100 sq. m	97%	6.73 per unit	96%	9.31 per unit	98.10%		
2019	6.53 per 100 sq. m	97%	7.44 per unit	97%	10.97 per unit	98.40%	7.09 per unit	

2020	7.7 per 100 sq. m	96%	8.4 per unit		11.18 per unit	99.10%	7.12 per unit	95.60%
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Source: Data is collected from annual reports of Barratt Developments, Persimmon, Bellway, Miller Homes, 2010 to 2020

Table 16. Four Housebuilders' Waste Generation Intensity, 2010 to 2020

5.4.3 Performance for the Benefits of Society and the Environment

Based on the assessment of the four housebuilders' performance within the social and environmental dimensions, the respondent is asked to give an overall assessment of the housebuilders' performance for the benefits of society and the environment. According to the mean analysis, the four housebuilders' performance for the benefits of society and the environment is defined at a moderate level. Nevertheless, the specific grades of each housebuilders' performance assessment suggest Barratt Development has best performed while Persimmon has worst performed for the benefits of society and environment in the UK from 2010.

The builders are primarily assessed as a moderate performance by inhabitants from the frequency analysis. Barratt Developments' satisfactory or above result is much higher than the other three builders Comparing the proportion of inhabitants' responses. Meanwhile, Barratt Developments receives the fewest dissatisfactory assessment. The overall performance assessment of Persimmon is dragged by the highest proportion of dissatisfactory assessment with 26.7% among the four cases. Bellway and Miller Homes are at the middle position between Barratt Development and Persimmon based on the mean result.

Nevertheless, it notices Bellway's ratio of satisfactory is higher than Persimmon's and only slightly lower than Barratt Developments', while Miller Homes receives the most response of neither satisfactory nor dissatisfactory in the four cases.

Based on the above secondary findings, inhabitants' overall assessment of the four builders' performance for the benefits of society and the environment is agreed upon. Regarding the builders' performance in meeting the housing demands raising housing affordability and quality, the secondary finding is generally in line with the primary result and provides more detailed and credible evidence for performance assessment. As for the performance for the environmental benefits, the primary and secondary findings take different perspectives but still conclude the best performance of Barratt Developments and the poorest performance of Bellway. Therefore, based on the primary and secondary findings, the four housebuilders' performance for the benefits of the society and environment from 2010 to 2020 is concluded as moderate.

	Barratt Development	Persimmon	Bellway	Miller Homes
Mean	3.24	2.84	3.07	3.00
Result	moderate	moderate	moderate	moderate

Table 17. Four Housebuilders' Performance for the Benefits of Society and the Environment, 2010 to 2020 (the author)

Figure 28. Frequency Analysis: Performance Assessment for the Benefits of Society and the Environment

The mean of the four housebuilders' performance scores in each metric is calculated in the overall performance assessment. It finds that the four housebuilders' performance in raising housing affordability is the poorest compared to other performance assessments. Although the four aspects are all identified with high importance in the private housebuilding sector from 2010, the housing affordability issue is particularly worrying based on inhabitants' less satisfaction about the builders' performance.

Performance metric	Mean result
Performance for meeting housing demands	3.3
Performance for raising housing affordability	2.7
Performance for raising housing quality	3.3
Performance for environments benefits	3.0

Table 18. Mean result of Four Housebuilders' Performance

5.4.4 Performance in Creating Business Profit Financial

Performance of the Four Housebuilders

5.4.4.1 Primary Findings

The inhabitants might not review the financial statement of their housebuilder in detail, but their assessment of the builders' financial performance is still collected in this study. So that inhabitants' evaluation of the builders' profitability and the published financial performance can be compared, which also help identify the gaps between the public's typical awareness and the builders' real performance.

About the housebuilders' performance in generating company profit, most of the respondents for the four housebuilders all expressed their housebuilders have realised high to very high performance in making company profits. None of the respondents believed the four housebuilders had a deficient financial performance. Comparatively, the mean result tells the respondent believes Barratt Development, Persimmon and Bellway have a better financial performance than Miller Homes from 2010 to 2020.

	Barratt Development	Persimmon	Bellway	Miller Homes
Mean	4.52	4.51	4.55	4.20
Result	very high	very high	very high	high

Table 19. Four Housebuilders' Financial Performance, 2010 to 2020

5.4.4.2 Secondary Findings

In assessing the four housebuilders' financial performance since 2010, the major financial indicators of revenue, profits before tax, and dividend payment are

focused on (Willard, 2012, Žak, 2015). Most of the financial data could be collected from the published financial statement of each builder, which collaborates with the primary findings to explain the builders' finance performance in detail. Based on the secondary data, the CAGR of the key financial indicators is calculated to help further evaluate builders' profitability. According to Archer and Cole (2021), the ratio of profit before tax to housing output is taken as one indicator for the builders' profitability. The results between 2010 and 2019 would be analysed to assess the general performance since 2010, while the performance in 2020 would be analysed separately, considering the impacts of Covid-19 in 2020. In the following contents, the secondary findings of the four housebuilders are presented and analysed. When analysing the dividend policy, the pay-out ratio is calculated based on the published statistics of earning per share and dividend per share in the financial statements (Appendix 6), and Figure 29 presents the ratio.

Source: calculation of dividend pay-out ratio is based on the secondary data of earnings per share and dividend per share and presented in Appendix 8.

Figure 29. Dividend Pay-out Ratio of the Four Housebuilders, 2010 to 2020.

5.4.4.2.1 Barratt

Affected by the Global Financial Crisis, Barratt Developments' revenue was low at £2,035 million in 2010. Then it was raised to over £4,700 million in 2019. Responding to the crisis, Barratt Developments set the top priority as optimising margin via “driving efficiency and optimising selling price growth” (Barratt Developments Plc, 2020, p. 4,7). As the group chief executive officer by then, Mark Clare, highlighted, “We have focused on securing the maximum price for every sale” and “accept lower sales volume to preserve value” (Barratt Developments Plc, 2010, p. 6). Correspondently, Barratt Developments reduced construction volumes and focused on the sites with a significant margin in the early 2010s.

The profit before tax was a loss of £162.9 million in 2010 (Barratt Developments Plc, 2010), then it has grown to £909.8 million in 2019 (Barratt Developments Plc, 2019). With Excel, the CAGR of profit before tax from 2010 to 2019 indicates that significant progress has been made in the financial performance of Barratt. Then because of the Covid-19 pandemic, the group revenue and profit before tax are dropped but still kept as a profitable status.

Year	Revenue	Profit Before Tax
2010 to 2019	9.9%	23.3%
2010 to 2020	5.3%	14.9%

Source: CAGR refers to the calculation and statistics in Appendix 6

Table 20. CGRA of Barratt Developments' Revenue and Profit before Tax, 2010 to 2019 and 2020.

Another evidence of Barratt Developments' financial performance is the dividend payments. Barratt Developments pays dividends twice every financial year and special dividends sometimes based on the market condition and financial performance. In Barratt Developments, the dividend cover is highlighted,

calculated as “the ratio of the group's profit or loss for the period attributable to the company’s owners to the total ordinary dividend” (Barratt Developments Plc, 2020, p. 7). The dividend cover ratio would tell Barratt Developments' plan on income distribution.

Affected by the Global Financial Crisis, Barratt Developments suspended dividend payments since June 2008 based on its cash conservation policy (Barratt Developments Plc, 2010). From 2013, Barratt Developments proposed the payment of the dividends again due to the growing profitability, finally paid in November 2014. Meanwhile, Barratt Developments updated a “progressive dividend policy” with the aim of “achieving a target dividend cover of around three times for the financial year 2016” (Barratt Developments Plc, 2013, p.7), which means Barratt Developments would spend 1/3 of the total comprehensive income recognised for the year on the dividend. Since then, the dividend payment of Barratt Developments has been increased till 2020. The dividend cover ratio was raised to 2.5 times in 2017 (Barratt Developments Plc, 2017, p. 6), and the updated cover ratio further indicates Barratt Developments' high emphasis on financial return to its shareholders. Besides, Barratt Developments paid special dividends in several years, increasing the proportion of the spending on the dividends other than the future production. In 2020, the payment of the dividends was decreased, and the Board of Barratt Developments decided to cancel the dividend payment for the financial year 2020 because of the uncertainties caused by the Covid-19. However, the overall dividend payment history still confirms the good financial performance of Barratt Developments, which is in line with the primary findings that its financial performance is assessed as high.

5.4.4.2.2 Persimmon

Persimmon's revenue was dropped about 50% to £1569.5 million in 2010 due to

the Global Financial Crisis. Similarly, Persimmon took the conventional strategy as Barratt Developments to maximise the profit. Persimmon's revenue was increased to £3649.4 million in 2019. As for the profit before tax, Persimmon only incurred a loss in 2008 when the crisis happened in the UK. Then Persimmon recovered from the crisis quicker and made profits again in 2009. Between 2010 to 2019, the CGRA of Persimmon's revenue and profit before tax between 2010 to 2019 is 9.8% and 23.8%, respectively. The fast growth of the revenue and profit before tax indicates Persimmon's outstanding performance in finance.

Year	Revenue	Profit Before Tax
2010 to 2019	9.8%	23.8%
2010 to 2020	7.8%	18.8%

Source: CAGR refers to the calculation and statistics in Appendix 6

Table 21. CGRA of Persimmon's Revenue and Profit before Tax, 2010 to 2019 and 2020.

In 2010, Persimmon realised an income recognised for the year and paid the dividend of £9 million in total and 3 pence per share. Since then, the dividend payment has been significantly raised, reaching the peak at £747.8 million and 235 pence per share in 2019 (Persimmon Plc, 2010, 2019). Because of the Covid-19 pandemic, Persimmon cancelled the prospective dividend payment, postponed the final dividend payment for the financial year 2019, and decreased the dividend payment for the financial year of 2020 (Persimmon Plc, 2020). The rapid growth of dividend payment and pence per share also support the research findings that Persimmon has made a very high financial performance so that this housebuilder has been able to give a great return to its shareholders.

5.4.4.2.3 Bellway

Before the Global Financial Crisis, Bellway's revenue was around £1,100 to £1,400 million. From a gloomy point of £768 million in 2010, the revenue of Bellway has been increased to £3,213 million in 2019, which suggests Bellway's spectacular growth in sales. Along with the revenue growth, the profit before tax also went up from £44 million in 2010 to £663 million in 2019. The 2019 profit before tax was almost three times higher than the booming period (2006) before the crisis. Besides, the CGRA of profit before tax from 2010 to 2019 further confirms a robust growing probability trend in Bellway.

Year	Revenue	Profit Before Tax
2010 to 2019	17.2%	35.0%
2010 to 2020	11.2%	18.0%

Source: CAGR refers to the calculation and statistics in Appendix 6

Table 22. CGRA of Bellway's revenue and profit before tax, 2010 to 2019 and 2020.

The dividend is paid in Bellway twice for every financial year: the interim dividend (paid within the financial year.) and the final dividend (paid in the next financial year). Bellway has an unbroken record of dividend payments from 2010 to 2020 (Bellway p.l.c., 2020). In 2010, the dividend payment was only 11.2 million with a cover ratio of 3 times. Since then, dividend payments have increased every year, almost 15 times higher from 2010 to 2019 (Bellway p.l.c., 2010, 2019). Despite being affected by the Covid-19 pandemic, Bellway's sale has resiliently received many orders. Therefore, Bellway proposed a reduced final dividend for 2020 (Bellway p.l.c., 2020). The significant growth in dividend payment and dividend per share confirm the high financial performance of Bellway during the same time, as the Board of Bellway has been optimistic in financial returns to its shareholders. Although the dividend payment in Bellway has been constantly increased, the

proportion of dividends in the total comprehensive income for the year has been relatively stable, which has been ranged from 33% to 24% from 2010 to 2019. This means Bellway could keep a more significant proportion of income for future productivity, demonstrating Bellway's determination to enlarge its housing supply in the future quickly.

5.4.4.2.4 Miller Homes

From 2010 to 2019, Miller Homes' revenue has been raised from £320.4 million to £841.4 million. Affected by the macroeconomy, Miller Homes' loss before tax was £134.9 million in 2010. With the recovery in the UK economy and housebuilding industry, Miller Homes completed a refinance securing additional capital from its investor in 2012. Meanwhile, Miller Homes continued its action in land purchasing with a particular focus on good quality suburban development (sites) with traditional layouts and a product mix. By 2019, Miller Homes' profit before tax was £122.1 million, and the CGRA of profit before tax is calculated as 7.4% from 2010 to 2019. (Miller Homes, 2010, 2019), which demonstrates the improved financial performance.

Year	Revenue	Profit Before Tax
2010 to 2019	11.3%	7.4%
2010 to 2020	7.6%	3.8%

Source: CAGR refers to the calculation and statistics in Appendix 6

Table 23. CGRA of Miller Home's revenue and profit before tax, 2010 to 2019 and 2020.

Furthermore, the ratio of profit before tax to housing outputs is calculated in Appendix 7 and presented by the line chart below. Because of the loss of profit from 2010 to 2021, Barratt Developments' and Miller Homes' ratio of profit before

tax to housing outputs cannot demonstrate the earnings per home sold and is not calculated here. Moreover, four housebuilders' financial development has been in a more stable status after 2015, and the CAGR of ratio of profit before tax to housing supply between 2015 to 2019 (Table 24) avoid the extreme value caused by the exceptional conditions, like Barratt Developments and Miller Homes' slower financial recover in 2013 and 2014, the pandemic's impacts. It suggests the four housebuilders all have raised the profitability of each home they sold from 2010 to 2019, and the profitability was badly dropped in 2020 because of the pandemic. Also, Persimmon and Bellway's profitability per home has been higher than Barratt Developments and Miller Homes' most of the time since 2010. Barratt Developments and Persimmon have the more promising profitability per home sold in a stable development stage based on their higher CAGR.

Source: ratio of profit before tax to housing outputs refers to the calculation and statistics in Appendix 7

Figure 30. Four Housebuilders' Ratio of Profit before Tax to Housing Outputs, 2010 to 2020

Housebuilder	CGRA
Barratts Developments	10.3%
Persimmon	11.2%
Bellway	7.9%
Miller Homes	4.9%

Source: CGRA refers to the calculation and statistics in Appendix 7

Table 24. CGRA of the profit ratio before tax to housing outputs, 2015 to 2019.

5.4.5 Comparison of the Non-financial Performance for the Benefits of Society and the Environment and the Financial Performance

After answering the above questions about the private housebuilders' performance in serving the benefits of society and environment as well as financial performance, the respondents are expected to have the consolidated metrics for performance assessment and more credible understandings about the last question of performance comparison than directly answering it without the thoughts about the preceding questions. About the four housebuilders, most respondents believe the housebuilders' performance in serving company profit has surpassed or far surpassed serving the social and environmental benefits. Furthermore, none of the respondents considers the four private housebuilders have done more for serving the benefits of society and the environment than generate their business profits. Although in a small proportion, some respondents deem the builders' performance in the two sections equal. Although the four housebuilders' results about the performance comparison are generally similar, the specific extent of transcendence among them is different, which is demonstrated by the frequency analysis of the inhabitants' responses.

	Barratt Development		Persimmon		Bellway		Miller Homes	
Financial performance far surpasses non-financial performance	18	21.4%	48	53.3%	40	47.6%	42	47.7%
Financial performance surpasses the non-financial performance	52	61.9%	40	44.4%	42	50%	40	45.5%
Financial performance equal to non-financial performance	14	16.7%	2	2.2%	2	2.4%	6	6.8%

Table 25. Performance Comparison, 2010 to 2020 (the author)

CHAPTER 6, RESEARCH DISCUSSION

6.1. Introduction

In the last chapter, the primary and secondary findings and the result of statistical analysis are presented. Furthermore, in this chapter, the above findings are discussed in detail to demonstrate how they would help address the research questions and build on the previous studies. The-research discussion is the core part of this chapter, which covers the assessment of the four housebuilders' performance in serving the social and environmental benefit, creating business profits, and the performance comparison. The discussion finally determines the alignment or divergence between research findings and hypotheses. Finally, a summary of the discussion is included.

6.2 Housebuilders' Performance in Serving Benefits of Society

As the TBL framework highlights, the supportive practices within the social dimension should consider people's needs and help with the major social issues (Rogers and Ryan, 2001). This thesis took the inhabitants' perspective and assessed the four housebuilders' social performance via examining how well the four builders have satisfied inhabitants' needs or helped with their concerns.

6.2.1 Performance in Meeting Supply Demands

The UK housebuilding sector has experienced firstly the recovery from the financial crisis then the growth since 2010. Although the number of newly

completed dwellings has been raised, the growth rate has failed to simultaneously meet the increasing housing demands (Payne, 2019). Therefore, based on the gap between the housing supply and demands in the UK market, the first hypothesis is that the four housebuilders' performance in housing supply is dissatisfactory. However, the finding regarding this hypothesis presents a different result that the supply performance of Barratt Developments, Persimmon and Miller Homes is assessed as moderate while Bellway's supply performance is assessed as satisfactory. Based on Ali et al.'s (2021) view, there is a positive relationship between adequate housing supply and customer satisfaction. Therefore, the moderate or satisfactory supply performance responses suggest the four housebuilders' annual housing outputs have been acceptable among their inhabitants and at a better level than the average industrial supply.

Meanwhile, the secondary findings of annual supply and Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) also disagree with the first hypothesis. Based on the annual supply from 2010, it finds the four housebuilders have made an effort to raise their supply to meet the local needs of the newly built homes. As the above findings disclose, the CAGR of the total new dwellings completed within the UK housebuilding sector is only 5.6% from 2010 to the 2019 calendar year. Comparatively, the CAGR of Persimmon, Bellway and Miller Homes' annual supply is all higher than the national level, while Barratt's annual supply is about 0.5% lower than the national level. It suggests the under-supply issue in the UK. The sizeable private housebuilder has cared about the amount of newly completed homes and the growth of housing production. Furthermore, Bellway's supply performance is more satisfactory than the other three builders, in line with the primary findings.

Overall, based on the evidence from the inhabitants' assessment and the published statistics, this thesis defines the supply performance of large housebuilders as moderate or above, in which Bellway's performance is better than the other three builders. The findings of supply performance enrich the studies that only highlight the under-supply issue but ignore the performance of different housing developers (Wilson and Barton, 2020). Meanwhile, the supply performance of the four large private housebuilders challenges the view of blaming the under-supply issue primarily on the private housebuilders (Khan, 2017) because the findings suggest a moderate or above performance of the large private housebuilders.

In addition to assessing the supply performance, the findings also contribute one new perspective for the less agreement on the solutions of raising the housing supply, which is a supplementary explanation for the study of Wilson and Barton (2020). Regarding the issue of under-supply housing, the four large housebuilders have made efforts and had moderate or satisfactory performance in raising their annual housing supply since 2010. Especially in the fast-developed building companies like Bellway, the average supply growth rate has significantly surpassed the national level. It first demonstrates the indispensable role of large housebuilders in meeting inhabitants' growing housing needs since 2010. Meanwhile, this result also reminds researchers that only depending on the large private housebuilders is not adequate to solve the issue of under-supply housing based on the current gap between supply and demand and the large builders' supplying performance. Hence, the other housebuilders, like the smaller and medium housebuilders, the local authority and housing association, should be encouraged to contribute more housing supplies. This finding and conclusion also present convictive evidence to support the suggestions that encouraging and supporting more small and medium-sized housebuilders into the market (Legal & General, 2014, Wilson and Barton, 2020, Built Environment Committee, 2022) as

well as the local authorities and housing associations (Department for Communities and Local Government, 2017) to solve the under-supply issue in the UK.

Large housebuilders are supposed to play a significant role in meeting the UK's housing demands. Although the supply performance of Barratt Development, Persimmon and Miller Homes are higher than hypothesised, it is only assessed as moderate. In the four large housebuilders, only Bellway's performance in housing supply is assessed as satisfactory. In the earlier studies, the land was ever regarded as a constraint for the UK housing supply (Golland, 1996), which is still used to explain today's less dissatisfactory supply (Stephens, 2011, Payne, 2019). Meanwhile, Archer and Cole (2016) also believed the private housebuilders had utilised the landbanks to control their delivery of the newly developed house into the market and enhance their negotiation power with the landowners. Therefore, to further critically assess the four builders' performance in housing supply, the land bank is discussed here to clarify whether the land element has restricted their supply.

Supply Capability - Land

When discussing the housing supply performance, some criticisms regarding the land occupation were raised and believed there are the “land hoarding” phenomena among the big housebuilders (Jefferys, 2016, Wainwright, 2017, Howell, 2019). Considering the housing needs, the private housebuilders who have intentionally hoarded lands and kept them in the undeveloped statute for a long time are less evaluated regarding their contributions to the housing supply. From the perspective of industrial productivity, the land owned or controlled by a few housebuilders would not be good. The national housebuilders can acquire many lands based on their advantages in cash and relationships. Then they would

constrain the construction development to realise a better selling price or other beneficial position for themselves. Moreover, the land hoarding action potentially worsens the weak position of small and medium housebuilders (Payne et al., 2019, Breach, 2020).

In Figure 24, housebuilders' landbank supporting the forward supply at the current outputs is analysed, clarifying the four housebuilders' capacity in housing supply and demonstrating their land strategy. It finds that housebuilders with more home supplies have the bigger land bank size, which Payne et al. (2019) agreed on, who find the bigger housebuilders usually have more advantages in the land. The time for forwarding supply is longer in 2020 than in other years because the Covid-19 pandemic badly decreases home supplies.

Based on the above land banks result, it firstly confirms that the land should not be a constraint for the four builders' housing supply. Moreover, the four housebuilders should be capable of producing more homes than their real supply from 2010 to 2020, and they all have adequate lands for future development. Then the changes in land bank demonstrate the four housebuilders' business strategy that tends to shrink the current land bank and build more on the existing land, which might be driven by the expectation of quicker return on capital or by the consideration of the national housing demands. No matter which reason, the four housebuilders' decisions in land planning have reduced the land hoarding phenomenon to some extent and be beneficial to solve the under-supply issue in the UK market. Comparing the four builders, it finds Persimmon has stored more land than others. With a similar annual supply, the land bank of Persimmon is at least one year higher than Barratt Developments most of the time, indicating Persimmon has occupied lots of lands but not developed them. Meanwhile, Bellway has the most effective control in the land bank.

Understandably, housebuilders, especially the more prominent builders, maintain a particular land bank to ensure its future housing supply because the land is a crucial production material and indicator to attract investment (Payne et al., 2019). However, the question is whether the housebuilders should hold so much land for such a long time when there is a badly supply shortage in the UK housebuilding industry (Jefferys, 2016). Considering the land bank size and the annual supply, Persimmon has the most substantial possibility of hoarding the land while Bellway has the quickest speed to consume its land. The land hoarding behaviours might interrupt other builders to acquire the land they wanted, which finally hurt the overall housing supply in the UK market (Breach, 2020). Hence, from industrial productivity, Persimmon's land strategy should have less help with the supply issue and reduce its supply performance.

The changes of landbank also provide specific evidence for the discussion on the land hoarding of the large private housebuilders. Generally, the result of the landbank suggests the large housebuilders have reduced their landbank and maintained it to a smaller size than before. Unlike some studies rejecting the accusation of land hoarding without finding the evidence that the private housebuilders occupied a large amount of undeveloped land (Barker, 2004, Office of Fair Trading, 2008), this thesis provides the specific pieces of evidence identifying the intention of the four housebuilders to shrink the length of time of landbank. Without a clear standard, it is hard to define the acceptable land bank for each housebuilder; therefore, the discussion here would not define whether the four housebuilders have hoarded the land, but the discussion already demonstrates the builders' efforts in reducing the landbank.

The reason for such phenomenon could not be confirmed based on the existing

data. However, according to the conclusion of Payne et al. (2019) and Breach (2020), such business decisions in the landbank would help reduce the land hoarding and solve the under-supply issue, demonstrating the builders' efforts for inhabitants' benefits. Meanwhile, this result is also a response to the accusation that the large housebuilders have hoarded excessive land in the UK market (Bentley, 2016b, Morton, 2016), which only highlighted the relatively larger landbank of the private builders but did not mention the changes of builders' business decisions in the landbank.

After considering one significant productivity, landbank, the thesis still insists that the four large builders' supply performance since 2010 has been moderate or above and generally over the industrial performance. They all have reduced their landbank to serve the industrial production. However, Persimmon's largest land bank has been more likely to hold the land and deliberately reduce the annual supply among the four cases. Although the sizeable private housebuilder has more contributions in the under-supply issue, it has to admit that the large builders also have more substantial power in maintaining favourable landbank, which provides the greedy large builders with an opportunity to hurt the overall industrial housing delivery.

6.2.2 Performance in Solving Affordability Issue

The overall housing affordability is not satisfactory based on the decreased affordability ratio from 2010 to 2020 in the UK, which has become another issue concerned by the inhabitants (Berry, 2010, National Housing Federation, 2019). Based on the affordability in the UK house market, the second hypothesis is that the four housebuilders' efforts in helping with housing affordability are dissatisfactory. For Barratt Development, Bellway and Miller Homes, the research

findings support this hypothesis and confirm the dissatisfactory result of the three builders. Meanwhile, Persimmon's outcome is better than the hypothesis, and this builder receives a moderate assessment. The housing price is identified as the key reason for the affordability issue, and the fast boosted selling price lets the buyers, especially the first-time and young buyers, be in a problematic situation (Zyed, Abd Aziz and Hanif, 2016). Therefore, the primary research findings suggest that Persimmon should sell properties at a more affordable price averagely than the other three builders.

According to the analyse of the average selling price of the four housebuilders, it finds a similar result with the responses collected from inhabitants. After the global financial crisis, the UK housing market has experienced recovering and rebounding (Payne, 2019). Correspondingly, the average selling price of many housebuilders, including the four cases, has been growing in the first decade of the 2010s. The average selling price of Persimmon has been lower than the other three housebuilders, as well as the average level of the UK housebuilding sector from most of the year from 2010 to 2020. Therefore, the average selling price comparison demonstrates that Persimmon's housing product is more affordable than the other three builders and the average industrial level. Meanwhile, the average selling price of the other three housebuilders has surpassed the average industrial level most of the time.

In terms of the growth rate, the above findings suggest that Persimmon has well-controlled the growth of housing prices, which is slower than the other three builders and the national speed. Meanwhile, Bellway's CAGR of the average selling price from 2010 to 2019 is the highest one among the four cases, which indicates Bellway has adjusted its business strategy towards the market with the relatively higher-priced property.

By analysing the four national private housebuilders' average selling price and inhabitants' assessment, the result supports the general concern about the UK's fast-boostered housing price and housing affordability. Meanwhile, the opinion highlighting the critical role of housing price in the affordability issue (Zyed, Abd Aziz and Hanif, 2016, Lyons et al., 2017) is agreed. The inhabitants tend to have a higher assessment about the housebuilders selling the property at an affordable price and maintaining price growth at a relatively slower pace. Although Persimmon has made an effort to maintain its average selling price at the industrial level below and control the growth rate of the selling price, Persimmon's performance in raising housing affordability does not meet inhabitants' satisfaction. Meanwhile, the relatively higher selling price and significantly increased growth rate low down respondents' assessment.

According to Porter's Generic Strategies model, cost leadership is one of the typical strategies companies offer lower-priced products than the competitors. Keeping the price at a lower or reasonable level means the company has to maintain the overall cost at a certain level (Tanwar, 2013). Therefore, the private housebuilders offering the property with a lower or reasonable price, like Persimmon, should take some effort to control the cost, which finally helps with the affordability issue. For example, the builders could reduce the supply of the big and fancy houses, select the less favourable land, lower the operation cost or raise the innovative approach to save the total cost. Based on the total cost of Persimmon (Persimmon Plc, 2019), it finds that effective cost control is one of the critical reasons that allows Persimmon to sell at a more affordable price. For example, with a slightly smaller housing supply than Barratt Developments in 2017 and 2018, Persimmon's total cost was much lower (more than £1,000 million lower) (Persimmon Plc, 2017, 2018). Persimmon's progress in cost

reduction demonstrates its efforts to help with the affordability concerns. Therefore, even facing the so-called unfavourable planning system, private housebuilding companies could also adjust their business strategies and practices to offer a more affordable property.

Such results challenge one opinion, only highlighting improving the housing affordability in the UK mainly via policy makers' encouragement of housing supply and deregulation of the planning process (Affordable Housing Commission, 2020). Some studies blame the policy-maker for the strict requirements and delay process causing extra cost for the housing developers, raising the average selling price (Royal Town Planning Institute, 2017). However, Persimmon's better performance in raising housing affordability than the other three builders suggests business strategy and decisions of the private housebuilders should be considered as one reason for the affordability issue. Therefore, the research findings add view and suggest the individual housebuilders' efforts and performance in raising housing affordability can be varied based on their own business decisions rather than only depending on the local planning policy and system.

Meanwhile, this analysis also enriches the view connecting the increased housing price with the lack of housing supply (Hilber and Vermeulen, 2014, Ministry of Housing, Communities and Local Government, 2018). This result provides specific and supportive evidence for the relationship between the land supply, housing supply, and the average selling price (Saunders, 2016). Based on the research findings, the thesis believes a more complicated relationship between the housing supply and the growth of housing prices has existed in the UK market, which is in line with the conclusion of the Royal Town Planning Institute (2017).

6.2.3 Performance in Meeting Quality Needs

The housing quality is another essential element cared for by inhabitants, as it would directly influence their health and living conditions (Krieger and Higgins, 2002, Bonnefoy, 2007). The issue of housing quality has been regarded as one of the fundamental aspects of developing housing policies (Northern Housing Consortium, 2018, Goodchild, 2021). Therefore, maintaining a good quality of properties is beneficial for the inhabitants. The third hypothesis regarding housing quality is that the four housebuilders have satisfactory performance in terms of housing quality from 2010. Furthermore, according to the primary findings, the quality performance of Barratt Developments and Bellway is assessed as satisfactory, while Persimmon and Miller Homes are assessed at a moderate level. Meanwhile, it is noticed that Persimmon has the lowest grades than the other three builders, which demonstrates its worse result in terms of housing quality.

In addition to the homeowners' response, the secondary findings also help assess the four private housebuilders' performance in maintaining good housing quality. After reviewing the business strategies and practices, it finds that the four housebuilders have claimed they have included the housing quality in their strategic objectives and daily practices, which suggests the large private housebuilders are usually aware of the importance of the housing quality. Therefore, when the performance assessment of housing quality is low, the reason should not be to neglect the housing quality among the significant private housebuilders. Then the secondary data of Pride in Job Award suggests relatively the high quality of the site managers in Barratt Developments as its site managers have won most of the pride awards every year, which also explains Barratt Developments' satisfactory assessment in the primary findings. With a smaller

business scale, the quality of the site managers in Bellway and Miller Home has also been recognised by this award. Comparatively, Persimmon has the lowest quality of site managers among the four cases based on the number of awards.

The secondary data disclose the differences among the quality of site managers of the four housebuilders. The thesis believes the large private housebuilders' internal management of quality should be one of the reasons for the housing quality issue in the UK, combined with the four builders' performance assessment of housing quality. In the four cases, the more awards received by the private builder, the higher the performance assessment of housing quality. Therefore, inadequate or inappropriate quality management, including the site manager's quality, would lower the housing quality, which is in line with the findings of the Chartered Institute of Building (Wilson and Rhodes, 2019). Meanwhile, the thesis agrees with the opinion of Atout (2014) and van Heerden (2018) that the site managers can affect the construction quality and accomplishment via their experiences, expertise and soft skills, and supports (Ariadi and Setiawan, 2012) view about the positive influence of the site managers on raising housing quality. The relatively lower quality of the site managers of Persimmon helps explain the poorer grades of its performance in raising housing quality. This result also raises an implication for Persimmon or the similar housebuilders facing the quality concern that examining and assessing the quality and work of internal site managers to improve the housing quality.

Considering the housing supply, it doubts the view describing the relationship between the housing supply and the housing quality. All-Party Parliamentary Group (2016) suggested that the increased number of newly built homes would decrease the housing quality in the UK market based on the statistics of supply and customer satisfaction after the 2008 financial crisis. However, this conclusion

would not always be appropriate in the housebuilding sector during the decades of the 2010s, especially for the individual housebuilding companies. With the more housing supply every year, Barratt Developments receives a much higher performance assessment of housing quality than Persimmon in this study. Therefore, the decreasing annual supply would not be appropriate for raising the housing quality for the individual housebuilders. Moreover, the research findings also imply that raising the housing supply and quality can be realised simultaneously, and the increased housing supply would not be an excuse for the dropped housing quality.

Many media and scholars have highlighted the concern of housing quality, especially after the Grenfell Tower fire in 2017. The UK government has further intensified the stress of housing quality issues. Meanwhile, a kind of perception that the housing quality of the newly built properties has been dropped is also raised among the public (Wilson and Rhodes, 2019). However, few of these studies ever further explained the quality issue among different types of housing developers; therefore, whether the newly built properties of the large private housebuilders should take responsibility for this housing issue is still a question. Based on the research findings, it firstly supports a generally accepted view that “there is a quality gap between customer demands and industrial delivery” (All-Party Parliamentary Group, 2016, p5).

Moreover, a piece of additional evidence is provided by this thesis to help confirm the responsibility of the large private housebuilders for the dropped housing quality. Taking the national customer satisfaction survey as a reference, it finds the satisfaction (satisfactory and very satisfactory) of the four large private housebuilders’ home quality performance (Table 12) is generally lower than the national customers’ satisfaction of home quality (Figure 26), especially

Persimmon and Miller Homes have a much poorer quality performance than the national result. Although the four housebuilders are assessed with four or five stars these years in the national customers' satisfaction survey (Appendix 5), it should notice the result covers a set of questions rather than only focusing on the housing quality.

Overall, the above discussion help raise the conclusion that the large private housebuilders should take certain responsibility for the housing quality issues in the UK. Even the builder with a relatively famous brand and large commercial size, like Persimmon, its housing quality cannot always be guaranteed. Barratt Developments, Bellway and Miller Homes are believed to have a better performance in maintaining good housing quality, which is assessed as moderate to satisfactory in terms of quality performance.

Although this research finding and conclusion does not fully explain the reason for the dropped housing quality, it still confirms the hindrance of the builders' inadequate quality management and highlights the role of the site manager, which can be a reminder for the future practices of the private housebuilders to raise their housing quality. Based on the general condition of the housing quality in the UK, the research findings also offer the supplementary view that help explore studies on the housing quality of the large private housebuilders.

However, it should be noticed that this thesis and other similar studies only provide the perspectives of the inhabitants and large private housebuilders for the quality issue. To build a comprehensive understanding of the dropped housing quality and finally solve the quality issue in the UK, the scholars might consider studying this topic from other perspectives, like the government, the customers and the third parties, in the future.

6.3 Housebuilders' Performance for the Benefits of Environment

The primary data presents the private housebuilders' environmental performance from the inhabitants' perspective. The related question in the questionnaire highlights that the environmental performance assessment of the housebuilder mainly depends on how well the environmental benefit has been served by the properties inhabitants live in. For example, has the housebuilders used environmentally friendly material to improve the property's energy efficiency, and has the housebuilders efforted in building a "green" community. The private housebuilders usually emphasised their "green" contributions when promoting their brand and homes, which might not be critical. The primary data collected from their inhabitants can help assess builders' environmental performance based on their real living experience. In the prior studies, none included the primary data about the environmental performance and was collected from the homeowner, whose living experience provides direct evidence for the builders' environmental performance. Hence, the research findings fill the gap of lacking primary data to assess the builder's environmental performance.

Based on inhabitants' responses about their housebuilders' environmental performance, it was noticed that the Persimmon, Bellway and Miller Homs' grades are different despite getting the same performance assessment. Bellway has the lowest performance, while Persimmon and Miller Homes' environmental performance is close. It suggests Barratt Developments has the highest assessment while Bellway has the lowest performance. The response of the inhabitant confirms Barratt Developments and Persimmon's efforts in delivering environmental friendly properties and building environmental friendly communities. Comparatively, inhabitants feel less satisfied with such efforts of

Bellway and Miller Homes. When assessing the environmental performance of private housebuilders, it is common to use figures that are most relevant to the major environmental issue in the local market. However, the key stakeholder's (inhabitants) satisfaction is also a valuable perspective helping identify the builder's environmental efforts directly related to people's daily lives.

Compared to the primary result, a similar conclusion is raised based on the secondary findings of the four builders' environmental strategies and practices, GHG emission and waste generation. Following the widely accepted description of the metrics for the environmental performance (Uddin, Hassan and Tarique, 2008), the secondary finding can critically assess the four builders' environmental performance via examining how well have the four housebuilders done to protect the environment and reduce the negative influences of business on the environment.

First of all, the research finding is in line with the conclusion of Adams, Payne and Watkins (2008), Jones and Comfort (2020), Iles and Ryall (2016) that the focus on environmental sustainability among large housebuilders has been increased. Based on the specific sustainability strategies and practices published in the annual report, the thesis finds that the four housebuilders have prioritised major environmental issues, like GHG emissions. Therefore, it believes the larger private housebuilders have developed a strong awareness of environmental sustainability in business development. However, as Jones and Comfort (2020) mentioned, one difficulty for housebuilders to pursue sustainable development goals is performance measurement. Concerning Jones and Comfort's view (2020), the thesis proposed two approaches to measure the environmental performance of the large private housebuilder. One measurement is based on inhabitants' daily life experience about "green" property and community, which is mentioned in the

above contents, and another measurement is based on the critical environmental indicator highlighted here.

Secondly, the secondary data published in the builders' annual report, greenhouse gas (GHG) emission and waste management, is also collected to help examine the builders' environmental performance from their internal management. Towards the target of reducing carbon emission to net zero, companies from diverse sectors, including housebuilders, are expected to reduce their emissions of GHG. For the specific environmental performance, the statistics of carbon intensity suggest Barratt Developments, Persimmon and Miller Homes all have worked on decreasing the carbon emission and maintaining the carbon intensity at a more acceptable level than Bellway. Comparatively, the carbon intensity of Bellway has been increased from 1.9 to 2.8 tonnes per unit completed (Table x), which means Bellway has a poorer performance in controlling the GHG emission. About waste management, the secondary data demonstrates Barratt Developments, Persimmon and Miller Homes have a relatively better performance in controlling and reducing the waste generation than Bellway. Meanwhile, Bellway's waste intensity has been raised since it was firstly published in 2020. Although the four housebuilders all have claimed their efforts of protecting the environment, the secondary data suggests Barratt Developments, Persimmon and Miller Homes all have made some progress in their environmental performance, in which Barratt Developments has reduced its business impacts on the GHG emission and waste generation to the minor level among the four cases. Oppositely, with a growing record of GHG emission and waste generation intensity, Bellway has less served the environmental interests than the other three builders.

The comparative analysis finds that although the primary and secondary findings have different perspectives to assess the four builders' environmental

performance, the performance rank is highly close. Therefore, this thesis confirms that Barratt Developments has the best environmental performance among the four large housebuilders, while Bellway's environmental performance should be the lowest. The environmental performance of Persimmon and Miller Homes is just assessed in the middle.

According to Bowles and McLaren (2021), the consideration of private housebuilders' "green" performance has been raised among the shareholders and investors. Therefore, the research findings imply that private housebuilders with lower environmental performance, like Bellway, should pay attention to a possible future decrease in investment. Despite that the environmental target and sustainability have been widely emphasised in the UK housebuilding sector, only a small number of studies studying the business practices and performance for protecting the environment are identified. Therefore the research findings help expand the discussion for assessing the private housebuilders' environmental performance.

Thirdly, to assess the sizeable private housebuilder's environmental performance, the discussion part also assess the four large builders' environmental performance in the industrial range. As Bowles and McLaren (2021) disclosed, the average carbon intensity per home of private housebuilders has been decreased from around 2.31 tonnes per home in 2016 to 1.94 tonnes per home in 2019. During 2020, fewer home completions and increased carbon intensity (2.62 tonnes per home) in the UK private housebuilding sector because of the Covid-19 pandemic (Bowles and McLaren, 2021). Comparing the findings of Bowles and McLaren (2021) confirms the performance of Barratt Developments, Persimmon and Miller Homes in the GHG emission is above the average level, while Bellway's performance in GHG emission is still lower than the average level.

From a more holistic perspective, the 2021 NextGeneration Sustainability Benchmark suggests a similar outcome of environmental performance with the findings of this thesis. Barratt Developments and Persimmon's environmental performance is confirmed as above the average industrial level, and Barratt Developments is even ranked as the second in the 2021 NextGeneration assessment (NextGeneration, 2021). A different conclusion between the 2021 NextGeneration Sustainability Benchmark and this thesis is about the environmental performance of Bellway and Miller Homes. The NextGeneration's report (2021) deemed Bellway's environmental performance is a little ahead of Miller Homes, while the findings of this thesis suggest that Miller Homes' environmental performance is better than Bellway's. Nevertheless, this difference is explainable as this thesis assesses environmental performance from inhabitants' perspective, GHG emission and waste management. At the same time, the 2021 NextGeneration assessment considers more environmental metrics. This means Miller Homes should have focused more on building environmentally friendly properties and communities, managing GHG emissions and waste generation, while Bellway should have worked on raising environmental performance via a more general approach.

Overall the research findings indicate the environmental performance of the large private housebuilder could be varied based on their impacts on the environment via building the "green" properties and communities, managing the GHG emission and waste generation. Even the environmental issues, like GHG emission and waste generation, have been highlighted in the UK, the large private housebuilders' contributions to helping with such issues would not be promising. The large housebuilders have already taken the corresponding strategies and actions with an awareness of environmental sustainability. However, the general

environmental performance assessment could only be moderate, and a few builders like Barratt Developments would be assessed as satisfactory. Moreover, the housebuilders with a larger commercial-scale tend to be more effective than the builder with a smaller commercial scale based on the environmental metrics in this study.

When using the secondary data to assess the private housebuilders' performance, (WWF, n.d.) reminded that the private housebuilders' real practice and performance for environmental protection can be more than disclosed. As the author does not get the consent to collect the primary data directly from the four private builders, the assessment of the four builders' performance in serving the environmental benefits is not comprehensive. Nevertheless, from the perspectives of the inhabitants and the critical environmental issues in the UK, the above conclusion is more focused and practical. Future studies on the environmental performance in the UK private housebuilding sector, the more comprehensive aspects could be included.

6.4 Overall Performance for the Benefits of Society and the Environment

Overall, the primary findings indicate that the performance of Barratt Developments, Persimmon, Bellway, and Miller Homes for the benefits of society and the environment is neither satisfactory nor dissatisfactory, which is better than the 5th hypothesis of dissatisfactory performance. Based on the average grades of each builders' performance, it finds Barratt Developments has the highest performance assessment while Persimmon has the lowest result. Bellway and Miller Homes' scores are close and in the middle. When assessing the builders' performance for the benefits of society and the environment, the respondents give

their answers based on their responses to the questions in the second section of the questionnaire, which covers the builder's efforts in helping with inhabitants' needs and concerns (social performance) as well as the impacts on the environment (environmental performance). Therefore, the overall performance assessment of the four private housebuilders for the benefits of society and the environment is an assembly of the performance within the social and environmental dimensions.

It also notices that the performance for the benefits of society and the environment is the same among the four builders, but the reasons for such results are different for the individual builder, presented in table 24. For Barratt Developments, the less satisfactory performance of housing supply and affordability decrease its overall social and environmental performance. In Persimmon, the low effort in housing supply and quality is the main reason for its lower result. Bellway's dissatisfactory result in meeting inhabitants' affordability needs and moderate environmental performance makes its overall performance less than satisfactory. Like Bellway, Miller Homes also has a relatively weak performance in housing affordability and environmental impacts, resulting in the overall performance assessment.

Performance	Metrics	Barratt Developments	Persimmon	Bellway	Miller Homes
Social performance	Housing supply	Moderate 3.40	Moderate 2.96	Satisfactory 3.60	Moderate 3.16
	Housing affordability	Dissatisfactory 2.43	Moderate 3.38	Dissatisfactory 2.40	Dissatisfactory 2.48
	Housing quality	Satisfactory 3.79	Moderate 2.62	Satisfactory 3.57	Moderate 3.25

Environmental performance	Impacts on environment	Satisfactory 3.52	Moderate 3.18	Moderate 2.52	Moderate 2.93
Performance for the benefits of society and the environment		Moderate 3.24	Moderate 2.84	Moderate 3.07	Moderate 3.00

Table 26. Summary of Performance Assessment of Four Housebuilders

Based on each metric's four builders' mean results, the large private housebuilders' performance in the specific social and environmental aspects is calculated (Table x). It finds that builders' efforts for the social issues of unaffordable housing affordability are assessed as lower than the efforts in other aspects. This means the large private housebuilders' social performance in raising housing affordability should take large responsibility for the gap between the financial and non-financial performance, which will be further discussed in the following part of the comparative analysis.

Last but not least, the findings fill a gap that none of the prior research has ever studied how well the private housebuilders performed for the benefits of society and the environment from 2010 to 2020, especially with the primary findings. The TBL framework places an academic foundation for assessing the private housebuilders' social and environmental performance and helps confirm the specific assessment metrics for this study. Each metric's responses are first collected instead of collecting the answers that directly assess the housebuilders' performance for the benefits of society and the environment. Therefore, the result well avoids the deviation caused by people's different understanding about measuring builders' performance for the benefits of society and the environment, as the specific metrics are explained for the respondents before they answer the questions.

6.5 Housebuilders' Financial performance

Regarding financial performance, both the primary and secondary findings suggest that the four housebuilders have made high or very high financial performance since 2010, which is also in line with the sixth hypothesis.

Specifically, the group revenue and profit before tax are direct evidence to confirm the builders' financial performance. The dividend payment is discussed to tell the housebuilding firms' decisions between the shareholders' benefits and the reinvestment on the future production. For a company, the dividend policy signifies the financial performance and the business strategy (Loughlin, 1982). After including a set of incomes and costs, the total comprehensive income (or expense) recognised for the year would pay for the dividends and the business development in the following year. Therefore, a high dividend payment to the shareholder would influence the remaining spending on the continuing productivity in the future (Yee, 2017).

6.5.1 Key Financial Indicators

6.5.1.1 Barratt Developments

Regarding the financial performance of Barratt Development, most respondents believe it has been very high since 2010. Meanwhile, the secondary result of the group revenue, profit before tax, and their annual growth rate all indicate Barratt Developments has a good performance in finance. Furthermore, as Barratt Developments disclosed in its annual report, the financial KPIs have been completed in most of the years.

Barratt Developments' history of dividend payment firstly confirms its financial performance improvement since 2010, as Barratt Developments has increased the financial return to its shareholders. Then the dividend pay-out ratio has been increased from 32.5% in 2013 to 63.4% in 2019 (Table x). This result demonstrates that the board of directors in Barratt Developments has been more likely to raise the financial payment to the shareholders instead of the production in the following year. Meanwhile, Barratt Developments' business strategy and practices are proven effective based on the financial progress.

6.5.1.2 Persimmon

About the financial performance of Persimmon, the primary and secondary data suggest the same conclusion. The CAGR of the group revenue and profit before tax is 23.8% and 18.2% from 2010 to 2019, which confirms the growth of Persimmons' financial performance.

Persimmon has maintained a continuous record of dividend payments since 2010. The dividend pay-out ratio has increased from 19.6% to 88.1% between 2010 and 2019 in Persimmon, with promising financial performance. This result demonstrates the growing emphasis on the financial returns to the shareholders, which potentially reduce the funds for future production.

6.5.1.3 Bellway

The primary results suggest Bellway has maintained a very high financial performance since 2010. The secondary data specifically disclose a 17.2% and 35.0% CGRA of the group revenue and the profit before tax in Bellway from 2010

to 2019. Like Persimmon, Bellway has consecutive records of dividend payments since 2010. The total comprehensive income for the year has covered the dividend payment by 2.5 to 3.5 times. Based on the dividend pay-out ratio of around 33% (Table x), the board director at Bellway has maintained relatively lower but stable financial returns to its shareholders among the cases, which suggests Bellway tried to return more funds for the future primary production.

6.5.1.4 Miller Homes

Miller Homes' financial performance since 2010 is assessed as high by its inhabitants, which is also supported by the secondary result of the growth of group revenue, profit before tax and return on capital employed. There is no dividend payment to the equity shareholders in Miller Homes. Therefore, Miller Homes' financial performance from the point of dividend cannot be analysed in this study.

6.5.2 Comparison of the Financial Performance

Although the financial performance of the four housebuilders is assessed as high to very high, some differences are highlighted by the performance comparison.

Firstly, it is no doubt that the four private housebuilders have significantly improved their revenue and profits since 2010. Despite using different performance metrics, the assessment of Barratt Developments, Persimmon and Bellway's financial performance is still consistent with the conclusions of Hardman & Co. (2020), Archer and Cole (2021, 2014). Although the financial performance of Miller Homes has not been studied in depth by scholars, the consecutive record on its annual account can raise a credible conclusion.

Moreover, agreeing with the existing studies on the private housebuilders' financial performance, the result also suggests that large private housebuilders have generally made progress in their financial performance since they recovered from the financial crisis in the UK.

Secondly, the dividend payment records demonstrate the growth of the four larger builders' financial performance as the dividend payment per share, and the dividend pay-out ratio has been increased. This conclusion is consistent with the widely accepted view that the earnings per share and dividend payment has a positive relationship in the UK housebuilding sector (Ooi, 2001, Vivian, 2006, Khan and Shamim, 2017).

Meanwhile, the business decision of the director of the board in the four building companies can be indicated by the dividend pay-out ratio, which is believed as a measure of a firm's dividend policy (Loughlin, 1982). Generally, Bellway has a relatively lower and stable dividend pay-out ratio than Barratt and Persimmon, which has been maintained between 30% to 35%. The director of the Barratt Developments Board usually decided not to issue the dividend when they faced challenges, like the recovery period after the financial crisis and the year of the covid-19 pandemic. Furthermore, Barratt Development has raised the dividend pay-out ratio from below 40% in 2013 to over 60% in 2019. Comparatively, the dividend pay-out ratio of Persimmon has been mostly fluctuant and kept above 60% in most years. According to Fitri, Hosen and Muhari (2016), the remaining amount that is not used for dividend payment would usually be paid off debt or the reinvestment in the core operations.

Therefore, the above result suggests Bellway has more focused on expanding its core business and spending earnings on delivering more dwellings, which can also

explain the significant growth of its housing supply since 2010. As a national housebuilding leader, Barratt Developments has a highly cautious attitude and a long-term perspective when proposing the dividend payment. The findings also suggest that in Barratt Developments, the total earnings for the period attributable to the group owners can usually cover the regular dividend payment by 2.5 times, and including the special dividend, the pay-out ratio was usually over 60%.

Barratt Developments' decision on the dividend payment not only reserves adequate funds for future housing delivery but also secures shareholders' interests and investments for the long term. Although the dividend pay-out ratio in Barratt Development is not relatively high, its total financial returns to the shareholder have been higher than most of the housebuilders in the UK (Hardman & Co., 2020). However, the conclusion of Hardman & Co. (2020) did not consider the dividend payment of Persimmon. Persimmon's dividend records demonstrate that it has tended to give financial returns to its shareholders to secure or acquire more shareholders' funds and interests; therefore, the reserved funds for the housing development afterwards should be reduced.

The comparison of the annual housing supply further confirms that despite being a national housing builder as Barratt Developments, Persimmon has spent a smaller proportion of money on reproduction. Meanwhile, Persimmon's average cost per newly built property is lower than Barratt Developments', which also confirms Persimmon's allocation of earnings less, highlighting building the properties with prices as high as the properties of Barratt Developments and Bellway.

Generally, the dividend payment and pay-out ratio of the three cases support the conclusion of Barclay, Holderness and Sheehan (2003), Holder, Langrehr and Hexter (1998), Fama and French (2001), Grullon and Michaely (2002), Al-Malkawi (2007), Uwuigbe, Jafaru and Ajayi (2012) that the larger companies are more likely to pay more dividend or raise higher pay-out ratio because they feel easier to access to the external funds and less dependent on the internal capital. Although Barratt Developments and Persimmon have made different decisions on dividend policy, the dividend payment and pay-out ratio of them have been higher than the smaller housebuilder, Bellway.

Overall, the results of the four cases confirm that the financial performance of the large private housebuilders in the UK has been significantly improved since 2010. From the perspective of finance, the large private housebuilders have come out from the “recovery” stage from the financial year of 2013. However, Payne (2016, 2019) mentioned no recovery stage. It found that although the builders like Persimmon still made profits after the financial crisis, their financial records have poorly been dropped. Therefore, more specifically, the financial performance of the large private housebuilders has been obvious and rapidly boosted after 2013. Since the covid-19 pandemic spreading and corresponding policies being implemented in the UK, the financial performance of the large private housebuilders has been badly hit. However, a set of favourable policies released the pressures of the large private housebuilders and maintained the acceptable profits on the builders' financial records but still poorer than the prior years.

The dividend payment and dividend pay-out ratio generally confirm the high to the very high financial performance of the large private housebuilder in the UK. However, the specific dividend policy of the four cases demonstrates that large private housebuilders have different decisions on financial returns to their

statehooders or reproduction in the future, for which the specific reasons are not further investigated. Therefore, future research could consider studying the factors driving the dividend decisions of large private housebuilders in the UK. Based on the research findings, it finds. However, as the large private housebuilders in the UK, the building companies with the larger business scale and annual housing supply (e.g., Barratt Development, Persimmon) tended to maintain a higher dividend pay-out ratio than the building companies with a smaller business scale and annual housing supply (e.g., Bellway).

6.6 Comparative Analysis: Non-financial Performance for the Benefits of Society and the Environment vs Financial Performance

According to the primary and secondary results, the last research question is that the four housebuilders' financial performance has surpassed or far surpassed their social and environmental benefits performance. The above contents confirm that the non-financial performance for social and environmental benefits of the four large private housebuilders from 2010 to 2020 is assessed as moderate, while the financial performance of the four builders is assessed as high or above.

The primary findings suggest that Barratt Developments should have a more negligible difference between its financial performance and its performance for the benefit of society and the environment. About 21.4% of the responses believe Barratt Developments' financial performance far surpasses the social and environmental benefits performance, and 16.7% of the respondents select the equal performance. Furthermore, about the other three housebuilders, over 45% of respondents consider that their builder's financial performance far exceeds the

performance for social and environmental benefits. Especially in Persimmon, about 53.3% of the respondents believe this builder's financial performance is far beyond its non-financial performance for the benefits of society and the environment. Moreover, the research findings also demonstrate the four housebuilders' more significant considerations for their business profit than the social and environmental benefits in some decisions.

The secondary findings also support the above conclusion. Specific evidence is provided from the secondary results regarding the performance assessment via each metric. As the above discussion mentioned, comparing the four housebuilders' performance based on the primary findings is also well supported and further explained by the secondary results. Although the conclusion about the last research question seems the same as the primary results, it is raised based on the analysis of both the primary and secondary findings.

Based on the above results, the gap between the four housebuilders' financial and non-financial performance has mainly resulted from the builders' moderate performance in serving the benefits of society and environment and the high or very high financial performance.

As mentioned above, the four builders' overall performance for social and environmental benefits is determined by their performance within the specific social and environmental aspects, which means the particularly low-performance assessment would explain the gap between the housebuilders' non-financial and financial performance. Based on the four builders' mean results of specific social and environmental aspects, it suggests the large builders' performance in helping with inhabitants' concerns about the affordability issue is less satisfactory than other aspects. Besides, the private housebuilder's supply performance has been

discussed and regarded as the top priority. One typical view that is widely accepted is that the current housing supply has been far below the housing demands in the UK (Payne, 2019, Neil, 2020, Barton and Wilson, 2021), which is different from the conclusion of this study. Therefore, a further study on the significant challenges in raising housing supply and affordability and the potential conflicts between the housebuilders' non-financial and financial decisions are taken in the following contents, which is expected to better explain whether the large private housebuilders have more served the benefits of the society and environment or their profits. It also discusses the reasons causing the performance gaps among the four cases are different, demonstrating the large private housebuilders' different levels of focus in terms of these social and environmental aspects.

6.6.1 Housing Supply vs Business Profit

Regarding the above comparative result, this part discusses the corresponding causes and further confirms the four private housebuilders' higher motivation for profits than meeting inhabitants' supply needs.

It is believed that the actual number of homes completed is usually lower than what the private housebuilders would produce (Bentley, 2016c, Payne et al., 2019). Based on the above discussion over the four builders' land bank and financial performance, this view is partly agreed and further explained as the large private housebuilders should be capable of delivering more dwellings than its current housing supply. However, this study cannot confirm the gap between real supply and the resources and capability of the small and medium builders. The four housebuilders should have the more excellent capability, including the skills and resources to produce more homes than the current outputs, but they have

decided not to do so, which means some supply constraints existed in the four building companies.

Two significant reasons were raised to explain why the housing developer constricted their supply. In Adams, Leishman and Moore's (2009) study about the building speed of the speculative housebuilder within the UK, the market absorption is highlighted. It believes how fast the home could be sold rather than how fast the construction technology allows the housebuilder to produce would determine the speed of home construction and supply. The competition of acquiring the limited lands among housebuilders was usually fierce, so the housebuilders had to "take the most optimistic view" about the future selling price and financial returns to raise the winning bids for lands (Adams, Leishman and Moore, 2009, p304, Payne et al., 2019). It explained why the housebuilders have been extremely cautious about the capacity that the local housing marketing could absorb and the related selling price when making the construction plan. From the market-based perspective, it believes the four housebuilders should have considered the market absorption when making the housing supply plan, which means they have placed the business profits ahead of the inhabitants' housing demands at the beginning. Considering the market absorption, the housebuilders tend to develop a business model of maximising the profit from the site instead of the quantity or speed of delivery adopted (Select Committee on Economic Affairs, 2016).

It is reasonable for the private builders to consider the market absorption as it would directly affect the business revenue and -term development. Ignorance of the local market absorption would disturb the real estate market and hurt the builder itself or other builders' benefits (Office of Fair Trading, 2008, Payne et al., 2019). Nevertheless, the concern that some private builders only care about the

market absorption and over restrict the build-out rate intentionally is raised (Payne et al., 2019).

The research finding of the supply performance suggests the supply of Barratt Developments, Persimmon and Miller Homes has not reached inhabitants' satisfaction, while Bellway's annual supply is satisfactory among the inhabitants. This means Barratt Developments, Persimmon and Miller Homes' market in the UK range is more likely to be not saturated than Bellway's. Therefore, market absorptivity should not be an excuse for Barratt Developments, Persimmon and Miller Homes to restrict their annual supply.

About the behaviour of production restriction, the author agrees with what the Communities and Local Government Committee (2017, p8) explained “it was rational commercial behaviour” for housebuilders to build out slowly to avoid saturating the local housing market and reduce their profits. Intentionally keeping the speed of the home construction and delivery might be a “sound” business model in the housebuilding industry. However, it “was not one that for the country's best interests”. The author has contacted the four housebuilders about collecting the primary data, but none provides such an opportunity. Therefore, it cannot judge whether the four housebuilders have intentionally constrained their supply for the higher profits in this study.

The UK range's housebuilding market is far from saturation, considering the national housing supply storage. However, saturation is still possible in the local market, which further affects the built-out rate of builders (Chamberlain Walker and Barratt Developments, 2017). Even though admitting market absorption has existed for the large private housebuilders, they still have some initiatives to raise the market absorption rate and increase their supplies. By realising the restricted

market absorption, Letwin (2018) suggested solving the problem that the relatively homogenous housing products (similar in size, design, context and tenure) have been built by the major housebuilders. In addition, Eve (2018) pointed out that a relatively lower price and selecting the site with lower local competition would also help increase market absorption. This means the four housebuilders at least have the solutions to raise their local market absorption, develop more homes for the people in need, and raise their performance assessment. Moreover, the Housing, Communities and Local Government Committee (2021) collected data from multiple stakeholders regarding the build-out rate. They summarised that the build-out had not been raised in the past few years and the issue is particularly worse in the large builders than the small builders, which raise doubts about whether the large private housebuilders have intentionally constrained their annual supply for the higher profits or not.

Overall, it confirms that the market rule in the housebuilding sector makes the four housebuilders place the business profit ahead of local demands. Specifically, the research findings present several facts. Firstly, the four large builders have adequate resources and capability for a higher housing supply. Secondly, market saturation should not be a constraint for the housing supply of Barratt Developments, Persimmon and Miller Homes because inhabitants' housing demands have not been satisfied. Thirdly, whether market saturation is the reason for production constraint cannot be confirmed in Bellway.

Another reason for the shortage of supply is the planning system. Although admitting the inadequate housing supply from the private housebuilder, some studies defend the housebuilder's supply performance and blame the planning system. Based on this view, the government's policy should take significant responsibility for the low supply (Adams, Leishman and Moore, 2009,

Chamberlain Walker and Barratt Developments, 2017).

Based on the statistics of the granted application and the duration for approval, it finds the proportion of plan approval has been raised while the corresponding time has also been reduced (Department for Levelling Up, Housing & Communities, 2021). The efficiency of the UK land planning system has not met the private housebuilders' requirements (Payne et al., 2019, Airey and Doughty, 2020). However, it firstly confirms some improvements in the planning system. Therefore, the pressures from the planning system should be reduced for the large private housebuilders, and more planning applications should have been approved in a shorter time than before. In the industrial range, a gap between the approved units and the dwellings started or completed has existed since 2010, and this gap has been enlarged over time. It suggests the decreased interference from the planning systems to the private builders' housing supply. The author cannot assess the data of approved units of the four housebuilders and identify the gap between approved units and annual completion. However, the above discussion suggests the moderate supply performance of Barratt Developments, Persimmon and Miller Homes should less blame the planning system than before.

Because of lacking access to collecting the primary data from the four housebuilders, the author cannot confirm whether the four large builders have sacrificed some inhabitants' demands and pursued higher profitability. Even accessing the four builders' responses, the author might not confirm this question. Therefore, the author discusses the two most typical and significant factors for constraining housing supply in the UK and confirms the reduced impacts of the market saturation and the delay of the planning system on reducing the annual housing supply for the large housebuilders. This discussion raises the doubt and the new pieces of evidence for the prior views that only blaming the external

factors for the dropped build-out rate but ignoring the possibility of the large private housebuilders' excessive pursuit of profits (Adams, Leishman and Moore, 2009, Chamberlain Walker and Barratt Developments, 2017, Payne et al., 2019).

6.6.2 Housing Affordability vs Business Profit

Regarding the affordability issue, substantial research has ever studied the causes. Based on the relevance with the private housebuilders, the factors of price and supply are discussed. As Zyed, Abd Aziz and Hanif (2016) highlighted, the reduction of affordability mainly results from the fast growth of housing prices. According to the above discussion on the average selling price, it finds the four housebuilders all have significantly raised their average selling price from 2010.

Along with the growth of the average selling price, the profitability of the four housebuilders has been significantly raised at the same time. The profit ratio is analysed before-tax to housing outputs to measure the housebuilder's profitability. Based on analysing this ratio in the UK housebuilding sector, it finds that the private housebuilders' profit has been increased for every newly completed housing. This result confirms that housebuilders' profitability has been raised and explains the fast growth of housing prices (Archer and Cole, 2021). Therefore, some views criticise housebuilders have made "juicy" profits in selling housing, but the whole market is still facing the supply shortage and affordability issue (The Economist, 2019).

With Archer and Cole's (2021) approach, the ratio of profit before tax to housing supply of the four housebuilding companies from 2010 to 2019 is analysed. Because of the pandemic, the ratio in 2020 is generally lower than its average level and cannot well present the overall trend since 2010. Therefore the 2020 ratio is

not included in the below discussion on the four housebuilders' overall profitability trend per unit. Even though including the ratio in 2020, there is still considerable profit growth before tax to housing supply in the four housebuilding companies from 2010.

The constraint on housing supply is also regarded as one reason to raise housing prices and the affordability issue (Hilber and Vermeulen, 2014). Therefore, the housebuilders could set a more favourable price by controlling their housing supply. The above section explains that the four housebuilders have restricted their supply. According to the impacts of supply constraints on the housing price (Glaeser, Gyourko and Saks, 2005, Hilber and Vermeulen, 2014), the selling price of properties of the four builders has been raised indirectly with the supply constraints, which also explains the rapid growth of their average selling price between 2010 to 2019. Regardless the four housebuilders would like to help with the affordability concerns. Their supply constraints have already negatively affected housing affordability.

The housebuilders' decisions to chase profits are reasonable, and this thesis would not criticise the large private housebuilders just because of their profit growth. Creating profits is one of the economic requirements of the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) framework, which is a crucial element for the sustainable development of business (Alhaddi, 2015). However, based on the above discussion, the doubt is raised that have the four large housebuilders been overly greedy, so that they have raised such high house prices and realised abundant profits despite facing the severe affordability issue in the UK market.

Based on the research findings, the fact is that the fast-growing average selling price has helped realise the superb profitability for the four housebuilders, but it

has less contributed to raising housing affordability and even worsened the affordability issue. Besides, the considerable growth of the ratio of profit before tax to supply (Figure 30) further confirms the four builders' tendency to the business model of maximising the profit from the site instead of the quantity or speed of delivery (Select Committee on Economic Affairs, 2016). This business model has helped the four housebuilders realise higher profits from every unit they sold but decreased their housing affordability at the same time.

Overall, without the primary data from the four housebuilders, the thesis still cannot confirm the builders' expectations about the profitability and whether they have overly greedy or not. Nevertheless, the research findings and above discussions agree with the studies of Archer and Cole (2016, 2021) and conclude that much more considerations have been placed on the business profit rather than helping with the affordability issue by the large private housebuilders.

6.6.3 Funds for Reproduction vs Financial Returns for

Shareholders

Since a large amount of money has been made in the housebuilding sector, how have the housebuilders used the total comprehensive income after deducing a set of costs is another evidence showing the builders' business decision. According to Sholichah et al. (2021), the dividend policy is usually determined by two elements: paying the shareholders and how many profits are retained for future projects. A high-value dividend payment means the company has done well in generating profit, while it also indicates the company would reinvest less money back into the business.

After analysing the payment and pay-out ratio of the dividends of the four

housebuilders, it finds that a large proportion of the attributable income has been allocated to the shareholders instead of investment in future production. This also indicates that the three builders contribute more benefits to their shareholders than the wide range of inhabitants. The attributable incomes might be invested in the projects, like upgrading technologies to raise construction quality and efficiency, innovating in home design to deliver better property, using environmentally friendly materials (Cheshire and Buyuklieva, 2019), or developing more private and affordable properties relating to the benefits for inhabitants and the environment. Although the three builders mentioned they had taken similar actions, the distribution of income suggests the large part of income has gone to the pocket of their shareholders instead of raising the benefits for inhabitants, and the environment is questioned.

A disagreement might be raised as the high dividend payment is expected to increase the investors' confidence and attracts more funds for future development (Harris, Hartzmark and Solomon, 2015). However, the fact in the UK housebuilding sector might be different from Harris, Hartzmark and Solomon's view (2015). Archer and Cole (2021) analysed one of the largest shareholders in the UK housebuilding sector, Norges Bank Investment Management, and found that the large scale of capital has flowed to this shareholder from the UK housebuilders. Nevertheless, compared to the significant capital returns, Norges's reinvestment in the productive activities in the UK housebuilding industry has been fewer, which means the high dividend payment might not always get more funds for future development. According to the equities information of the four housebuilders, Norges is also one major shareholder of Barratt Developments, Persimmon and Bellway (Financial Times, 2021). Therefore, it believes the dividend policy in Barratt Developments, Persimmon and Bellway should be more beneficial for the shareholders than the productive activities.

6.7 Summary

The primary and secondary findings are discussed in this chapter, which helps answer the research questions and revise the hypotheses in this thesis. The first conclusion is that the four large private housebuilders' performance in creating benefits for the UK society and environment from 2010 to 2020 is assessed as moderate, which is raised based on the builders' performance in each metric of the social and environmental dimension. Then the large private housebuilders' financial performance in the UK within the same period is assessed as high to very high, suggesting significant financial progress within the building sector. Finally, by comparing the non-financial and financial performance of the four cases, the thesis concludes that large private housebuilders' performance in creating business profits has surpassed or highly surpassed the performance in creating the social and environmental benefits. In addition to answering the research questions, the above discussions and comparisons also help enrich the research of the private housebuilders' performance in the UK, providing a new or more vital explanation to support, extend or challenge the prior studies. Meanwhile, some practical implications for the large private housebuilders and other stakeholders are also identified.

CHAPTER 7, CONCLUSION

The last chapter provides the concluding remarks on the thesis, structured with four sections. Firstly, the chapter summarises this thesis and highlights conclusions for the research objectives. Then, the significant contributions, implications and recommendations, and limitations of this thesis are explained in the following sections, respectively.

7.1 Summary of the Thesis

Regarding performance management, more and more private housebuilders realise the importance of non-financial performance, highlighting the influence of business on society and the environment. It finds many private housebuilders in the UK have set the business objective of serving customers' needs, developing the local communities and protecting the ecosystem, which is expected to benefit UK society and the environment. Despite caring about the benefits of society and the environment, the private housebuilders' contributions to the social and environmental benefits are controversial, and the previous evaluations of their overall business performance are varied. Based on the controversial performance assessment of the private housebuilders, the author identifies the significance of this research topic, the academic, theoretical and methodological gaps. Then the research aim is raised as assessing and comparing the target private housebuilders' performance for the benefits of society and the environment, and their financial performance in the UK from 2010 to 2020.

A theoretical framework for assessing the private housebuilder's performance is developed with the literature review on the cooperate social responsibility (CSR), triple bottom line (TBL), and stakeholder theory. TBL sets the foundation of this

framework, and the widely adopted metrics of the three TBL dimensions are included in the theoretical framework for this study. Meanwhile, one of the essential stakeholders in the housebuilding sector is identified, the customer (inhabitant), who provides another perspective to refine the theoretical framework for performance assessment. Finally, the performance assessment framework comprises the inhabitants' needs or concerns, environmental impacts, and key financial indicators to assess social, environmental, and financial performance. The literature review on the industry helps identify the significant issues in the UK housebuilding sector since 2010. It enriches the knowledge about the industrial and private builders' previous performance and improves the applicability of the theoretical framework for the target industry and cases via including the issues representing the social and environmental benefits the most. The theoretical framework and research hypotheses are developed based on the second and third chapters.

The thesis is conducted with the deductive approach and case study strategy. The primary data is collected from the customers (inhabitants) of the four housebuilders via the questionnaire based on the quantitative research method. The secondary data related to the research questions are collected from the companies' annual report, financial statement, national statistics, National House Building Council's data, and other trusted sources. Then the raw data is processed and analysed with the SPSS and Excel tools and descriptive statistics. Finally, the research findings and primary and secondary data discussion are presented in the fifth and sixth chapters, realising the following objectives.

1. The four private housebuilders' performance for the benefits of society and the environment in the UK from 2010 to 2020 is assessed as moderate, neither satisfactory nor dissatisfactory.

This result is raised based on the metrics for assessing the social and environmental performance: 1) the contributions to meeting the inhabitants' needs or helping with their concerns in terms of housing supply, housing affordability and housing quality (social dimension), and 2) the contributions to helping the environmental issues in greenhouse gases (GHG) emission and waste generation. Although the research findings indicate the four housebuilders' performance for the benefits of society and the environment are at the same level (moderate), their contributions to the specific issues are varied, explaining their different performance scores. Specifically, Barratt Developments, Bellway and Miller Homes' dissatisfactory performance in raising housing affordability decrease their overall social and environmental performance. Meanwhile, only Persimmon's effort with housing affordability is assessed as moderate. Only Bellway's performance is assessed as satisfactory about the housing supply issue, but its environmental performance is much lower than the other three builders. Barratt Developments' highest score of non-financial performance is contributed by its satisfactory result in housing quality and environment issues. Comparatively, Miller Homes has performed at a moderate level in raising housing supply, quality, and environmental impacts.

2. The four private housebuilders' financial performance in the UK from 2010 to 2020 is assessed as high to very high.

Implicated from the TBL framework, the private housebuilder's finance performance is assessed by the key financial indicators of revenue, profit before tax, dividend payments. From 2010 to 2020, the four housebuilders have made considerable revenues and profits, ensuring that great dividends for their shareholders have been made. Miller Homes is an exception in the four cases

which has not released the dividend. Specifically, the financial performance of the larger housebuilders, Barratt Developments, Persimmon and Bellway, is assessed as higher than Miller Homes'.

3. The four private housebuilder's financial performance surpassed or far surpassed their performance for the benefits of society and the environment in the UK from 2010 to 2020.

Based on the private builder's performance for the benefits of society and the environment and their financial performance, the third research question is finally answered, and a noticeable gap is identified between the financial and non-financial performance. Specifically, the primary challenges in improving housing supply and affordability, the conflicts between the housebuilders' non-financial and financial decisions, the considerations on the financial returns to shareholders and the reproductions are further discussed to further explain the large private housebuilders have more served profits than the benefits of the society and environment

7.2 Research Contributions

The thesis provides insights to assessing the large private housebuilder's performance for the benefits of society and the environment and their financial performance in the UK from 2010 to 2020. After reviewing a broad range of literature on the UK housebuilding sector, few of them ever studied the performance of the private housebuilders for the benefit of society and the environment. Relevantly, several studies ever explained the CSR and sustainable development goals (SDGs) practices of the private housebuilders in the UK (Idowu and Towler, 2004, Myers, 2005, Jones, Comfort and Hillier, 2006, Jones and

Comfort, 2020). Nevertheless, none of these studies assesses the private housebuilder's performance under the CSR or SDGs target. Therefore, the first contribution of this thesis is to enrich the literature of builder's performance assessment for the benefits of society and the environment, CSR performance, the progress of SDGs in the UK housebuilding sector.

Another contribution of the thesis is to develop a theoretical framework for performance assessment in the UK private housebuilding sector. Learning from the TBL framework and including the most updated and significant issues in the UK housebuilding sector during the target period, this framework should assess the private builder's performance for social and environmental benefits and financial performance. The performance assessment framework in this thesis can be a reference for the private builders in the UK to measure their performance or for scholars to conduct relevant studies in the future. Meanwhile, the contributions of the theoretical framework should be extended to studies in other areas. The development of the theoretical framework overcomes the TBL drawback of covering too many elements in the three dimensions and identifying the most typical metrics. Also, the thesis contributes an approach of focusing on the particular perspective of the stakeholders and the most critical issues in the industry to deal with the difficulty of quantifying the social performance in the TBL framework. For the studies focusing on other stakeholders, industries or countries, the development process of the performance assessment framework would also be a reference.

The thesis offers the methodological contribution, which is assessing the private builders based on the primary data, the responses of inhabitants. Many statistics about the UK housebuilding sector are available, which explains why many scholars only use secondary data in their studies (Wellings, 2006). As the first

chapter mentioned, the methodological gap was identified by Wellings (2006) before, which still exists in recent studies. Therefore, the thesis helps narrow down the methodological gap in the studies on performance measurement in the UK housebuilding sector. The thesis discusses the primary and secondary data to answer the research questions. Compared to some existing studies only using secondary data, the combination of the primary and secondary data facilitates the extension of evidence, presents multiple perspectives, and further reinforces the conclusion's credibility.

The thesis contributes by raising some findings and conclusions via a relatively objective discussion. Under the research topic, the intermediate results of the four private builders' performance for the benefits of society and the environment are concluded, which response to the arguments on the builder's social and environmental performance in the UK. The thesis presents the result with trackable evidence and objective analysis about the performance assessment of Barratt Developments, Persimmon, Bellway and Miller Homes. Instead of directly assessing the four private builders' overall performance for the benefits of society and the environment, the questionnaire explains a consolidated approach for the performance assessment, which reduces the confusion among the respondents and ensures consistency in the assessment system. Even though the overall assessment of performance for the benefits of society and the environment is the same, the thesis elaborates the four builders' performance in each specific housing issue, like to what extent the four housebuilders have satisfied their inhabitant's housing demands, helped with the affordability and quality concerns. These findings would extend the understanding of the stakeholders who care about the specific evidence of builders' social and environmental performance. For example, the findings of four builders' efforts to raise housing affordability could be a reference for young buyers with limited affordability. The findings regarding the

builder's environmental impacts would be valuable for the organisations aiming to protect the environment.

Furthermore, discussions on these specific factors would be valuable for the four builders themselves to assess companies' performance, make business decisions, and practice in the future. For example, Barratt Developments has a better performance in supply, quality and environment but poor result in housing affordability, which should clarify Barratt Developments' marketing position from customers' perspective and raise Barratt Developments' awareness in managing the housing price. Persimmon has performed better in housing affordability than other aspects, benefiting business promotion and extension. However, the performance in housing quality would raise Persimmon's concern based on its lowest score among the four cases. Bellway's poor environmental performance results should be a lesson to realise the necessity of more effective environmental efforts. The above discussions help Miller Homes realise its relatively poor performance of housing affordability, which could be a warning for overall customer satisfaction. Overall, the discussion and result in the thesis is expected to draw some recommendations for private housebuilders in the UK, which is explained in the next section

The high financial performance of the four builders is confirmed by both the primary assessment and secondary financial data. In addition to the most discussed indicators of revenue and profit before tax, the thesis highlights the new financial evidence in the data discussion chapter: dividend payment and the ratio of profit before tax to per housing supply. According to Select Committee on Economic Affairs (2016), the business model of maximising the profit from the site instead of the quantity or speed of delivery is taken in the UK housebuilding sector. No builders ever admitted it, and few researchers ever discussed it. However, the

thesis contributes to this viewpoint by disclosing the high growth rate of the ratio of profit before tax to housing supply. Therefore, the discussion on the four builders' financial performance reminds readers to pay more attention to business revenue, profits, and other financial evidence.

The big gap between the private builder's performance for the benefits of society and the environment and their financial performance is confirmed, and it demonstrates the four private housebuilders have more or much more served the business profits than the benefits of the UK society and environment. The comparative analysis responds to some views that defend the private housebuilders' behaviours — for example, comparing the time and number of planning applications approved from 2010 to 2020 challenges the viewpoint of taking the planning system as the primary constraint for housing supply (Adams, Leishman and Moore, 2009, Chamberlain Walker and Barratt Developments, 2017). However, it should be noticed that the thesis is not on the opposite side of these defending viewpoints. The primary intention of the thesis is to contribute more discussions and evidence from multiple perspectives. Additionally, the thesis also reinforces some views about private housebuilders' behaviours. For example, the four builders' land bank enhances the viewpoint of large builders having more land acquisition and control (Payne et al., 2019). Overall, the thesis gathers multiple shreds of evidence for comparing the four private builders' performances for the society and the environment and their financial performance, which contributes strands of insights to the systematic research agenda on the sizeable private builder's performance in the UK.

7.3 Implications and Recommendations of Thesis

The thesis raises some implications for both the academics and functional areas.

Based on research findings, the four builders' financial performance is found to surpass or far surpass their performance for the benefits of society and the environment. Regarding this finding, the four builders' moderate performance for the benefit of society and the environment attracts more attention. Although the four housebuilders' performance in some aspects is better than the industrial performance, the moderate and dissatisfactory performance, especially from the inhabitants' perspective, could threaten the housebuilders' customer satisfaction and brand image. Therefore, the four builders are suggested to monitor their non-financial performance and identify the priority issues to reduce the performance gap.

Specifically, Barratt Developments, Bellway and Miller Homes all have the weaker performance in housing affordability. The three housebuilders should be aware of inhabitants' dissatisfaction with their efforts in housing affordability. Furthermore, the secondary results further confirm the low affordability of the three builders. Firstly, the three builders' low affordability is likely to cause more criticisms and enhance the greedy company image in the housebuilding sector. Then, the low profitability might not be a threatening issue for the three builders currently. However, such a price strategy could reduce the builders' competitiveness in price when the under-supply issue is being mitigated in the UK. Moreover, the significantly boosted housing price causing the overheated market could be a potential risk for the financial crisis, a hit for the private housebuilders.

According to the average selling price and the price growth rate of Barratt Developments, Bellway and Miller Homes, the thesis suggests that the three builders should do land planning considering housing affordability, reducing the production cost and lowering the housing price at the beginning. Given the very

rapid growth of profit, the directors in the three builders might consider making more contributions to meet the affordability needs of inhabitants, even scarfing some of the profits, like giving some discounts to the young buyers or first-time buyers.

Conversely, Persimmon has the best performance in housing affordability because its average selling price and price growth are slower than others. Compared to the other three builders and the industrial level, Persimmon's high affordability would be particularly attractive to buyers with high price sensitivity. Persimmon's effort in housing affordability would also help many young, and first-time buyers get on the property ladder. It suggests that Persimmon take the affordable housing price as one of the marketing points to raise affordable features, attract more buyers, build a strong relationship with the young and first-time buyers, which could be further developed as a competitive advantage for the long term. However, Persimmon has a poorer performance in housing supply and housing quality than the other three builders. As one of the biggest housebuilders, Persimmon should be aware of assessment below satisfaction. As the thesis disclose, the performance assessment in supply issue could be explained by Persimmon's inclination for land hoarding. Although Persimmon has been a leader based on its annual supply, it has owned or controlled numerous undeveloped lands, which would raise the negative evaluations of housing organisations, the public and the small and medium-sized builders. Meanwhile, the large landbank could risk Persimmon's cash flow and funds for other aspects, like reproduction. Therefore, reducing the landbank size or clarifying the necessity of the large landbank could be a solution instead of increasing the housing supply blindly. Meanwhile, both the primary findings and the secondary evidence demonstrate a less satisfactory quality of Persimmon dwellings. This should be a top priority for Persimmon. The quality issue would increase the customer complaints, decrease customer satisfaction,

incur extra costs for housing maintenance, negatively affecting the companies' sales and evaluation. It is highly recommended to Persimmon to take more efforts to raise the housing quality than before, like implementing "the Plan" rigorously. Based on the research discussion, the site managers should be one of the reasons for the quality performance; therefore, Persimmon is suggested to consider taking some actions about it, like regularly reviewing the works of site managers and providing more training to its site managers.

Additionally, Bellway is found to have a lower performance in terms of its influence on the environment, resulting from its less satisfactory result of building "green" property and community, GHG emissions and waste generation. More and more people have cared about the environmental issues in the UK; therefore, Bellway's environmental performance first would raise more negative comments. Meanwhile, a weak environmental performance would also make Bellway unfavourable among the customers highly concerning with environmental protection. Moreover, the UK government has put the net zero emission target by 2050 in the legislation, which means Bellway's slower environmental progress currently might require investing ample unexpected time and money in the future. If continued such environmental efforts and performance, Bellway would be inferior to others in environmental innovation. Therefore, one implication for Bellway is to take more effort into the two environmental aspects. Bellway is suggested first to examine the reason for its lower performance. Considering Bellway's business expansion target, the builders should spend the money on the most significant aspects, like reducing the GHG emission. Meanwhile, Bellway should invest in advanced technologies and innovation for environmental sustainability.

In addition to the four private housebuilders, the thesis is expected to bring some implications and recommendations to other stakeholders in the housebuilding sector and the author.

Regarding social and environmental benefits, CSR achievements, SDGs in the UK housebuilding sector, it is typical to discuss the efforts with noticeable CSR features, like charity donation, building on local infrastructures. However, the practices and performance in the core issues that inhabitants care about have been less discussed. The thesis assesses the private housebuilder's performance for the benefits of society and the environment via examining how well the builders have helped with inhabitants' needs in supply, affordability, quality and environment protection. This systematic approach should raise an implication for the government, multiple organisations, scholars, inhabitants, and even the housebuilders themselves that instead of the traditional CSR efforts, actions related to the inhabitant's needs and concerns could be taken to contribute to the UK society and local communities.

In the performance assessment for the four housebuilders, only the performance in raising housing affordability is assessed as dissatisfactory. Regarding each performance metric, the affordability issue receives the most dissatisfaction responses. According to the comparative analysis, the fast growth of average selling price results in the boost in profit and the decrease in housing affordability, demonstrating the builders' intention to pursue high profitability but sacrifice housing affordability. Accordingly, one recommendation is raised for the government and policymakers that encourage more affordable supplies from the private housebuilders. Firstly, the national statistics only provide the specific affordable supplies based on the funding schemes to the public, making it difficult to evaluate the private housebuilder's accurate contributions in raising affordable

supplies. If possible, it suggests presenting the more specific affordable supplies statistics completed by different builders so that the local policymaker can assess the individual private builder's performance in the affordable supply within the local area. Secondly, most affordable supplies from the private housebuilders should be completed under the Section 106 project, which works as a compulsory requirement for the private housebuilders and might affect the private builder's initiative. Therefore, it suggests the policymaker should consider the new approaches to encourage more affordable suppliers from the private builders, like raising the prospective profits from the affordable supply, awarding the private builders with a high proportion of affordable supply in their total completions.

This research journal also brings implications for the author. Firstly, the four housebuilders' moderate performance in serving benefits of society and the environment enhances the author's interest in studying more private housebuilders' non-financial performance after 2010. The author plans to study one more housebuilder with an annual supply of over 10,000 and three more housebuilders with an annual supply between 1,000 to 5,000 units within the following year. With the four cases in this study, the future study is expected to draw a more generalised and credible conclusion. Secondly, the housebuilders' aspects of performance in 2020 are not analysed in this study. Therefore, the author's other academic interest is to study the Covid-19 pandemic's influence on large private housebuilders' financial and non-financial performance and compare it with the performance before the pandemic. Thirdly, the author is inspired to study the private housebuilders' social, environmental and financial performance in other countries. Then the author will compare the private housebuilder's performance in different countries.

7.4 Limitations of the Thesis

Like other studies, the thesis also has some limitations. Based on the research topic, the Covid-19 pandemic and the year 2020 are not included in some parts of the analysis because it is regarded as an exception that cannot represent the overall performance since 2010. Moreover, another reason is lacking literature about the housebuilding sector during the pandemic period and some secondary data of the private housebuilders. Therefore, neglecting the builder's performance during 2020 is one limitation of this thesis. It is known that the housing supply of almost all the housebuilders has been dropped for the financial year of 2020 because of the suspension of constructions works (HM Revenue & Customs, 2020). Meanwhile, the house selling price in the second half of 2020 was generally higher than the same period in 2019, which was boosted by the tax cut and increased mortgage approvals (Küçük, Lenoël and Macqueen, 2021). It predicts more uncertainties or a worse unbalance between housing supply and demands in the future housebuilding sector (Maunder, 2021). Based on the information, the author suggests a future study examining the private housebuilder's performance from 2020 until the post-pandemic periods. Furthermore, this thesis could be the relevant study before the Covid-19.

The thesis is conducted based on the case study. The generalisation of the research conclusions would be a concern. The author studies four housebuilders due to the limited time and source; therefore, the conclusion is more applicable within the selected cases or the private housebuilders with similar company profiles. The investigation should include more housebuilders to reach a generalised conclusion regarding the private housebuilder's performance for the benefits of society and the environment and their financial performance in the whole UK housebuilding sector.

Another limitation is the data collection. Because of the Covid-19, most questionnaires could only be sent out via the internet. As a result, it is hard to collect the data from a certain of responses with no or less access to the internet, like the elder respondent. This is one of the reasons for a relatively smaller number of respondents aged 65 years old or over. The author does not take age as a variable in this study. Therefore, the tiny group of responses from the older people would have fewer influences on the result. It suggests that for the future study with adequate respondents in all age groups, age might be taken as a variable when assessing the private housebuilder's non-financial performance.

The TBL theory is a foundation for developing the thesis's theoretical framework for performance assessment. Moreover, other trusted performance assessment models, like the balanced scorecard, are omitted. Considering the diverse elements in the social dimension of the TBL, the thesis only takes the perspective of inhabitants to refine the specific standards for social performance assessment. Therefore, as the author emphasised in the contribution part, the theoretical framework here only provides a new perspective to performance assessment but might not apply to a wide range of studies highlighting different stakeholders. Furthermore, for the research preferring other assessment models, taking other stakeholder perspectives, the applicability of the theoretical framework in this thesis is a limitation.

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APPENDIX

Appendix 1. Research Questionnaire

Before starting the following questions, the participant's consent and housebuilders will be confirmed. Once the responses match, the participant could start answering the questions.

Section 1: Questions of Demographic Information

1. What is your age?

A. Under 24

B. 25-34

C. 35-44

D. 45-54

E. 55-64

F. Over 65

2. What is your sex?

A. Male

B. Female

3. Which is the best option to describe your current occupation?

A. Student

B. Self-employed

C. Employed

D. Unemployed

E. Retirement

F. Other

4. Which is the best option to describe the place you currently live in?

- A. Detached house
- B. Semi-detached house
- C. Terraced house
- D. Flat
- E. Other

Section 2: Questions of Specific Performance Metrics

5. Based on what you know, how do you assess housebuilders' performance in raising housing supply in the UK from 2010 to 2020?

- A. Very satisfactory
- B. Satisfactory
- C. Neither satisfactory nor dissatisfactory (Moderate)
- D. Dissatisfactory
- E. Very dissatisfactory

6. Based on what you know, how do you assess housebuilders' performance in raising housing affordability in the UK from 2010 to 2020?

- A. Very satisfactory
- B. Satisfactory
- C. Neither satisfactory nor dissatisfactory (Moderate)
- D. Dissatisfactory
- E. Very dissatisfactory

7. Based on what you know, how do you assess housebuilders' performance in housing quality in the UK from 2010 to 2020?

- A. Very satisfactory
- B. Satisfactory
- C. Neither satisfactory nor dissatisfactory (Moderate)

D. Dissatisfactory

E. Very dissatisfactory

8. Based on what you know, how do you assess housebuilders' environmental performance in the UK from 2010 to 2020? (2 indicators for this question: GHG emission and waste generation)

A. Very satisfactory

B. Satisfactory

C. Neither satisfactory nor dissatisfactory (Moderate)

D. Dissatisfactory

E. Very dissatisfactory

Section 3. Questions of Overall Performance Assessment

9. Overall, how do you assess housebuilders' performance for the benefits of society and the environment in the UK from 2010 to 2020?

(Notes: following the theoretical framework in this research, please answer this question based on the responses in section 2.)

A. Very satisfactory

B. Satisfactory

C. Neither satisfactory nor dissatisfactory (Moderate)

D. Dissatisfactory

E. Very dissatisfactory

10. Based on what you know, how do you assess housebuilders' financial performance in the UK from 2010 to 2020?

A. Very high

B. High

C. Neither high nor low

D. Low

E. Very low

11. Which is the best option to describe the difference between the housebuilders' non-financial performance for benefits and the environment and the financial performance?

A. Financial performance far surpasses the non-financial performance

B. Financial performance moderately surpass the non-financial performance

C. Financial performance is equal to non-financial performance

D. Financial performance is moderately below non-financial performance

E. Financial performance is far below the non-financial performance

Appendix 2. Annual Housing Supply of the Four Housebuilders and Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR), 2010 to 2020.

Year	Private housebuilder	Barratt Developments	Persimmon	Bellway	Miller Homes
2010	105,250	11,377	9,384	4,595	1,915
2011	105,440	11,171	9,360	4,922	1,632
2012	107,700	12,857	9,903	5,226	1,831
2013	106,760	13,663	11,528	5,652	2,053
2014	115,080	14,838	13,509	6,851	2,181
2015	134,330	16,447	14,572	7,752	2,153
2016	139,280	17,319	15,171	8,721	2,380
2017	158,370	17,395	16,043	9,644	2,775
2018	161,600	17,579	16,449	10,307	3,170
2019	171,890	17,856	15,855	10,892	3,498

2020	N/A	12,604	13,575	7,522	2,620
Total		163,106	145,349	82,084	26,208

Source: Woodhill (2021a), annual report of Barratt, Persimmon, Bellway Miller Homes, 2010 to 2020

CAGR Calculation

		Private housebuilder	Barratt Developments	Persimmon	Bellway	Miller Homes
CAGR , 2010 to 2019	Beginning value (BV)	105,250	11,377	9,384	4,595	1,915
	Ending value (EV)	171,890	17,856	15,855	10,892	3,498
	Number of years (n)	10	10	10	10	10
		5.6%	5.1%	6.0%	10.1%	6.9%
CAGR , 2010 to 2020	BV	105,250	11,377	9,384	4,595	1,915
	EV	171,890	17,856	15,855	10,892	3,498
	n	11	11	11	11	11
		N/A	1.0%	3.8%	5.1%	3.2%

Appendix 3. Land bank of the Four Housebuilders (Years), 2010 to 2020

Year	Barratt Developments	Persimmon	Bellway	Miller Homes
2010	5.5	6.3	7.1	N/A
2011	5.4	6.5	6.3	N/A
2012	4.3	6.9	6.0	4.4
2013	4.4	6.5	5.8	4.3
2014	4.7	6.5	5.2	4.6
2015	4.5	6.3	4.7	5.4
2016	4.5	6.4	4.0	5.5
2017	4.5	6.1	3.9	5.1
2018	4.8	6	4.0	4.2
2019	4.7	5.9	3.9	4.1
2020	6.7	6.2	5.9	N/A

Source: annual report of Barratt, Persimmon, Bellway Miller Homes, 2010 to 2020

Appendix 4. Average Selling Price and CAGR, 2010 to 2020

Year	England	Barratt Developments	Persimmon	Bellway	Miller Homes
2010	£168,703	£174,300	£169,339	£163,200	£168,000
2011	£167,048	£178,300	£166,142	£175,613	£161,000
2012	£168,843	£180,500	£175,640	£186,648	£170,000
2013	£177,971	£194,800	£181,861	£193,025	£181,000
2014	£191,669	£219,900	£190,667	£213,182	£200,000

2015	£204,920	£235,000	£199,173	£223,800	£227,000
2016	£215,500	£259,700	£206,765	£252,800	£231,000
2017	£225,330	£275,200	£213,321	£260,400	£239,000
2018	£229,729	£288,900	£215,563	£284,900	£249,000
2019	£231,792	£274,400	£215,709	£291,968	£249,000
2020	£249,578	£280,300	£230,534	£293,054	£261,000

Source: Data collected from Office for National Statistics (2021), annual reports of Barratt, Persimmon, Bellway, Miller Homes, 2010 to 2020

CAGR Calculation

		Private housebuilder	Barratt Developments	Persimmon	Bellway	Miller Homes
CAGR, 2010 to 2019	BV	£168,703	£174,300	£169,339	£163,200	£168,000
	EV	£231,792	£274,400	£215,709	£291,968	£249,000
	n	10	10	10	10	10
		3.6%	5.2%	2.7%	6.7%	4.5%
CAGR, 2010 to 2020	BV	£168,703	£174,300	£169,339	£163,200	£168,000
	EV	£249,578	£280,300	£230,534	£293,054	£261,000
	n	10	10	10	10	10
		4.0%	4.9	3.1%	6.0%	4.5%

Appendix 5. Performance in Housing Quality, 2010 to 2019

Primary data: Four Housebuilders' Performance in Housing Quality

Performance	Barratt Developments	Persimmon	Bellway	Miller Homes
Very satisfactory	19.0%	0.0%	14.3%	9.5%
Satisfactory	54.8%	11.1%	31.0%	11.9%
Moderate	11.9%	42.2%	52.4%	78.6%
dis satisfactory	14.3%	44.4%	2.4%	4.8%
very dis satisfactory	0.0%	2.2%	0.0%	0.0%

National Customer Satisfaction Survey - Home Quality Satisfaction

Year	Home quality				
	Very satisfied	fairly satisfied	neither	fairly dissatisfied	very dissatisfied
2009/10	51%	37%	6%	4%	2%
2010/11	53%	37%	4%	4%	2%
2011/12	53%	38%	4%	3%	1%
2012/13	52%	38%	4%	4%	2%
2013/14	47%	39%	5%	6%	3%
2014/15	47%	39%	5%	6%	3%
2015/16	45%	39%	6%	7%	3%
2016/17	46%	39%	6%	6%	3%
2017/18	48%	38%	5%	6%	3%

2018/19	49%	37%	6%	5%	3%
2019/20	49%	39%	6%	4%	2%

Source: data collected from the HNBC national customer satisfaction, 2010 to 2021

National Customer Satisfaction Survey - Quality Problem Result, 2009/10 to 2019/20

Year	Quality problem			
	1-5	6-10	11-15	16 plus
2009/10	42%	31%	13%	14%
2010/11	44%	29%	13%	14%
2011/12	47%	30%	12%	11%
2012/13	42%	30%	13%	15%
2013/14	36%	29%	15%	20%
2014/15	34%	28%	16%	22%
2015/16	31%	28%	16%	25%
2016/17	31%	28%	16%	25%
2017/18	30%	28%	16%	26%
2018/19	32%	28%	15%	25%
2019/20	31%	28%	16%	25%

Source: data collected from the HNBC national customer satisfaction, 2010 to 2021

National Customer Satisfaction Survey - HBF Star Rating (star), 2009/10 to 2019/20

Year	Barratt Developments	Persimmon	Bellway	Miller Homes
2009/10	5	3	4	\
2010/11	5	4	5	5
2011/12	5	4	5	5

2012/13	5	4	5	5
2013/14	5	3	5	5
2014/15	5	3	4	5
2015/16	5	3	4	5
2016/17	5	3	5	4
2017/18	5	3	5	5
2018/19	5	4	5	5
2019/20	5	4	5	5

Source: data collected from the HNBC national customer satisfaction, 2010 to 2021

Appendix 6. Financial Performance and CAGR of the Four Housebuilders, 2010 to 2020

Group revenue (million)

	Barratt Developments	Persimmon	Bellway	Miller Homes
2010	£2,035.20	£1,569.50	£768.34	£320.36
2011	£2,035.40	£1,535.00	£886.10	£270.60
2012	£2,323.40	£1,721.40	£1,004.20	£265.16
2013	£2,606.20	£2,085.90	£1,110.70	£326.26
2014	£3,157.00	£2,573.90	£1,484.82	£387.50
2015	£3,759.50	£2,901.70	£1,765.41	£499.60
2016	£4,235.20	£3,136.80	£2,240.65	£565.30
2017	£4,650.20	£3,597.80	£2,558.56	£675.20
2018	£4,874.80	£3,737.60	£2,957.66	£747.00
2019	£4,763.10	£3,649.40	£3,213.20	£841.40
2020	£3,419.20	£3,328.30	£2,225.40	£664.80

Source: Data collected from annual reports of Barratt, Persimmon, Bellway, Miller Homes, 2010 to 2020

CAGR Calculation

		Barratt Developments	Persimmon	Bellway	Miller Homes
CAGR, 2010 to 2019	BV	£2,035.20	£1,569.50	£768.34	£320.36
	EV	£4,763.10	£3,649.40	£3,213.20	£841.40
	n	10	10	10	10
		9.9%	9.8%	17.2%	11.3%
CAGR, 2010 to 2020	BV	£2,035.20	£1,569.50	£768.34	£320.36
	EV	£3,419.20	£3,328.30	£2,225.40	£664.80
	n	11	11	11	11
		5.3%	7.8%	11.2%	7.6%

Profit before Tax (Million)

	Barratt Developments	Persimmon	Bellway	Miller Homes
2010	(£162.90)	£153.90	£44.43	(£134.92)
2011	(£11.50)	£147.20	£67.16	(£71.81)
2012	£100.00	£218.20	£105.28	(£9.26)
2013	£104.80	£337.10	£140.93	£6.94
2014	£390.60	£467.00	£246.00	£36.40
2015	£565.50	£629.50	£347.30	£62.00
2016	£682.30	£774.80	£480.60	£89.30
2017	£765.10	£966.10	£560.70	£119.50
2018	£835.50	£1,090.80	£641.10	£102.10
2019	£909.80	£1,048.10	£662.60	£122.10
2020	£491.80	£863.10	£236.70	£60.10

Source: Data collected from annual reports of Barratt, Persimmon, Bellway, Miller Homes, 2010 to 2020

CAGR Calculation

		Barratt Developments	Persimmon	Bellway	Miller Homes
CAGR, 2010 to 2019	BV	(£162.90)	£153.90	£44.43	(£134.92)
	EV	£909.80	£1,048.10	£662.60	£122.10
	n	10	10	10	10
		23.3%	23.8%	35.0%	7.4%
CAGR, 2010 to 2020	BV	(£162.90)	£153.90	£44.43	(£134.92)
	EV	£491.80	£863.10	£236.70	£60.10
	n	11	11	11	11
		14.9%	18.8%	18.2%	3.8%

Note: the adjusted CGRA formula is applied for calculating Barratt Developments and Miller Homes' growth rate.

Appendix7. The Ratio of Profit before Tax to per House Completion and Ratio Growth, 2010 to 2020

	Barratt Developments	Persimmon	Bellway	Miller Homes
2010	(£14,318.4)	£16,400.3	£9,669.9	(£70,454.8)
2011	(£1,029.5)	£15,726.5	£13,645.3	(£44,001.8)
2012	£7,777.9	£22,033.7	£20,146.2	(£5,055.7)
2013	£7,670.4	£29,241.8	£24,934.0	£3,379.0
2014	£26,324.3	£34,569.5	£35,907.5	£16,689.6
2015	£34,383.2	£43,199.3	£44,801.3	£28,797.0
2016	£39,396.0	£51,071.1	£55,108.4	£37,521.0
2017	£43,983.9	£60,219.4	£58,139.8	£43,063.1
2018	£47,528.3	£66,314.1	£62,200.4	£32,208.2
2019	£50,952.1	£66,105.3	£60,833.6	£34,905.7
2020	£39,019.4	£63,580.1	£21,731.5	£17,181.2

Source: Data collected from annual reports of Barratt, Persimmon, Bellway, Miller Homes, 2010 to 2020

Note: Formula is Profit before tax / Annual housing supply

CAGR Calculation

		Barratt Developments	Persimmon	Bellway	Miller Homes
CAGR, 2015 to 2019	BV	£34,383.2	£43,199.3	£44,801.3	£28,797.0
	EV	£50,952.1	£66,105.3	£60,833.6	£34,905.7
	n	5	5	5	5
		10.3%	11.2%	7.9%	4.9%

Appendix 8. Dividend Pay-out Ratio, 2010 to 2020

Calculation of dividend pay-out ratio

Year	Barratt			Persimmon			Bellway		
	Earnings per share	Dividend per share	Ratio	Earnings per share	Dividend per share	Ratio	Earnings per share	Dividend per share	Ratio
2010	N/A	N/A		38.3	7.5	19.6%	29.7	10	33.7%
2011	-1.4	N/A		36.1	10	27.7%	41.5	12.5	30.1%
2012	7	N/A		55.4	75	135.4%	65.5	20	30.5%
2013	7.7	2.5	32.5%	84.7	70	82.6%	89.3	30	33.6%
2014	31.2	10.3	33.0%	121.8	95	78.0%	157	52	33.1%
2015	45.5	25.1	55.2%	170.3	110	64.6%	231.5	77	33.3%
2016	55.1	30.7	55.7%	203	135	66.5%	328.7	108	32.9%
2017	61.3	41.7	68.0%	255	235	92.2%	370.6	122	32.9%
2018	66.5	43.8	65.9%	283.3	235	83.0%	423.4	143	33.8%
2019	73.2	46.4	63.4%	266.8	235	88.1%	437.8	150.4	34.4%
2020	39.4	N/A		200.3	110	54.9%	156.6	50	31.9%

Source: Data collected from annual reports of Barratt, Persimmon, Bellway, Miller Homes, 2010 to 2020

Note: Formula is unit of earnings per share/dividend per share